

INTERFEROMETRIC OBSERVATIONS OF GALACTIC OH EMISSION

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ABSTRACT

Measurements of the sizes and spatial distribution of the sources of OH emission at 1665 MHz near the HII regions W3, W24, W49, and NGC6334 are reported here. The initial measurements were made on W3 with an interferometer having a fringe spacing of 3" of arc. The spectral features were found to be unresolved but spatially separated from one another. The equipment and data processing technique was developed to make spectral line observations with interferometers having elements widely spaced and not connected to one another in real time. This was done in conjunction with the joint group from the National Radio Astronomy Observatory and the Arecibo Ionospheric Observatory. The tests of the phase stability of this system, which was controlled by atomic frequency standards, are reported here. Successive measurements of W3 with resolutions of 0.04, 0.01 and 0.005 seconds of arc have resolved all the features of this source. The individual features are typically found to consist of several components separated by about 0.02". The size of the smallest feature is 0.004" and its brightness temperature is 5×10^{12} °K. A map of the relative positions of the features was made which shows that the emission points are scattered over an area of about 3 square arc seconds. The separation between the two strongest features has not changed noticeably in a year's time. Maser models with IR or UV pumping can be adapted to fit the observed geometry. Typical feature sizes in NGC6334, W49, and W24 are 0.015, 0.05 and 0.09 seconds of arc respectively. It is suggested that the large angular sizes of W49 and W24 could be caused by interstellar scattering.

The results of an unsuccessful search for radiation from interstellar CH in the ground state are reported.

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The Agassiz-Millstone interferometer project was carried out in cooperation with the Harvard College Observatory and with much assistance from H. Penfield and B. M. Zuckerman and the staff of the Agassiz Field station.

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CHAPTER I

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The existence of the OH molecule as a constituent of the interstellar medium was confirmed by Weinreb, Barrett, Meeks and Henry (1963) in October, 1963. They detected absorption lines in the spectrum of the radio source Cassiopeia A at a wavelength of 18 centimeters due to transitions in the ground state lambda doublet of OH. Since its discovery, OH has been detected in emission, (Gundermann, 1965; Weaver, Williams, Dieter and Lum, 1965), and absorption in many parts of the galaxy. The emission was found to be linearly polarized by Weinreb, Meeks, Carter, Barrett and Rogers (1965) and circularly polarized by Barrett and Rogers (1966) and by Davies, de Jager, and Verschuur (1966). The first interferometer observations (Rogers, Moran, Crowther, Burke, Meeks, Ball and Hyde, 1966, 1967; Cudaback, Read and Rougoor, 1966) put an upper limit on the angular sizes of several OH emission sources of 20" of arc and a lower limit on the brightness temperature of 10^6 °K. The characteristics of the radiation are so startlingly different from those anticipated that the role of OH in the interstellar medium is far from being understood. It was hoped that the OH measurements would lead to a better understanding of star formation and interstellar processes. These goals have not been achieved yet.

The purpose of this thesis research was to measure the sizes and geometric structure of the OH emission sources. These measurements were done with a series of interferometers whose baselines were increased from $7.4 \times 10^4 \lambda$ to $4.2 \times 10^7 \lambda$ where the sources observed were finally resolved.

In this thesis, considerable space is devoted to describing the equipment and data processing techniques because new systems were built for the measurements and certain aspects of the data handling were novel. Chapter I describes the known characteristics of interstellar OH and its environment. An account is also given of an unsuccessful search for CH. In Chapter II the properties of interferometers are explained and in Chapter III the results of the $74,400\lambda$ interferometer are presented. In Chapters IV and V the operation of the long baseline interferometer is discussed along with a detailed account of the experimental data obtained on the OH emission sources. Chapter VI summarizes the findings.

1.2 THE INTERSTELLAR MEDIUM

Before discussing the properties of OH, some of the basic characteristics of the interstellar medium will be mentioned. Comprehensive treatment of this subject can be found in Nebulae and Interstellar Matter, Middlehurst and Aller (1968) and in a review article by Dieter and

Goss (1966). The "interstellar medium" includes all the matter in the galaxy exclusive of the stars. This matter is generally rather tenuous; typical electron densities being 0.1 electrons /cm³, yet it comprises between 1 and 10% of the total mass of the galaxy.

One interesting phenomenon in the interstellar medium is the emission nebula of which the Orion nebula is a well known example. Most OH emission sources are associated with nebulae of this type. A nebula is excited by O or B type stars whose ultraviolet radiation ionizes the surrounding hydrogen. When the hydrogen recombines the electrons cascade down to the ground level emitting radiation in the radio, infrared and optical regions of the spectrum. The radio recombination lines were predicted to have observable intensities by Kardashev (1959) and the $n = 110 \rightarrow n = 109$ transition, denoted 109 α , was detected by Hoglund and Mezger (1965). Surveys of radio recombination lines have been published by Mezger and Hoglund (1967), and by Dieter (1967). The region of ionized hydrogen is called an H II region and the surrounding unionized hydrogen is called an HI region. The transition between the two regions is very sharp, the ionized gas being roughly contained within a sphere called the Stromgren sphere whose radius is approximately

$$r_o \sim \left(\frac{3L}{4\pi\alpha} \right)^{1/3} n_H^{-2/3} \quad (1-1)$$

where

L = luminosity of exciting star

α = recombination coefficient

n_H = density of hydrogen

For $n_H = 10 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ $r_o = 30$ parsecs for an O5 exciting star.

For the sun $r_o \approx 10^{-4}$ parsecs. The temperature in the HII region is typically 10^4 °K and in the surrounding HI region, 10^2 °K. Because of HII regions, there is no free radiation beyond the Lyman limit of $912 \text{ \AA}$ since the hydrogen absorbs it all and reradiates the energy at longer wavelengths.

Large aggregates of atoms and molecules called grains are another constituent of the interstellar medium.

Several theories of the composition of grains have been set forth to explain the extinction and optical properties observed. Water may be a major constituent of the grains and it has been suggested that a large fraction of the heavy elements are locked up in them. They also may play a role in molecular formation.

Absorption lines have been observed in the spectra of hot stars and have been attributed to interstellar matter because they are narrow and do not share the velocities of the background stars. Sodium, iron, titanium, potassium, and calcium lines have been identified as well as lines of CH, CH⁺ and CN. Adams (1949) lists about 30 stars which show either CH or CH⁺ absorption. The optical band of OH which is near 3064 Å has never been detected partly because the atmospheric transmission is low at that wavelength. Bates and Spitzer (1951) and Stromgren (1948) have estimated the density of CH to be 10⁻⁶ and 10⁻⁸ molecules cm⁻³ respectively. The oscillator strengths of the optical lines of CH are not known accurately and thus make the density estimates uncertain. Other authors have also considered the problem of molecule formation. Carroll and Salpeter (1966) and Stecher and Williams (1966) discuss some mechanisms of OH formation.

There are undoubtedly many spectral lines of detectable intensity in the radio range. Unfortunately the spectral analysis techniques available in this range make frequency searches difficult. Spectral line measurements are well known in radio astronomy since the 21 cm transition of neutral hydrogen has been extensively investigated and has provided

important information on the structure of the galaxy.

Emission from other atoms and diatomic molecules such as SH, SiH and CH will probably be detected in the near future (Barrett 1964).

1.3 THE OH SPECTRUM

The physics of diatomic molecules is well documented in books by Herzberg (1950) and Townes and Schawlow (1955). The energy of a diatomic molecule such as OH, CH, SiH, SH is roughly represented by the sum of the rotational, vibrational and electronic energies:

$$E = E_R + E_V + E_e \quad (1-2)$$

The rotational energy for the end over end rotation with quantum number J' is

$$E = h B J'(J' + 1) \quad (1-3)$$

where B is 555 GHz, ($B/c = 18.52 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), for OH so that the first rotational level is in the far infrared. The vibrational energy with quantum number v is

$$E = h \nu_{\text{osc}} \left(v + \frac{1}{2} \right) \quad (1-4)$$

where $\nu_{\text{osc}}/c = 3735 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for OH. The electronic motion is

much more rapid than the rotational and vibrational motion of the molecule so it is assumed that the electrons move in an axially symmetric field. The electronic angular momentum is, therefore, quantized along the internuclear axis. Λ denotes the projection of the orbital angular momentum on this axis and the molecular state is designated as $\Sigma, \pi, \Delta \dots$ depending on whether Λ is 0, 1, 2 $\dots$. The ground state of OH is a π state and the only excited state is the Σ state. The wavelength of the $\Sigma - \pi$ transition is 3064 Å. OH dissociates just above the Σ state at 4.35 eV. OH has 9 electrons, the unpaired one giving rise to a net spin angular momentum S whose projection on the internuclear axis is Σ . The sum of Σ and Λ is denoted Ω . Finally the rotational quantum number is N . The coupling scheme for all these vectors is shown in figure 1-1. The case of interest is called Hund's case a. As N increases, the electron spin becomes uncoupled from the internuclear axis and the coupling shifts to Hund's case b. The ground state of OH is intermediate to these two cases, and is denoted

$${}^2_{\frac{3}{2}}\pi_3, J = \frac{3}{2}$$

where the superscript is equal to $2S + 1$ and the subscript is equal to $|\Lambda + \Sigma| = \Omega$ and J is the total angular momentum. The ground rotational level is split into two levels depending

FIGURE 1-1. HUND'S COUPLING, CASES A AND B.

FIGURE 1-2. ENERGY LEVEL DIAGRAM OF OH. LAMBDA DOUBLING NOT SHOWN.

on whether Σ equal $+\frac{1}{2}$ or $-\frac{1}{2}$. The energy difference is proportional to the fine structure constant A which is -139.7 cm^{-1} for OH, the negative sign indicating that the ${}^2\Pi_{3/2}$ state lies lower than the ${}^2\Pi_{1/2}$. The various energy levels of OH are shown in figure 1-2.

The degeneracy in Λ for $\Lambda \neq 0$ is removed through interaction between the electronic and rotational motions of the molecule in a phenomenon called lambda doubling which is described by Van Vleck (1929), Mullikan and Christy (1931) and Dousmanis, Sanders and Townes (1955). These levels are further split through hyperfine interaction with the hydrogen nucleus. The resulting four energy levels are shown in figure 1-3 along with a sketch depicting the probability distribution of the unpaired electron. The relative intensities of the four lines are approximately 1:5:9:1 in an optically thin medium. The four L band frequencies listed were measured in the laboratory by Radford (1964) with the exception that the 1720 GHz frequency was adjusted so that the sum rule is obeyed, (Goss, 1967).

The brightness temperature T_B is related to the intensity I_ν (watts-meter⁻² - Hz⁻¹ - steradian⁻¹) by $I_\nu = 2kT_B \nu^2 / c^2$ in the radio region. The brightness temperature observed in the direction of an OH cloud is predicted by the solution to the equation of radiative transfer. If the cloud, shown in figure 1-4, has an optical depth τ_ν and an excitation temperature

FIGURE 1-3
 ENERGY LEVELS AND SPECTRUM OF THE $^2\Pi_{3/2}, J=3/2$ STATE OF OH

FIGURE 1-4

A POSSIBLE GEOMETRY FOR OH ABSORPTION

T_{EX} and refractive effects are neglected, then

$$T_B = T_c e^{-\tau_\nu} + T_{EX} (1 - e^{-\tau_\nu}) \quad (1-5)$$

where T_c is the brightness temperature of any background continuum source. The optical depth is given by

$$\tau_\nu = \int_0^L K_\nu dl = \frac{8\pi^3 \nu^2 |\mu_{10}|^2}{3ck T_{EX}} \frac{g_1}{g_0} f(\nu) \int_0^L n_0 dl \quad (1-6)$$

where

K = Boltzmann's constant

L = length of cloud

K_ν = absorption coefficient

ν = frequency

g_1, g_0 = statistical weights of upper and lower energy levels respectively.

$\int n_0 dl = \frac{g_0}{\sum g_i} N_{OH}$ = number of OH molecules in lower level

N_{OH} = total number of OH molecules

μ_{10} = matrix element of transition

$f(\nu)$ = line shape factor

The matrix element is proportional to the electric dipole

moment of OH which is $1.72 \pm .02 \times 10^{-18}$ esu, (Phelps and Dalby, 1965).

$|\mu_{10}|^2$ for the lambda doublet, unsplit by hyperfine interaction

is 2.4×10^{-36} esu.

The excitation temperature is defined for any two energy levels 1 and 0 as

$$\frac{n_1}{n_0} = \frac{g_1}{g_0} e^{-\frac{h\nu}{KT_{EX}}} \quad (1-7)$$

where n_1 and n_0 are the number of molecules in the upper and lower levels respectively. If the cloud is in statistical equilibrium and the relative populations of the levels are determined by the collisional process and the microwave radiation field, then the excitation temperature is

$$T_{EX} \sim T_K \frac{T_0 + T_R}{T_0 + T_K} \quad (1-8)$$

where

T_R = radiation temperature

T_K = kinetic temperature of gas

and

$$T_0 = \frac{h\nu}{k} \frac{R_{10}}{A_{10}} \sim \frac{\tau_{Radiation}}{\tau_{Collision}} \quad (1-9)$$

R_{10} and A_{10} are the collisional and spontaneous emission probabilities and $\tau_{Collision}$ and $\tau_{Radiation}$ are the corresponding

lifetimes. For the 21 cm hydrogen line which is a magnetic dipole transition, the radiative lifetime is much greater than the collision time so that the excitation temperature is close to the kinetic temperature of the electrons which is about 100 °K, (Field, 1958). Rogers and Barrett (1968) estimated the excitation temperature of normal OH to be about 30 °K when $n_H \sim 10 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Goss (1967) estimates 20 °K for the same hydrogen density. The lack of emission near the galactic center absorption suggests that the excitation temperature is less than 10 °K, (Goldstein, Gundermann, Penzias, and Lilley, 1964). To explain the intense emission of OH, Litvak, McWhorter, Meeks and Zeiger (1964) have included the effects of ultra-violet radiation which is selectively absorbed by the cloud and can produce a negative T_{EX} .

The observable quantity in radio astronomy is antenna temperature, T_A , which is the convolution of the antenna gain function, G , with the brightness distribution T_B . That is,

$$T_A(x,y) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{\text{Source}} T_B(X',Y') G(X-X',Y-Y') dx'dy' \quad (1-10)$$

where x,y are linear coordinates over a small portion of the sky. If the source is small with respect to the antenna beam, then the maximum antenna temperature is

$$T_A = T_B \frac{\Omega_S}{\Omega_B} \quad (1-11)$$

where Ω_S and Ω_B are the solid angles subtended by the source and antenna beam respectively. The measured difference between the antenna temperature on the line and off the line for the simple geometry of figure (1-4) is

$$\Delta T_A(\nu) = \frac{\Omega_S}{\Omega_B} (T_{EX} - T_C) (1 - e^{-\tau_\nu}) \quad (1-12)$$

If the cloud is large, then whether the source appears in emission or absorption can depend on the size of the antenna beam. The precise expression for ΔT_A is obtained by substituting equation (1-5) into equation (1-10).

1.4 CLASSIFICATION OF OH SOURCES

The only other transition of OH that has been observed astronomically, besides the ground state at 18 cm, is the $^2\Pi_{1/2}$ $J=1/2$ line, (Zuckerman, 1968). It was detected in W3 and possibly in W49 and NGCG334. The features were unpolarized and the antenna temperature was about 1% of the values obtained at 18 cm. The bulk of the observations have been done on the $^2\Pi_{3/2}$, $J=3/2$ transition. The sources observed in this transition fall into roughly four, possibly arbitrary, categories suggested by Turner (1967). Class IV is the normal OH emission found recently by Heiles (1968). The emission extends over

several square degrees near dust clouds and has a brightness temperature of about 1 °K. The ratio of the main lines is 5:9 and the line widths are about 10KHz. Class III includes the sources of anomalous absorption. Goss (1967) measured OH absorption profiles in 26 galactic radio sources. In general, the line profiles are not the same among the transitions and the intensities could not be explained by a single excitation temperature. The mean feature width is 5.8 km/s and the mean ratio of OH to neutral hydrogen N_{OH}/N_H , is 4.5×10^{-8} on the assumption $T_{EX(OH)} = 3$ °K. The sources W28, W41, W42, W43 and W81 exhibit a 5:9 absorption ratio in the main lines but show emission in either or both of the satellite lines. These are called Class II sources. Class I includes the sources which show strong anomalous emission in the main lines such as W3, W49, NGC6334 and W24. These four sources are the ones examined in this thesis work. Table 1 - 1 lists some of the characteristics of these OH sources and the associated HII regions. The distance between the peak of the radio continuum radiation and the OH source varies. In W3, the OH source lies 14' of arc from the main nebula. However, a small continuum source has been found at the OH position, (Aikman, 1967; Mezger, Altenhoff, Schraml, Burke, Reifenstein and Wilson, 1967). In W49 the OH at position 1 is coincident with the thermal source (Mezger, Schraml, Terzian, 1967).

TABLE 1-1
 INFORMATION ABOUT THE STRONGEST OH EMISSION SOURCES AND ASSOCIATED HII REGIONS

SOURCE	HII REGION POSITION**	OH POSITION *		OH POSITION		$V_{H\alpha}$ ^{**} km/s	EM ^{**} cm ³ kpc	D kpc	V_{OH} km/s	R_1	R_2
		α (HMS) δ (DMS)	α (HMS) δ (DMS)	l Deg	b Deg						
W3	2 21 55 61 51 59	2 23 16.7 $\pm$.2 61 38 54 $\pm$ 1	133.95	1.06	-42.3	540	2.6	-41, -50	1	2	
NGC6334(1)	17 17 12 -35 45 58	17 17 32.1 $\pm$.4 -35 44 15 $\pm$.4	351.41	0.64	-2.5	250	0.7	0, -13	3	4	
W24	17 44 07 -28 21 36	17 44 10.7 $\pm$.4 -28 22 51 $\pm$.3	0.66	-.04	61.6	500	10.0	52, 76	5	6	
W49(1)	19 07 54 09 01 01	19 07 49.9 $\pm$.4 09 01 18 $\pm$.2	43.17	.01	8.6	1900	13.8	0, 25	7	6	

** From Reifenstein (1968). * From Raimond and Eliasson (1968). These positions appear to be more accurate than those reported by Rogers et al. (1967).

HEADINGS: $V_{H\alpha}$ = Recombination line velocity, EM = Emission Measure = $\int n_e^2 dl$, D = kinematic distance, R_1 is reference for map of continuum emission, R_2 is reference for OH spectra.

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6. Palmer and Zuckerman, (1967).
7. Mezger, Schraml and Terzian, (1967).

The sources in class I have spectra which are different for each transition in the multiplet. The features in the spectra are highly polarized, typically either 100% pure left circular or 100% pure right circular.

This situation cannot be explained by the Zeeman effect and a multiplicity of clouds as was pointed out by Barrett and Rogers (1966). The emission features have been shown to originate from regions of very small angular size, (Rogers, et al 1967). The brightness temperature of the features in W3 is about 10^{12} °K (Moran, Burke, Barrett, Rogers, Ball, Carter, Cudaback, 1968). The widths of non-overlapping features varies from about 600 Hz to 2000 Hz corresponding to temperatures between 4 °K and 50 °K.

The strongly non-thermal characteristics of the emission may be due to maser amplification in the OH cloud. In this case equation (1-5) becomes

$$T_B = T_c e^{|\tau_\nu|} + |T_{EX}| (e^{|\tau_\nu|} - 1) \quad (1-13)$$

where τ_ν and T_{EX} are negative. If τ_ν has a Gaussian profile due to thermal broadening, then the ratio of the amplified line width to the unamplified line width is $1/\sqrt{\tau}$ if the maser is unsaturated. For example, if $\tau = 25$ the gain is 10^{11} and the linewidth is reduced by a factor of 5. Following Robinson (1967) and using equations (1-13) and (1-6), if $T_c = 10$ °K and

$e^{\tau} = 10^{11}$ and the population inversion is 10%, ($T_{EX} \sim -1$ °K), then the OH cloud contains 10^{49} OH molecules. If the O:H ratio is 1:1500 and the fraction α of the oxygen atoms have formed OH, then the cloud has $1.5 \times 10^{52}/\alpha$ hydrogen atoms and a mass of $10^{-5}/\alpha M_{\odot}$. If the maser is saturated; i.e., the power output is limited by the pump rate, then the mass may be much greater.

The question of what the maser is amplifying and what the images seen by the interferometer are, remain unanswered. If the maser amplifies the radiation from a small source behind the OH cloud, then the observer on earth sees an image which has the shape of this source because of the spatial coherence properties of the maser amplifier. The same situation is true if there are small condensations within the OH cloud itself which supply the input signal. If the spontaneous emission of the OH cloud itself is being amplified, then the observed size is the size of the whole OH cloud but with apparent dimensions reduced in the same way that the spectral width of the radiation is narrowed; i.e., by a factor of about 5.

A theory to explain the polarization characteristics has been worked out in a saturated maser model by Heer and Settles (1967).

Rogers (1967) estimates that the total flux from all the features in W3 is 3×10^{-20} watts/meter². If the distance is

assumed to be 2600 parsec, then this is equivalent to 2×10^{21} watts of power radiated isotropically. The maser's pump must supply this power.

Several suggestions have been made as to the nature of the pump; i.e., the mechanism producing the population inversion. Litvak, et. al, (1966) proposed ultraviolet pumping. In the original presentation of the model, the OH cloud surrounds an O5 type star at a distance of about one parsec. The ultraviolet excites the OH to the $^2\Sigma^+$ state which then decays back to the ground state via the excited rotational levels of the $^2\Pi$ state. They showed that as the UV radiation proceeds through the OH cloud the part of the UV spectrum which tends to anti-invert the lambda doublet is absorbed out leaving only the radiation capable of inverting the ground state levels. Zuckermann (1968) describes other geometries for the UV pump model which conform to the measured cloud sizes.

Infrared pumping has been proposed by Shlovskii (1965) and investigated by Litvak (1968) and Zuckerman (1968). This model can produce inversion and appears attractive since the OH source in Orion has been shown to be coincident with an IR star, (Raimond and Elisson, 1967). Mennon (1967) suggested that the OH is part of a protostar. Such a star in the process of formation should have intense infrared emission. Others have suggested that OH originates in regions where stars are being formed.

Other pump mechanisms which might play a role are chemical pumping (Solomon, 1968), microwave pumping (Rogers, 1967), and collisional pumping (Johnston, Turner, 1967).

No detailed analysis of any non-maser mechanism has been published. Rogers (1968), however, has suggested that refraction effects might be capable of focusing the radiation from a background source such as a quasi-stellar radio source having brightness temperature and produce many of the observed effects.

1.5 SEARCH FOR CH ("METHYLADYNE")

Skhlovsky (1960) suggested that a search should be made for CH and discussed the possibility of detecting it. The exciting observations of galactic OH and a new laboratory determination of the ground state lambda doublet splitting of CH prompted the search in April, 1966. Furthermore, CH was known to exist in the interstellar medium, Adams (1949).

Unlike OH, the ground rotation state of CH is not an inverted doublet so that the $^2\Pi_{1/2}$, $J = \frac{1}{2}$, state has the lowest energy. The $F = 0 \rightarrow 0$ transition in the lambda doublet is forbidden so that the multiplet has three lines with relative intensities of 1:2:1 as shown in figure 1-5. The energies of the levels could be calculated from equation (33) in the paper by Dousmanis, Sanders and Townes (1955) if the molecular

constants were known well enough. The ratio of the fine structure constant and the rotational constant, $\lambda = A/B$, is close to 2.0 for CH. This is a critical value in the molecular theory and it is difficult to estimate the splitting of the energy levels with any accuracy. Much more serious a problem than determining the hyperfine energies is determining the frequency of the lambda doublet. The microwave transition is difficult to measure directly because of the short lifetime of the free radicals. Several laboratory attempts have failed, so far, (Strandberg, 1966; Radford, 1966). Douglas and Elliot (1965) reported a value of 3403 ± 33 MHz (75% confidence) which they obtained by extrapolating to the ground state the measurements of the lambda doublet energy separations for the excited rotational states of the $^2\Delta - ^2\Pi$ band of CH near $4300 \text{ \AA}$. Miles (1966) at M.I.T. used a Fabry-Perot interferometer to duplicate the technique of Douglas and Elliot and, also, to measure the difference in frequency between transitions from an excited level to each of the two lambda doublet levels (ignoring hyperfine splitting) of the ground state. The spectra obtained showed the two lines which were thermal broadened and, hence, heavily overlapped so that the dip between them was about 10% of the total line intensity. The frequency separation was found to be 3380 ± 40 MHz. The

FIGURE 1-5

Spectrum of ground state lambda doublet of CH, $^2\Pi_{1/2}$, $J=1/2$.

FIGURE 1-6

BLOCK DIAGRAM OF 9 CENTIMETER RADIOMETER

TABLE 1-2

OBSERVED ABSORPTION OF OH AND EXPECTED ABSORPTION OF CH

SOURCE	OH				CH			
	T_A^* °K	ΔT_A °K	τ	$\Delta\nu$ KHz	T_A^* °K	ΔT_A °K	τ	$\Delta\nu$ KHz
SAG A	120	38	0.30	~300	50	12	0.24**	750
CAS A	700	11	0.016	{ 5 } { 15 }	300	4	0.013	{ 7 }*** { 35 }

* Measured on the NRAO 140 foot antenna.

** The opacity is probably higher if CH absorption comes from small condensations of high opacity like the OH does.

*** Lines may be narrower since the OH features have multiple components.

astronomical search was centered on this frequency.

The search was concentrated in absorption measurements because of the inherently greater sensitivity they afford compared with emission measurements in a normal situation.

The ratio of CH opacity to OH opacity is

$$\frac{\tau_{\text{CH}}}{\tau_{\text{OH}}} = \frac{\nu_{\text{CH}}^2 \left| \frac{\mu_{10}}{10} \right|^2_{\text{CH}}}{\nu_{\text{OH}}^2 \left| \frac{\mu_{10}}{10} \right|^2_{\text{OH}}} \cdot \frac{T_{\text{EX}}(\text{OH})}{T_{\text{EX}}(\text{CH})} \frac{\Delta\nu_{\text{OH}}}{\Delta\nu_{\text{CH}}} \frac{N_{\text{CH}}}{N_{\text{OH}}} \quad (1-14)$$

where $\Delta\nu$ is the line width and N_{OH} and N_{CH} are the number of OH and CH molecules in the cloud, virtually all of which are assumed to be in the ground state. Without more detailed knowledge one can only assume that $T_{\text{EX}_{\text{OH}}} = T_{\text{EX}_{\text{CH}}} \sim 3^\circ\text{K}$.

Since the transition probability, A , is greater for CH than OH, it appears at first glance that $T_{\text{EX}_{\text{CH}}}$ would not be greater than $T_{\text{EX}_{\text{OH}}}$. $N_{\text{CH}}/N_{\text{OH}}$ is set equal to $N_{\text{C}}/N_{\text{O}}$ which

is 0.45 from the cosmic abundances given by Allen (1955).

This assumption may be very bad since it ignores all the differences in the formation and destruction processes between the two molecules. It is not inconsistent with the mean density of OH found by Goss (1967) of $4.5 \times 10^{-8} \times n_{\text{H}}$ and the density of CH, determined optically, of $10^{-8} - 10^{-6}$

molecules cm^{-3} . $\Delta\nu_{\text{OH}}/\Delta\nu_{\text{CH}}$ is equal to 0.425 if the thermal broadening is scaled. The ratio of the electric dipole moment of CH to that of OH was measured by Phelps and Dalby (1966) as 0.84 from which $|\mu_{10}|^2_{\text{CH}} / |\mu_{10}|^2_{\text{OH}} \approx 2.0$. Combining these calculations gives

$$\frac{\tau_{\text{CH}}}{\tau_{\text{OH}}} \sim 0.8 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\Delta\nu_{\text{CH}}}{\Delta\nu_{\text{OH}}} = 2.5, \quad (1-15)$$

results which are more notable for ease in remembrance than for accuracy.

The search was done with the 140 foot antenna of the National Radio Astronomy Observatory. The radiometer, whose block diagram is shown in figure 1-6, consisted of a traveling wave tube amplifier followed by a voltage tunable filter, to remove the image band, intermediate frequency conversion stages and a digital autocorrelator. The local oscillator was phase locked to a crystal oscillator. Linear polarization was used and the antenna efficiency was about 50%. The correlator was not working properly and the spectra had curved baselines, a situation which was corrected by differencing adjacent frequency scans. The problem was unrelated to the 7 MHz baseline ripple caused by standing waves between the feed and reflector. The radiometer was operated in switched mode and the correlator bandwidth was always set at

2.5 MHz giving a resolution of 50 KHz. The receiver was tunable over a range from 2900 MHz to 3600 MHz. Recombination lines in Orion and M17 were periodically observed to check the system performance. Figure 1-7 shows the 128 α line in M17, obtained with 2 hours of integration.

Table 1-2 gives a guideline of the expected results based on the OH measurements and the predicted opacity ratio. No CH or any other unidentified astronomical lines were observed. The sources observed, the frequencies covered and the sensitivities achieved are tabulated in table 1-3. About forty hours of integration time was spent on both Cas A and Sag A, looking for CH in absorption. In both sources the line should have been seen if the uncertain quoted by either Douglas and Elliot or by Goss was realistic and if the opacity calculation was correct. Several dark clouds where CH had been seen optically were searched for emission. These regions are not unlike those in which extended normal emission with brightness temperatures of 1 °K and line widths of 10 KHz have been detected by Heiles. Our sensitivity was almost adequate enough to see the "normal CH" if it scales by equation (1-15). Turner (1967) reported that CH should be capable of the same maser amplification as OH; however, no significant amount of time was spent looking at the positions of the strong OH emission sources.

FIGURE 1-7

M 17

HYDROGEN EMISSION LINE

$$n_{129} - n_{128}$$

REST FREQUENCY: 3099.368 MC/S

ANTENNA TEMPERATURE

$20 \mu / s = 5.00 \text{ KHz}$
 $\frac{14}{20} \times 500 =$

3098.571 3098.870 3099.370 3099.870 3100.370

FREQUENCY MC/S

TABLE 1-3

SUMMARY OF RESULTS OF SEARCH FOR INTERSTELLAR CH, APRIL 1966.

SOURCE	RIGHT ASCENSION	DECLINATION	FREQUENCY RANGE	INTEGRATION TIME	ΔT_A (rms)	MINIMUM DETECTABLE OPACITY*
	Epoch 1950	Epoch 1950	MHz	Seconds	$^{\circ}\text{K}$	
CAS A	$23^{\text{h}} 21.2^{\text{m}}$	$58^{\circ} 33'$	3000-3020	300	0.9	0.015
			3071-3086	300	0.9	0.015
			3129-3340	20	3.5	0.057
			3340-3373	1800	0.4	0.006
			3373-3470	1200	0.4	0.007
SAG A	$17^{\text{h}} 42.5^{\text{m}}$	$-28^{\circ} 55'$	2953-3131**	20	2.5	0.310
			3251-3257	900	0.4	0.045
			3329-3369	1800	0.3	0.032
			3369-3421	1200	0.3	0.040
			3421-3455	300	0.6	0.080
			3455-3485	1200	0.3	0.040
			3485-3519	1800	0.3	0.032
AE AURIGAE	$5^{\text{h}} 9.7^{\text{m}}$	$34^{\circ} 12'$	3342-3362	1800	0.3	
			3362-3412	300	0.6	
LYNDS-317 ⁺	$16^{\text{h}} 58.0^{\text{m}}$	$-8^{\circ} 0'$	3353-3403	1200	0.3	
LYNDS-1470	$4^{\text{h}} 50.0^{\text{m}}$	$30^{\circ} 50'$	3343-3381	1800	0.3	
			3381-3401	1200	0.6	

* Equal to $5\Delta T_A/T$ CONTINUUM

** The SiH lambda doublet ground state is thought to be in this range.

+ Lynds (1962)

Subsequent to our observations, Goss (1966) reported an improved laboratory interferometric study of the ${}^2\Delta - {}^2\Pi (0,0)$ band of CH. He obtained 3030^{+60}_{-30} MHz from a direct measurement and 3400^{+36}_{-30} from the procedure used by Douglas and Elliot which relies on the molecular theory of Van Vleck. Goss suggests that the Van Vleck theory is inapplicable to the ${}^2\Pi_{1/2}$ state but does not satisfactorily explain the discrepancy. Furthermore, the direct measurement is similar to the one used by Miles who obtained 3380 MHz.

No details of searches for interstellar CH have been published, but references to other such attempts have been made at the Commonwealth Scientific Industrial Research Organization, University of California at Berkeley, and Air Force Cambridge Research Laboratory.

Naturally it was desired to extend the search to greater sensitivity and frequency coverage. To this end a radiometer was built for the Millstone Antenna and a 3.3 GHz feed purchased. Because of the pressing demands of OH interferometry, the Millstone observations have not been undertaken.

CHAPTER II

INTERFEROMETRY

2.1 BASIC INTERFEROMETRY

A simple radio interferometer, drawn in figure 2-1, consists of two antennas, each followed by an amplifier and filter, to restrict the bandwidth of the signal, and by quadrature multipliers. A single plane wave induces a voltage $x(t)$ in receiver 1 and $x(t-\tau_G)$ in receiver 2 so that the output of the multipliers is

$$P_1 = \langle |X(\omega)|^2 \rangle \cos \omega \tau_G \quad (2-1)$$

$$P_2 = \langle |X(\omega)|^2 \rangle \sin \omega \tau_G$$

which can be combined to give

$$S = P_1 + j P_2 = |S| e^{j\omega \tau_G} \quad (2-2)$$

where $x(\omega)$ is the spectrum of $x(t)$ and τ_G is the difference in arrival time of the plane wave at the two stations. The baseline vector $\vec{B}$ is the vector joining the two receiving elements as shown in figure 2-2. If $\hat{s}$ is a unit vector in the source direction, then

$$\tau_G = \frac{1}{C} \vec{B} \cdot \hat{s} \quad (2-3)$$

or

$$\tau_G = \frac{D}{C} [\sin \delta_B \sin \delta_S + \cos \delta_B \cos \delta_S \cos(L_S - L_B)]$$

FIGURE 2-1. BLOCK DIAGRAM OF A SIMPLE RADIO ASTRONOMICAL INTERFEROMETER WITH QUADRATURE MULTIPLIERS.

using the celestial coordinate system defined in figure 2-2 where C is the velocity of light. The subscripts B and S refer to baseline and source coordinates respectively. It is sometimes convenient to express the delay in the azimuth-elevation coordinate system of one of the sites. In this case

$$\tau_G = \frac{D}{C} [\sin E_B \sin E_S + \cos E_B \cos E_S \cos (A_S - A_B)] \quad (2-4)$$

where E_B and E_S are the elevations of the baseline and source respectively and A_B and A_S are the azimuth angles.

The earth's rotation causes τ_G to change with time in a way specified by equation (2-3) or (2-4) so that the power from each of the multipliers varies sinusoidally with time. The total fringe phase, defined as $\omega \tau_G$, can be expanded in a Taylor series in time t giving

$$\phi = \omega \tau_G \sim \phi_0 + \omega \frac{d\tau_G}{dt} t = \phi_0 + \omega_f t \quad (2-5)$$

where $\omega_f = \frac{D}{\lambda} \cos \delta_B \cos \delta_S \sin(L_B - L_S) \frac{dL_S}{dt}$

ω_f is called the fringe frequency. The fringes are a manifestation of the fact that one antenna of the interferometer is moving towards the source faster than the other, thus producing a doppler frequency shift between the received signals.

Figure 2-2. Interferometer Baseline Geometry

P = Celestial North Pole S = Source
 Z = Local zenith at site 1 B = Baseline

$A_B, A_S, E_B, E_S, L_B, L_S, \delta_B, \delta_S$ are the azimuth, elevation, local hour angle, and declination of baseline and source respectively measured at site 1.

This phenomenon is basically undesirable so that in the data processing, S is usually multiplied by $e^{-j\omega\tau'_G}$ where τ'_G is the delay calculated on the best knowledge of the source and baseline positions. The resultant phase is

$$\Delta\phi = \omega(\tau_G - \tau'_G) \approx \omega \left[\frac{d\tau_G}{d\delta_S} \Delta\delta_S - \frac{d\tau_G}{dL_S} \Delta\alpha_S \right] \quad (2-6)$$

if it is assumed to depend only on the errors in the assumed direction of arrival of the plane wave; i.e., $\Delta\alpha_S =$ source right ascension error; $\Delta\delta_S =$ source declination error.

The interferometer response is thus

$$S = (I d\Omega A) e^{-j\Delta\phi} \quad (2-7)$$

where $I d\Omega$ is the flux of the infinitesimal source and A is the collecting area of the antenna and

$$\Delta\phi = 2\pi \frac{D}{\lambda} \left\{ \left[\sin \delta_B \cos \delta_S - \cos \delta_B \sin \delta_S \cos(L_S - L_B) \right] \Delta\delta_S + \cos \delta_B \cos \delta_S \sin(L_S - L_B) \Delta\alpha_S \right\} \quad (2-8)$$

Letting

$$\begin{aligned}
s_x &= \left[\cos \delta_B \sin(L_S - L_B) \right] \frac{D}{\lambda} \\
s_y &= \left[\sin \delta_B \cos \delta_S - \cos \delta_B \sin \delta_S \cos(L_S - L_B) \right] \frac{D}{\lambda} \\
x &= \Delta \delta_S \\
y &= \cos \delta_S \Delta \alpha_S
\end{aligned}
\tag{2-9}$$

the response is

$$S = (I \, d\Omega \, A) e^{-j2\pi(s_x x + s_y y)} \tag{2-10}$$

s_x and s_y are just the components of the baseline vector projected onto the celestial sphere in the direction of the source. s_x and s_y are also equal to $\partial \Delta \phi / \partial x$ and $\partial \Delta \phi / \partial y$ respectively. If a course consists of a continuum of independent radiators, then the interferometer response becomes

$$S = \frac{2k}{4\pi} \int_{\text{Source}} T_B(x,y) e^{-j2\pi(s_x x + s_y y)} G(x,y) \, dx \, dy \tag{2-11}$$

where we have used the relations

$$I_\nu(x,y) = \frac{2k}{\lambda} T_B(x,y)$$

$$G(x,y) = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda^2} A(x,y)$$

$$d\Omega = dx \, dy$$

T_B is the brightness temperature and G is the single antenna gain and λ is the wavelength and k is Boltzmann's constant. Assuming a source smaller than the beam width is being investigated, then the antenna gain can be removed from the integral and the integral limits extended to infinity with the realization that the single antenna response prevents interference from sources far away from the one under investigation.

Hence,

$$S(\vec{\Delta}) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} T_B(\vec{r}) e^{-j2\pi\vec{\Delta}\cdot\vec{r}} d\vec{r} \quad (2-12)$$

where the factor $2k/\Omega_B$, where Ω_B is the solid angle of the single antenna beam, has been dropped. Also,

$$\vec{r} = x \hat{x} + y \hat{y} = \text{position vector}$$

$$\vec{\Delta} = s_x \hat{x} + s_y \hat{y} = \text{baseline vector}$$

$\hat{x}$ and $\hat{y}$ are unit vectors in the East and North directions on the celestial sphere. The normalized fringe visibility is defined as

$$A(\vec{\Delta}) = \frac{\int \int T_B(\vec{r}) e^{-j2\pi\vec{\Delta}\cdot\vec{r}} d\vec{r}}{\int \int T_B(\vec{r}) d\vec{r}} \quad (2-13)$$

$S(\vec{\Delta})$ is the fringe visibility in °K and $A(\vec{\Delta})$ is the normalized fringe visibility whose magnitude is called the fringe amplitude

and whose phase is called the fringe phase. The inversion of equation (2-12) is

$$T_B(\vec{r}) = \iint S(\vec{\lambda}) e^{2\pi j \vec{\lambda} \cdot \vec{r}} d\lambda \quad (2-14)$$

Interferometry is thus reduced to Fourier transform theory.

Since $T_B(\vec{r})$ is a real function, turning the baseline end for end has no effect other than reverse the phase; that is

$$S(-\vec{\lambda}) = S^*(\lambda) \quad (2-15)$$

Polar coordinates can be used:

$$\begin{aligned} s_x &= s \cos p & s_y &= s \sin p \\ x &= r \cos \psi & y &= r \sin \psi \end{aligned} \quad (2-16)$$

so that

$$S(s, p) = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\infty T(r, \psi) e^{j2\pi sr \cos(\psi-p)} r dr d\psi \quad (2-17)$$

This is useful particularly if T is circularly symmetric, in which case

$$S(s) = 2\pi \int_0^{\infty} T(r) J_0(2\pi sr) r dr \quad (2-18)$$

$$T(r) = 2\pi \int_0^{\infty} S(s) J_0(2\pi sr) s ds$$

This pair of equations is called the Hankel transform.

Particularly simple examples of circularly symmetric sources are a uniformly bright disc, a Gaussian disc and a ring, all of which have diameter denoted by a , and transforms given by

$$T(r) = \begin{cases} 1 & r < a/2 \\ 0 & r > a/2 \end{cases} \quad \begin{cases} J_1\left(\pi \frac{a}{\theta}\right) \\ \frac{1}{\theta} \left(\pi \frac{a}{\theta}\right) \end{cases} \quad (2-19)$$

$$T(r) = e^{-\frac{2.77 r^2}{a^2}} \quad e^{-\frac{\pi^2}{2.77} \left(\frac{a}{\theta}\right)^2} \quad (2-20)$$

$$T(r) = \delta\left(r - \frac{a}{2}\right) \quad J_0\left(\pi \frac{a}{\theta}\right) \quad (2-21)$$

where $\theta = 1/\lambda$, the fringe spacing. These are shown in figure 2-3.

Another class of sources is those for which the fringe phase is always zero or π which means

$$T(r, \psi) = T(r, -\psi) \Rightarrow S(\lambda) \text{ REAL} \quad (2-21)$$

Circularly symmetric sources are a subset of this class. A

FIGURE 2-3. INTERFEROMETER RESPONSE TO COMMON BRIGHTNESS DISTRIBUTIONS.

simple example is a source with two small components:

$$\delta(x-x_0, y-y_0) + \delta(x+x_0, y+y_0) \leftrightarrow \cos(s_x x_0 + s_y y_0) \quad (2-23)$$

Some properties of a source are made immediately evident from interferometer measurements by expanding the fringe visibility in a Taylor series about the origin,

$$S(s_x, s_y) = S(0,0) + \frac{dS}{ds_x} s_x + \frac{dS}{ds_y} s_y + \frac{1}{2} \frac{d^2 S}{ds_x^2} s_x^2 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{d^2 S}{ds_y^2} s_y^2 + \frac{d^2 S}{ds_x ds_y} s_x s_y + \dots \quad (2-24)$$

Note that

$$S(0,0) = \iint T_B(x,y) dx dy$$

$$\left. \frac{dS}{ds_x} \right| = \iint x T_B(x,y) dx dy \quad \text{etc.} \quad (2-25)$$

Hence the series coefficients are the moments of the brightness distribution.

The ideal method for synthesizing the source distribution would be to measure the visibility on a uniform grid in the s_x, s_y plane. The grid interval is specified by the sampling theorem. If the source is confined to rectangle x_0 by y_0

radians in size then the visibility is completely specified by samples at intervals

$$\Delta s_x = \frac{1}{x_0} \quad , \quad \Delta s_y = \frac{1}{y_0} \quad \text{CYCLES/RADIAN} \quad (2-26)$$

Because the earth rotates the projected baseline locus is an ellipse as can be shown from equation (2-9). Changing the separation between antennas and using the earth's rotation provides data on a series of ellipses which can be chosen to cover the s_x, s_y plane. Figure 5-3 and 5-20 give examples of the accessible parts of the projected baseline for several OH sources. The parameters of the ellipse for a given baseline are

$$\text{CENTER : } s_{x_c} = 0, \quad s_{y_c} = \frac{D}{\lambda} \cos \delta_S \sin \delta_B$$

$$\text{ELLIPTICITY} = 1 / \sin \delta_S \quad (2-27)$$

Figure 2-2 and equation (2-9) show that if the source and baseline have the same declination then when $L_S = L_B$, the projected baseline is zero. This time of day, when the source transits the baseline; i.e. $L_S = L_B$, is interesting even if the declinations are not equal. The fringe rate is zero and the delay is at a maximum or minimum. This is sometimes called

the turning point because the phase reaches an extreme and then starts back. The right ascension of a source can be measured simply by noting the time of the turning point.

A map of a source made from data along one complete ellipse is equivalent to that made by scanning the source with a large dish of diameter D but with sidelobes which are only about 4 db down from the main lobe. If data on many ellipses is taken then the image constructed will be equivalent to that made by an antenna of diameter D equal to the maximum interferometer spacing.

2.2 SPECTRAL LINE RADIOMETRY AND INTERFEROMETRY

Spectral line radio astronomy is concerned with measuring the narrow band spectral characteristics of the emission from atoms and molecules in space. Measurements are usually done by dividing the IF band into segments with a bank of bandpass filters and detecting the power output of each channel. The work done here has relied solely on digital techniques for estimating the power spectra from radio sources.

The spectrum of a stationary random process $x(t)$ can be estimated by computing the Fourier transform of the auto-correlation function of $x(t)$, computed over time interval T; i.e.

$$S(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \langle x(t) x(t+\tau) \rangle_T e^{j\omega\tau} d\tau \quad (2-28)$$

which in discrete form becomes

$$S'(k\Delta\omega) = \sum_{m=-M}^M \sum_{\ell=-L}^L X(\ell\Delta t) X(\ell\Delta t+m\Delta t) e^{-jk\Delta\omega m\Delta t} \quad (2-29)$$

since $\Delta t = \Delta t$. Upon interchanging summations this becomes

$$S'(k\Delta\omega) \cong \sum_{n=-L/M}^{L/M} \left[\sum_{m=n-M}^{n+M} X(m\Delta t) e^{jk\Delta\omega m\Delta t} \right]^2 \quad (2-30)$$

Equation (2-30) is used in radar astronomy and the Cooley-Tukey algorithm (see, for example, Cochran et al, 1967) can be used to compute the inner summation. Notice that in both cases the resolution is the same, i.e. $\sim 1/2M\Delta t$.

Van Vleck and Middleton (1966) showed that the autocorrelation function of a Gaussian random process is uniquely related to the autocorrelation function of the clipped process. If $y(t)$ is the clipped version of the signal $x(t)$ such that

$$y = 1 \quad \text{when } x > 0$$

$$y = -1 \quad \text{when } x < 0$$

then

$$\rho_y(\tau) = \langle y_1 y_2 \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} y_1 y_2 p(x_1, x_2) dx_1 dx_2 \quad (2-31)$$

where x_1 and x_2 are samples of the signal before clipping at times 1 and 2 and y_1 and y_2 are the clipped samples at times 1 and 2, and where

$$p(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma^2 \sqrt{1-\rho_x^2}} e^{-\frac{[x_1^2 - 2x_1x_2\rho_x + x_2^2]}{2\sigma^2(1-\rho_x^2)}} \quad (2-32)$$

The result of carrying out the integral in equation (2-31) is

$$\rho_y(\tau) = \frac{2}{\pi} \sin^{-1} \rho_x(\tau) \quad (2-33)$$

where

$$\rho_x(\tau) = \frac{\langle x_1 x_2 \rangle}{\langle x_1^2 \rangle}$$

The digital one-bit correlator designed by Weinreb (1964) was used in the processing of the Agassiz-Millstone interometer data discussed in Chapter III to compute $\rho_y(\tau)$.

The signal into the clipper from a radiometer is the sum of the antenna signal, $s(t)$, (which is filtered by the receiver and denoted s') plus receiver noise, $n(t)$ or,

$$x(t) = \sqrt{T_A} s'(t) + \sqrt{T_R} n'(t) \quad (2-34)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}\langle s'(t) \rangle &= \langle n'(t) \rangle = 0 \\ \langle s'^2(t) \rangle &= \langle n'^2(t) \rangle = 1\end{aligned}\quad (2-35)$$

T_R = receiver temperature

$T_A = \int T_A(\omega) d\omega$ = average antenna temperature

The normalized correlation function of $x(t)$ is

$$\rho(\tau) = \frac{T_A}{T_A + T_R} \rho_{s'}(\tau) + \frac{T_R}{T_A + T_R} \rho_{n'}(\tau)\quad (2-36)$$

and can be determined from the clipped correlation function by equation (2-33). The power spectrum on the source obtained by Fourier transforming equation (2-36) is, therefore,

$$S_{ON}(\omega) = \frac{T_A}{T_R} S(\omega) S_{BP}(\omega) + \frac{T_R}{T_S} N(\omega) S_{BP}(\omega)\quad (2-37)$$

where

$$S'(\omega) = S(\omega) S_{BP}(\omega)$$

$$N'(\omega) = N(\omega) S_{BP}(\omega)\quad (2-38)$$

$$T_S = T_A + T_R$$

$S_{BP}(\omega)$ = receiver bandpass function

The spectrum off the source is

$$S_{\text{OFF}} = N(\omega) S_{\text{BP}}(\omega) = S_{\text{BP}}(\omega) \quad (2-39)$$

and hence the desired signal spectrum is

$$T_A(\omega) = T_A S(\omega) = \frac{T_S S_{\text{ON}}(\omega) - T_R S_{\text{OFF}}(\omega)}{S_{\text{OFF}}(\omega)} \quad (2-40)$$

It is usually assumed that $T_S \sim T_R$ so

$$T_A(\omega) = T_S \left[\frac{S_{\text{ON}}(\omega) - S_{\text{OFF}}(\omega)}{S_{\text{OFF}}(\omega)} \right] \quad (2-41)$$

Interferometry requires the measurement of the cross correlation function. If $x_{11}(t)$ is signal 1 at time 1 and $x_{22}(t)$ is signal two at time two, then

$$\begin{aligned} x_{11} &= \sqrt{T_{A1}} s_{11} + \sqrt{T_{R1}} n_{11} \\ x_{22} &= \sqrt{T_{A2}} s_{22} + \sqrt{T_{R2}} n_{22} \end{aligned} \quad (2-42)$$

where s_1, s_2, n_1 and n_2 are zero mean Gaussian processes and

$$\langle s_{11} n_{11} \rangle = \langle s_{11} n_{22} \rangle = \langle s_{22} n_{22} \rangle = \langle s_{22} n_{11} \rangle = 0$$

$$\langle s_{11} s_{22} \rangle = \rho_{12} \quad (2-43)$$

It is easy to show that x_{11} and x_{22} form a jointly Gaussian random process whose correlation function is given by

$$\rho \approx \frac{\sqrt{T_{A_1} T_{A_2}}}{\sqrt{T_{S_1} T_{S_2}}} \rho_{12}$$

Hence the Van Vleck relation is valid for cross correlation also. The desired correlation function can be obtained from the clipped correlation function ρ_y by

$$\rho_{12}(\tau) = \sqrt{\frac{T_{S_1} T_{S_2}}{T_{A_1} T_{A_2}}} \sin \frac{\pi}{2} \rho_y(\tau) \quad (2-45)$$

where $0 < |\rho_{12}(0)| < 1$, so ρ_y is usually very small so that

$$\rho_{12}(\tau) \sim \frac{\pi}{2} \sqrt{\frac{T_{S_1} T_{S_2}}{T_{A_1} T_{A_2}}} \rho_y(\tau) \quad (2-46)$$

2.3 NOISE IN INTERFEROMETERS

The ability to detect and measure radio astronomical signals is limited by the system noise of the radiometer. A well known procedure for estimating the fluctuation level of the radiometer involves computing the power spectrum of the signal out of the detector in terms of the signal at the antenna port. The receiver is usually considered to inject additive white noise of spectral density equal to T_R . The area under the power spectrum of the detected signal is proportional to the variance of the power estimate.

The optimum radiometer is the total power receiver whose fluctuations, in the absence of gain variations are given by

$$\Delta T = \frac{T_S}{\sqrt{B}} \left[\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |H(f)|^2 df \right]^{1/2} \sim \frac{T_S}{\sqrt{B\tau}} \quad (2-47)$$

where

$$T_S = \text{system temperature} = T_R + T_A$$

B = predetection bandwidth

$H(f)$ = post detection filter characteristic

τ = integration time (square filter)

For a balanced dicke radiometer (Kraus, 1966) the fluctuations are doubled owing to the fact that the receiver is looking

at the source only half the time and the difference of two random variables is being measured. The rms level is

$$\Delta T = \frac{2 T_s}{\sqrt{B\tau}} \quad (2-48)$$

The correlation receiver, in which the received signal is divided and passed through independent radiometers whose outputs are multiplied together, has rms fluctuations given by

$$\Delta T = \frac{\sqrt{2} T_s}{\sqrt{B\tau}} \quad T_s \gg T_A \quad (2-49)$$

Spectral line receivers of the filter bank type have noise levels given by either 2-47 or 2-48 depending on the mode of operation. The bandwidth is the resolution width. The one bit correlation spectrometer has a performance slightly worse than the equivalent filter bank receiver because of the loss in information in the clipping process. The rms noise in dicke mode is

$$\Delta T \approx 1.3 \frac{2 T_s}{\sqrt{R\tau}} \quad (2-50)$$

where R is the frequency resolution in Hertz.

The interferometer in figure 2-1 is simply a two channel correlation receiver except that there are two antennas involved and the output filter is not a low pass filter but a bandpass filter centered at the fringe frequency. The rms fluctuations for each of the orthogonal outputs is

$$\Delta T_{x,y}(\omega) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{\{ [T_{R1} + T_{A1}(\omega)] [T_{R2} + T_{A2}(\omega)] \}^{1/2}}{\sqrt{B\tau}} = \sigma \quad (2-51)$$

where the signal temperature is frequency dependent as appropriate to spectral line operation. The outputs 1 and 2 of the interferometer are combined to form a vector

$$\vec{S}(\omega) = \vec{A}(\omega) + \vec{N}(\omega) \quad (2-52)$$

where

$$\vec{A}(\omega) = A(\omega) \cos \psi(\omega) \hat{x} + A(\omega) \sin \psi(\omega) \hat{y} \quad (2-53)$$

This is shown in figure 2-4 for the large signal to noise case. $\vec{N}$ has approximately a Gaussian distribution given by

$$P(N_x, N_y) = \frac{1}{2\pi \sigma^2} e^{-\frac{(N_x^2 + N_y^2)}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (2-54)$$

Signal vector $\vec{A}$,
plus noise vector $\vec{N}$,
with Gaussian components

Probability distribution of the amplitude and phase of the noise vector.

Probability that the fringe amplitude of one or more points in an M point spectrum will exceed a specified level in the absence of signal

N.B. $\sigma' = \sqrt{2} \sigma$

FIGURE 2-4. NOISE CHARACTERISTICS OF AN INTERFEROMETER

where $\sigma = \Delta T_{x,y}^{(u)}$. Hence the probability distributions of the magnitude and phase of the noise vector are just

$$P(|\vec{N}|) = \frac{|N|}{\sigma^2} e^{-\frac{|N|^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (2-55)$$

$$P(\theta) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \quad (2-56)$$

We, therefore, have

$$\langle |N| \rangle = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{T_{S_1} T_{S_2}}{\sqrt{B\tau}} \quad (2-57)$$

and

$$\Delta |\vec{S}| \approx \sqrt{2} \sigma = \frac{T_{S_1} T_{S_2}}{\sqrt{B\tau}} = \sigma' \quad (2-58)$$

and

$$\Delta \epsilon \approx \langle \epsilon^2 \rangle^{1/2} \approx \left\langle \frac{(N \sin \theta)^2}{|S|^2} \right\rangle \approx \frac{\sigma}{|S|} = \frac{T_{S_1} T_{S_2}}{\sqrt{2} |S| \sqrt{B\tau}} \quad (2-59)$$

Equation(2-58) and(2-59) give the rms noise levels for the fringe amplitude and phase for the strong signal case.

It is shown in Davenport and Root (1958) that for a strong signal, $\bar{A} \gg N$, the probability distribution of $|\vec{S}|$ is approximately Gaussian, that is

$$p(|\vec{S}|) = \frac{1}{\sigma} \left(\frac{|\vec{S}|}{2\pi A} \right)^{1/2} e^{-\frac{(|\vec{S}|-A)^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (2-60)$$

One final matter of interest is the computation of the likelihood that a peak in a spectrum is a signal. If a spectrum consists of n points, then the probability that there is at least one point which has amplitude greater than x_0 in the absence of signal is

$$p(x > x_0) = 1 - \left[\int_0^{x_0} p(|N|) dN \right]^n \quad (2-61)$$

This is also shown in figure 2-4. For example, with 100 independent points, the probability that one or more points will have values greater than 3σ is about 0.01.

The analysis so far has been concerned with coherent interferometers. The intensity interferometer measures the correlation in the detected signals from each receiver. If the bandwidth after the detectors is W , then the signal to noise ratio for integration time τ is

$$\frac{S}{N} = \frac{T_{A_1} T_{A_2}}{T_{S_1} T_{S_2}} \sqrt{W \tau} \quad (2-62)$$

It is always preferable to coherently average the signal for as long as possible and then average the square of the fringe amplitudes. This procedure has been analyzed by Rogers.

The signal is

$$\left\langle \left\{ \sum_0^N \frac{|A|^2}{N} \right\} \right\rangle \approx T_{A_1} T_{A_2} + \frac{T_{S_1} T_{S_2}}{B \tau_{COH}} \quad (2-63)$$

The first term is the signal for an unresolved source and the second is a bias term. The signal to noise ratio is

$$\left(\frac{S}{N} \right) = \frac{T_{A_1} T_{A_2}}{T_{S_1} T_{S_2}} \frac{\tau_{COH} \sqrt{N}}{\sqrt{2}} = \frac{T_{A_1} T_{A_2}}{T_{S_1} T_{S_2}} \frac{B \sqrt{\tau}}{\sqrt{2 B_C}} \quad (2-64)$$

where

N = the number of coherent blocks of data averaged

τ_{COH} = coherent integration time

τ = total integration time

$B_C = 1 / \tau_{COH}$

The Jodrell Bank - NRAO interferometer data was processed using a combination of coherent and incoherent averaging. The results are shown in figure 5.26.

2.4 POLARIZATION ANALYSIS

A monochromatic wave is 100% elliptically polarized and its polarization characteristics can be specified by its ellipticity, position angle and intensity. On the other hand, the tip of the electric field vector in a narrow band wave can vary erratically with time so that its polarization is not pure elliptical. In this case the wave is called partially polarized and is specified by four quantities. One set of four parameters is Stokes parameters whose operational definition is in terms of the intensity measured with right and left circularly polarized antennas and a linearly polarized antenna with position angles of 0, 45, 90 and 135°. They are*

$$S_0 = I_R + I_L = I_0 + I_{90}$$

$$S_1 = I_0 - I_{90} \quad (2-65)$$

$$S_2 = I_{45} - I_{135}$$

$$S_3 = I_R - I_L$$

Another representation is in terms of intensity S_0 , percentage polarization, m , position angle ψ and ellipticity, $\tan \alpha$, where

* Right circular polarization is defined as clockwise rotation of the E vector as viewed along the direction of propagation. This is the I.R.E. convention which is opposite the optical convention.

$$m = \frac{\sqrt{S_1^2 + S_2^2 + S_3^2}}{S_0}$$

$$2\psi = \tan^{-1} \frac{S_2}{S_1} \quad (2-66)$$

$$2\chi = \tan^{-1} \frac{S_3}{\sqrt{S_1^2 + S_2^2}}$$

The Poincare sphere is a way of representing the polarized part of the wave as a vector. The components are S_1 , S_2 and S_3 as shown in figure 2-5.

The Stokes parameters are additive for an incoherent superposition of waves:

$$S_j = \sum_{k=1}^N S_j^{(k)} \quad (2-67)$$

A partially polarized wave can be represented as two independent oppositely polarized elliptical waves both 100% polarized. The S_0 parameter can be given in terms of S_0 , S_1 , S_2 and S_3 of the original wave:

$$S_0^{(1)} = S_0 - \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{S_1^2 + S_2^2 + S_3^2} \quad (2-68)$$

$$S_0^{(2)} = S_0 + \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{S_1^2 + S_2^2 + S_3^2}$$

FIGURE 2-5. POINCARÉ SPHERE FOR REPRESENTING THE POLARIZED COMPONENT OF THE RADIATION FIELD.

FIGURE 2-6. A SPECTRAL LINE POLARIMETER USING THREE CROSS CORRELATORS. LOAD SWITCHING IS UNNECESSARY SINCE THE NOISE IN THE RECEIVERS IS UNCORRELATED.

From the above decomposition it is clear that the incoherent sum of two 100% polarized waves create a new wave which is not 100% polarized. It is not known, for example, whether some of the elliptically polarized OH features consist of the sum of a pure elliptical plus an unpolarized wave or the sum of a circular and linear wave.

An antenna response can also be specified in terms of Stokes parameters. If the antenna has a set of Stokes parameters s'_i and the incoming wave has a set s_i , then the received power is

$$P = \frac{1}{2} (1-m) S A + m S A \cos^2 \frac{\gamma}{2}$$

where S = flux of wave, A = antenna area, m = degree of polarization, and γ = angle between vectors on Poincaire sphere, as shown in figure 2-5, of s_i and s'_i . A familiar case is an unpolarized wave where $m=0$ so that $P = \frac{1}{2} \cdot S \cdot A$ no matter what the antenna polarization. This relation also shows that the most power is extracted from the radiation field if the polarization of the radiation and antenna match.

Polarization measurements are often made by measuring the received power with a linear feed versus position angle of the feed. The response is sinusoidal, yielding three parameters, an average value, a sine wave phase and amplitude. The set is completed by measuring the difference in power between left and right circular polarization.

A more natural way of investigating polarization is available to interferometers and to radio telescopes equipped with multiple feeds and receivers. The ideal situation is shown in figure 2-6 for the single antenna system. There are two orthogonal feed horns each followed by two receivers. Three cross correlators are used to obtain S_{RR} , S_{LL} and S_{RL} in the case where the feeds are circularly polarized. A simpler system which requires load switching involves only one receiver on each feed port, each followed by an autocorrelator. A crosscorrelator is also used to measure S_{RL} . With either of these systems it is convenient to represent the polarization of the incident radiation in terms of the measured quantities,

$$S(\omega) = \begin{bmatrix} S_{RR}(\omega) & S_{RL}(\omega) \\ S_{RL}^*(\omega) & S_{LL}(\omega) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2-70)$$

Each frequency is specified by four numbers, S_{RR} , S_{LL} , $\text{Re}S_{RL}$, and $\text{Im}S_{RL}$. Notice that $S_{RL} = S_{LR}^*$. If two linear ports are available, then the parameters measured are

$$S(\omega) = \begin{bmatrix} S_{HH}(\omega) & S_{HV}(\omega) \\ S_{HV}^*(\omega) & S_{VV}(\omega) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2-71)$$

This second form is called the coherency matrix. The relationship between equation (2-70) and (2-71) is

$$2 S_{RR}(\omega) = S_{HH}(\omega) + S_{VV}(\omega) + 2 \operatorname{Im} S_{HV}(\omega)$$

$$2 S_{LL}(\omega) = S_{HH}(\omega) + S_{VV}(\omega) - 2 \operatorname{Im} S_{HV}(\omega) \quad (2-72)$$

$$2 S_{RL}(\omega) = S_{HH}(\omega) - S_{VV}(\omega) + j2 \operatorname{Re} S_{HV}(\omega)$$

$$2 S_{LR}(\omega) = S_{HH}(\omega) - S_{VV}(\omega) - j2 \operatorname{Re} S_{HV}(\omega)$$

Using equation (2-65) it is easy to make the transformation to Stokes parameters

$$S_0(\omega) = S_{HH}(\omega) + S_{VV}(\omega) = S_{RR}(\omega) + S_{LL}(\omega)$$

$$S_1(\omega) = S_{HH}(\omega) - S_{VV}(\omega) = \operatorname{Re} S_{RL}(\omega) \quad (2-73)$$

$$S_2(\omega) = \operatorname{Re} S_{HV}(\omega) = \operatorname{Im} S_{RL}(\omega)$$

$$S_3(\omega) = \operatorname{Im} S_{HV}(\omega) = S_{RR}(\omega) - S_{LL}(\omega)$$

similarly

$$\tan 2\psi = \frac{S_{HV} + S_{VH}}{S_{HH} - S_{VV}} \quad (2-74)$$

$$\sin 2\chi = \frac{j(S_{HV} - S_{VH})}{\sqrt{(T_r[S])^2 - 4 \operatorname{Det}(S)}}$$

$$m = \sqrt{1 - 4 \frac{\text{Det [S]}}{(\text{TR[S]})^2}}$$

The general interferometer configuration is also shown in figure 2-7. The spatial distribution of each polarization parameter must be measured. For a given projected baseline $\vec{A}$ the interferometer measures

$$A(\omega, \vec{A}) = \begin{bmatrix} A_{RR}(\omega) & A_{LR}(\omega) \\ A_{RL}(\omega) & A_{LL}(\omega) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2-75)$$

Each element of the matrix complex represents a fringe visibility for its polarization parameter. Instead of thinking of the fringe visibility function which is the transform of the brightness distribution we must think of 4 brightness distributions simultaneously, one for each polarization parameter in the system chosen. For example, consider the region of space to be mapped where the temperature distribution is given by $T_{RL}(x,y,\omega)$, $T_{LR}(x,y,\omega)$, $T_{RR}(x,y,\omega)$, $T_{LL}(x,y,\omega)$ the interferometer response is

$$A_{ij}(\vec{A}, \omega) = \iint T_{ij}(\vec{r}, \omega) e^{-j2\pi\vec{A} \cdot \vec{r}} d\vec{r} \quad (2-76)$$

where i and j correspond to the R-L system or the H-V system. We will write out the RL system because, although it may not

FIGURE 2-7. A SPECTRAL LINE INTERFEROMETER FOR MEASURING THE BRIGHTNESS DISTRIBUTION OF EACH POLARIZATION COMPONENT USING FOUR CORRELATORS.

be intuitively the best one to work with, it corresponds to the situation in the experiments discussed here because the antenna feeds are circularly polarized. Hence,

$$A_{RR}(\vec{A}, \omega) = \iint T_{RR}(r, \omega) e^{-j2\pi\vec{A}\cdot\vec{r}} d\vec{r}$$

$$A_{LL}(\vec{A}, \omega) = \iint T_{LL}(r, \omega) e^{-j2\pi\vec{A}\cdot\vec{r}} d\vec{r} \quad (2-79)$$

$$A_{RL}(\vec{A}, \omega) = \iint [\text{Re } T_{RL}(r, \omega) + j \text{Im } T_{RL}(r, \omega)] e^{-j2\pi\vec{A}\cdot\vec{r}} d\vec{r}$$

$$A_{LR}(\vec{A}, \omega) = \iint [\text{Re } T_{RL}(r, \omega) - j \text{Im } T_{RL}(r, \omega)] e^{-j2\pi\vec{A}\cdot\vec{r}} d\vec{r}$$

where we have made use of the fact that $T_{RL} = T_{LR}^*$. Notice that except for the case of a point source

$$A_{RL}(\vec{A}, \omega) \neq A_{LR}^*(\vec{A}, \omega)$$

The total flux from the source is

$$F(\omega) = A_{RR}(0, \omega) + A_{LL}(0, \omega) \quad (2-80)$$

Some intuitive feel is gained by using Stokes parameters:

$$A_{RL}(\lambda, \omega) - A_{LR}(\lambda, \omega) = \int S_2(\omega) e^{-j2\pi\vec{\lambda} \cdot \vec{r}} d\vec{r}$$

$$A_{RL}(\lambda, \omega) + A_{LR}(\lambda, \omega) = \int S_1(\omega) e^{-j2\pi\vec{\lambda} \cdot \vec{r}} d\vec{r}$$

(2-81)

$$A_{RR}(\lambda, \omega) + A_{LL}(\lambda, \omega) = \int S_0(\omega) e^{-j2\pi\vec{\lambda} \cdot \vec{r}} d\vec{r}$$

$$A_{RR}(\lambda, \omega) - A_{LL}(\lambda, \omega) = \int S_3(\omega) e^{-j2\pi\vec{\lambda} \cdot \vec{r}} d\vec{r}$$

Consider as a trivial example a source whose position angle ψ is proportional to x across a source whose $S_0(x, y)$ has a Gaussian shape. That is

$$S_0(x, y) = \frac{S_0}{2\pi\sigma^2} e^{-\frac{(x^2+y^2)}{2\sigma^2}}$$

$$S_1(x, y) = S_0(x, y) \cos \alpha x$$

$$\psi = \alpha x$$

$$S_2(x, y) = S_0(x, y) \sin \alpha x$$

$$S_3(x, y) = 0$$

The interferometer response is

$$A_{RR}(\vec{d}) = A_{LL}(\vec{d}) = \frac{S_0}{2} e^{-\frac{(s_x^2 + s_y^2)r}{2}}$$

$$A_{RL} = S_0 e^{-[(s_x - \alpha)^2 + s_y^2] \frac{\pi}{2}} \quad (2-83)$$

$$A_{LR} = S_0 e^{-[s_x^2 + (s_y + \alpha)^2] \frac{\pi}{2}}$$

If the fringe spacing is approximately $\frac{1}{\alpha}$ and much smaller than α , then the interferometer response is virtually nil to RR and LL feed configuration while significant to RL and LR because of structure in position angle.

2.5 POSITION MEASUREMENTS:

In the case where a radio source under investigation is unresolved, the fringe phase is influenced solely by positional uncertainties and instrumental errors. The interferometer can be used to measure the position of a radio source and, also, the position of the baseline. The first application has obvious importance in relationship to optical identification of the source. The second has potential application in the long baseline experiments as a means of detecting subtle motions in the earth's crust.

The ability to do ultra-precise position measurements is hampered by the uncertainty in the atmospheric and ionospheric refractive effects. The refractive effects increase in severity with increasing frequency because of the

water vapor resonance near 22 GHz. In this thesis, measurements were made down to 6° in elevation with no noticeable degradation in correlation. However, any apparent change in position of the source went unnoticed because of the lack of phase or fringe rate stability. The refraction problem is a difficult one and will have to be solved before measurements of positions to small fractions of a second of arc are undertaken.

We will ignore refraction and instrumental effects and discuss only the relative merits of measuring fringe phase, delay and fringe rate in order to determine positions. The fringe phase due to positional errors is

$$\Delta\phi = \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial\delta_B} \Delta\delta_B + \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial(L_B - L_S)} \Delta(L_B + \lambda\alpha_S) + \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial D} \Delta D + \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial\delta_S} \Delta\delta_S$$

(2-84)

since

$$\phi = \phi(\delta_B, L_B, \alpha_S, D, \delta_S)$$

Expanding this gives

$$\Delta\phi = 2\pi \frac{D}{\lambda} \left[\sin\delta_S \cos\delta_B \Delta\delta_B + \sin\delta_S \sin\delta_B \frac{\Delta D}{D} + \cos\delta_S \sin\delta_B \Delta\delta_S \right]$$

$$- 2\pi \frac{D}{\lambda} \left[\cos\delta_S \sin\delta_B \Delta\delta_B - \cos\delta_S \cos\delta_B \frac{\Delta D}{D} - \sin\delta_S \cos\delta_B \Delta\delta_S \right] \cos(L_S - L_B)$$

$$- 2\pi \frac{D}{\lambda} \cos\delta_B \cos\delta_S (\Delta L_B + \Delta\alpha_S) \sin(L_S - L_B)$$

(2-85)

or

$$\Delta\phi = A(\Delta\delta_B, \Delta D, \Delta\delta_S) + B(\Delta\delta_B, \Delta D, \Delta\delta_S) \cos(L_S - L_B)$$

$$+ C(\Delta L_B, \Delta\alpha_S) \sin(L_S - L_B)$$

(2-86)

where A, B, and C are constants independent of local hour angle and

where $L_S = t_{\text{sid}} - \alpha_S$. Tracking a source over a portion of

the day enables the observer to measure A, B, and C. If the

baseline is known the source position can be found and if

the source position is known the baseline can be determined.

We could also include uncertainty in time but this is

indistinguishable from local hour angle uncertainties.

Observation of two sources gives two phase curves from which 6 parameters can be obtained. There are also 6 unknowns = δ_B , D , δ_{S_1} , δ_{S_2} , $(L_B + \alpha_{S_1} + \Delta t)$, $(L_B + \alpha_{S_2} + \Delta t)$. Hence the system can be solved except for one arbitrary right ascension.

The phase information is the most accurate for positional measurements. However, because of its modulo 2π characteristic, care must be taken to keep track of which fringe the source is on. The number of measurements necessary to do this, N , is on the order of the ratio of position uncertainty to the fringe spacing

$$N \sim \frac{\Delta p}{\left(\frac{\lambda}{D}\right)} \quad (2-87)$$

A less sensitive method involves using the fringe rate information. The fringe rate and differential fringe rate are

$$f_R = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{d\phi}{dt} = \frac{D}{\lambda} \cos \delta_B \cos \delta_S \sin(L_S - L_B) \frac{dL_B}{dt} \quad (2-88)$$

and

$$\Delta f_R = \frac{\partial f_R}{\partial \delta_B} \Delta \delta_B + \frac{\partial f_R}{\partial \delta_S} \Delta \delta_S + \frac{\partial f_R}{\partial D} \Delta D + \frac{\partial f_R}{\partial (L_S - L_B)} \Delta (L_S - L_B) \quad (2-89)$$

so that

$$\Delta f_R = A \cos(L_S - L_B) + B \sin(L_S - L_B) \quad (2-90)$$

The fringe rate offset gives only two parameters since the average fringe rate offset is zero. Hence, the baseline and source parameters cannot both be obtained. The sensitivity in terms of fringes is given by

$$\frac{\left(\frac{\Delta f_R}{f_R}\right) 2\pi}{\frac{\lambda}{D}} \approx \frac{\Delta f_R}{f_{ROT}} \quad (2-91)$$

where f_{ROT} is the frequency of the earth rotation. The accuracy of the measurement of Δf_R is proportional to the reciprocal of the observing time (obviously Δf_R can not be measured by an elapsed phase technique). $\Delta f_R \sim 10^{-4}$ cps and $f_R \sim 10^{-5}$ cps for a few hundred second integration time on a strong source. Hence, two measurements during the day give the position to about 10 fringes.

The third technique involves measuring the delay,

$$\tau = \frac{D}{C} [\sin \delta_B \sin \delta_S + \cos \delta_B \cos \delta_S \cos(L_S - L_B)] \quad (2-92)$$

$$\Delta \tau = \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial \delta_B} \Delta \delta_B + \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial \delta_S} \Delta \delta_S + \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial D} \Delta D + \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial (L_S - L_B)} \Delta (L_S - L_B) \quad (2-93)$$

and hence

$$\Delta\tau = A + B \cos(L_S \cdot L_B) + C \sin(L_S \cdot L_B) \quad (2-94)$$

Hence 3 parameters can be measured and both source and base-line positions can be found except for the arbitrary right ascension. The accuracy of the measurement of $\Delta\tau$ is proportional to the reciprocal of the bandwidth. The sensitivity is in terms of fringes therefore

$$\frac{\left(\frac{\Delta\tau}{T_{\text{Max}}}\right)}{\frac{\lambda}{D}} \sim \frac{\Delta\tau}{\left(\frac{\lambda}{C}\right)} \sim \frac{f_0}{f_{\text{Bw}}} \quad (2-95)$$

A bandwidth of a few megacycles make $\Delta\tau \sim 10^{-8}$ and at 10^9 cps this means that three measurements during the day give position to about 10 fringes. Hence, both delay and fringe rate measurements are inherently less sensitive than phase measurements.

It is interesting to note how Δf_R and $\Delta\tau$ measurements complement one another. Writing

$$\Delta f_R = \vec{R}_F \cdot \vec{r}$$

$$\Delta\tau = \vec{R}_\tau \cdot \vec{r} \quad (2-96)$$

where $\vec{R}_F$ and $\vec{R}_\tau$ are resolution vectors given by

$$\mathbf{r} = \cos \delta_S \Delta \alpha \hat{x} + \Delta \delta_B \hat{y} \quad (2-97)$$

$$\vec{R}_F(L_S) = \frac{D}{\lambda} \omega_{ROT} [\cos \delta_B \cos(L_S - L_B) X + \cos \delta_B \sin \delta_S (L_S - L_B) Y] \quad (2-98)$$

$$\vec{R}_T(L_S) = \frac{D}{\lambda} \frac{\lambda}{C} [\cos \delta_B \sin(L_S - L_B) x + (\sin \delta_B \cos \delta_S - \cos \delta_B \sin \delta_S \cos(L_S - L_B)) y]$$

Notice that $\vec{R}_T$ is proportional to the projected baseline vector

$$\vec{R}_T(L_S) = \frac{C}{\lambda} \vec{A} \quad (2-99)$$

and that

$$\vec{R}_T(L_S + 6 \text{ Hours}) = \vec{R}_F(L_S) + \sin \delta_B \cos \delta_S \hat{y} \quad (2-100)$$

This last relation shows that $\vec{R}_T$ and $\vec{R}_F$ are usually nearly orthogonal and that one measurement of a source in delay and fringe rate are enough to find its coordinates.

Operationally, the use of fringe rate, delay or phase information in the VLB interferometer is hampered because

the atomic standards inject their own random phase and fringe rate and, hence, time error into the data. One partial solution to this problem is to move quickly between sources and measure the relative fringe rate, delay or phase before the atomic standard drifts and thereby deduce relative positions among sources. A more sophisticated instrumentation of this idea is to provide two antennas at each site linked to the same standard. One antenna at each site tracks a reference source and thereby provides a phase calibration for the fringe phase measured with the other pair of antenna which are tracking the source of interest.

Some advantage is obtained by making simultaneous observations at more than two stations. The amount of data per station, or per tape, increases because of the multiple correlations. Consider a three element interferometer. Each baseline consists of an estimated baseline vector, $\vec{B}_i$, and an unknown positional error vector, $\Delta\vec{B}_i$. We demand that both sets of these baseline vectors close, that is

$$\vec{B}_i = 0$$

$$\Delta\vec{B}_i = 0$$

The fringe phases measured on each baseline are

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta\phi_{BA} &= \vec{\Delta B}_1 \cdot \vec{S} + \vec{B}_1 \cdot \vec{\Delta S} + \psi_{BA} + (\theta_A - \theta_B) \\
\Delta\phi_{AC} &= \vec{\Delta B}_2 \cdot \vec{S} + \vec{B}_2 \cdot \vec{\Delta S} + \psi_{AC} + (\theta_C - \theta_A) \\
\Delta\phi_{CB} &= \vec{\Delta B}_3 \cdot \vec{S} + \vec{B}_3 \cdot \vec{\Delta S} + \psi_{CB} + (\theta_B - \theta_C)
\end{aligned}
\tag{2-101}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
\vec{\Delta B}_i \cdot \vec{S} &= \text{phase due to baseline error} \\
\vec{B}_i \cdot \vec{\Delta S} &= \text{phase due to source position error} \\
\psi_{BA} &= \text{phase of visibility function} \\
\theta_{A,B,C} &= \text{instrumental phase introduced by atomic} \\
&\quad \text{standard or certain types of atmospheric} \\
&\quad \text{fluctuation.}
\end{aligned}$$

Adding

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta\phi_{BA} + \Delta\phi_{AC} + \Delta\phi_{CB} &= \vec{S} \cdot (\vec{\Delta B}_1 + \vec{\Delta B}_2 + \vec{\Delta B}_3) + (\vec{B}_1 + \vec{B}_2 + \vec{B}_3) \cdot \vec{\Delta S} \\
&\quad + \psi_{BA} + \psi_{AC} + \psi_{CB} \\
&= \psi_{BA} + \psi_{AC} + \psi_{CB}
\end{aligned}
\tag{2-102}$$

The sum of the three phases equals the sum of the three phases of the visibility function for the appropriate projected baselines. If the source is unresolved

$$\sum \Delta\phi = 0
\tag{2-103}$$

CHAPTER III

THE AGASSIZ-MILLSTONE INTERFEROMETER

3.1 INTRODUCTION

In September, 1966, it was decided to construct an interferometer by linking the 84 foot antenna on Millstone Hill, Westford, Massachusetts, operated by the M.I.T. Lincoln Laboratory with the 60 foot antenna at the Agassiz station, Harvard, Massachusetts, operated by Harvard College Observatory. The first part of the experiment involved setting up the simplest possible phase coherent interferometer to test the feasibility of an elaborate phase stable system. This was done without purchasing new equipment.

The initial part of the program was successfully completed and useful observations were made during December, 1966, and January, 1967. The second part, the design and construction of a phase stable interferometer was never begun, partly because enthusiasm of the very long baseline experiments left no time for this project.

This chapter describes the interferometer system, the processing technique and the results of measurements on the OH source W3. This project was an extension of the Haystack-Millstone interferometer project, (Rogers, Moran, Crowther, Burke, Meeks, Ball, Hyde, 1966, 1967). The Haystack radio

telescope was replaced by the Harvard telescope and the cable link by a microwave link. The signal processing hardware and software were virtually the same.

3.2 INTERFEROMETER SYSTEM:

In short baseline interferometers operating in the microwave region, cables between the receiving elements are used to bring the received signals together for processing and to distribute a reference signal from which the local oscillator signals can be synthesized. If the electrical length of the cables is carefully controlled by a servomechanism then the system can be made phase stable for long periods of time. In this project a one way microwave relay link provided communication from Harvard to Millstone Hill. Since two way communication was not established, there were no means of sensing the instrumental phase and, thereby, providing long term stability. The link, a 1956 version of the Raytheon KTR-1000A color television relay system, was chosen because of its availability and not because of its merits.

The link system consisted of a transmitter and receiver, each having a four foot paraboloid antenna. It was licenced to operate in a band centered on 7225 MHz. The transmitter was capable of frequency modulating a klystron with a 6 MHz video signal. The radiated power was about one watt. The receiver contained a klystron local oscillator which mixed

the received signal to 130 MHz. A ratio discriminator demodulated the signal and a simple AFC circuit helped the local oscillator to track the transmitter frequency.

The link was set up in the laboratory for phase coherence tests with the transmitter connected to the receiver via a 70 db attenuator. A five MHz sine wave was put through the link and a phase comparison was made between the input and output signals. The phase comparison was made at 1 GHz to amplify the phase noise and simulate the real system. The phase stability was poor, owing principally to frequency shifts in the klystrons which were induced by a large number of environmental factors. The system was much improved by increasing the power supply regulation and by phase locking the local oscillator with an external 130 MHz oscillator.

The link transmitter was mounted on a fire tower 2000 feet from the telescope at Harvard and the receiver was placed on the pedestal of the Millstone antenna giving a line of site transmission path. Figure 3-1 shows the two radio telescopes. The link receiving antenna can be seen on the Millstone mount. Figure 3-2 shows the fire tower and the transmission path to Millstone Hill which is the most distant ridge. The horn used in the interferometer phase tests can also be seen in this figure.

FIGURE 3-1. THE ELEMENTS OF THE AGASSIZ-MILLSTONE INTERFEROMETER. LEFT: THE 60 FOOT AGASSIZ ANTENNA OF HARVARD COLLEGE OBSERVATORY; RIGHT: THE 84 FOOT MILLSTONE HILL ANTENNA OF THE M.I.T. LINCOLN LABORATORY.

FIGURE 3-2. THE TRANSMITTER OF THE MICROWAVE RELAY LINK ON THE HARVARD FIRE TOWER.

A condensed diagram of the entire interferometer is shown in figure 3-3. The receiver at the Harvard terminal included a cooled maser amplifier and had a system temperature of about 130 °K. The received signal was converted to a video band from 0 to 400 KHz via three frequency conversion stages. The local oscillator signal for each mixer was derived from a 5 MHz crystal oscillator. The video signal and the 5 MHz reference were multiplexed on a cable and then transmitted over the link. The received signal was sent directly to the Haystack control room on cables where the 5 MHz reference was filtered out and used to phase lock a crystal oscillator. The 28.5 MHz local oscillator frequency was synthesized from this and used to mix the video signal up to 30 MHz. The 5 MHz signal was also used to derive the local oscillator signal for the receiver on the Millstone antenna. The Millstone receiver had a tunnel diode amplifier which gave a system temperature of 700 °K. The signal from Millstone was converted to 30 MHz and sent to the Haystack control room. The two 30 MHz signals were alternately added and subtracted at 100 millisecond intervals before being converted to video and fed into the digital one-bit autocorrelator.

The distance between the antennas was 43925 feet or 74,400 wavelengths along an azimuth of $22^{\circ} 31.5'$. The maximum resolution was, therefore, 2.8" of arc.

AGASSIZ-MILLSTONE INTERFEROMETER

FIGURE 3-3. SIMPLIFIED BLOCK DIAGRAM OF THE AGASSIZ-MILLSTONE INTERFEROMETER SYSTEM.

3.3 THE SIGNAL PROCESSING

The Agassiz-Millstone interferometer is a spectral line version of a phase switched interferometer. The signal processing is essentially the same as that employed by the Haystack-Millstone interferometer. It has several peculiarities and restrictions on its validity which are caused by the phase switching technique and the one bit correlator. For this reason it will be discussed in some detail. See also, Rogers (1967).

Each antenna continually tracks the source and each receiver is continually connected to its receiver during the observations. The two received signals are alternately added and subtracted for periods of 100 milliseconds. A 100 point autocorrelation function of the combined signal for each period is computed by the digital correlator and the results are fed to the UNIVAC-490 computer where they are written out on magnetic tape along with the antenna pointing information. A program on the CDC-3300 computer written by the author, takes the difference between the sum and the difference correlation functions, thereby removing the contribution of the individual antennas and leaving only the cross correlation component. The result is synchronously detected at the fringe frequency and Fourier transformed to give the visibility spectrum.

If the signal received at one site is $x(t)$ and at the other site $y(t-\tau_t)$, where τ_t is the sum of the interferometer's geometric delay τ_G and the instrumental delay τ , then the auto-correlation functions of their sum and difference are

$$R^+(\tau) = \langle [x(t) + y(t-\tau_1)] [x(t-\tau) + y(t-\tau_1-\tau)] \rangle \quad (3-1)$$

$$R^-(\tau) = \langle [x(t) - y(t-\tau_2)] [x(t-\tau) - y(t-\tau_2-\tau)] \rangle$$

τ_1 and τ_2 are the interferometer delay, τ_t , evaluated at two instants of time separated by 100 milliseconds. Equation (3-1) becomes

$$R^+(\tau) = R_{xx}(\tau) + R_{yy}(\tau) + R_{xy}(\tau + \tau_1) + R_{yx}(\tau - \tau_1) \quad (3-2)$$

$$R^-(\tau) = R_{xx}(\tau) + R_{yy}(\tau) - R_{xy}(\tau + \tau_2) - R_{yx}(\tau - \tau_2)$$

The difference of these correlation functions is

$$R_D(\tau) = R_{xy}(\tau + \tau_1) + R_{yx}(\tau - \tau_1) + R_{xy}(\tau + \tau_2) + R_{yx}(\tau - \tau_2) \quad (3-3)$$

whose Fourier transform is

$$S_D(\omega) = 2 \operatorname{Re} \left\{ S_{xy}(\omega) e^{j\omega\tau_1} \right\} + 2 \operatorname{Re} \left\{ S_{xy}(\omega) e^{j\omega\tau_2} \right\} \quad (3-4)$$

or

$$S_D(\omega) = 4 \cos \Delta\phi \left\{ \text{Re } S_{xy}(\omega) e^{j\omega\tau_t} \right\} \quad (3-5)$$

where τ_t is the average geometric delay and $\cos \Delta\phi$ represents the reduction in signal cause by too high a fringe rate. That is,

$$\tau_t = \frac{\tau_2 + \tau_1}{2} \quad \Delta\phi = \frac{\omega\tau_2 - \omega\tau_1}{2} \approx \frac{1}{2} \omega_f \Delta t \quad (3-6)$$

where ω_f is the fringe frequency and Δt the 100 ms switching period. The fringe rate on W3 was always less than 2 Hz so that $\cos \Delta\phi \geq 0.8$. Hence, this interferometer measures only the real part of the cross correlation spectrum. Fortunately the earth's rotation changes τ_t so that the whole of S_{xy} can be determined.

Ignoring the $\cos \Delta\phi$ term, equation (3-5) can be expanded by writing S_{xy} in terms of an amplitude $A(\omega)$ and phase $\psi(\omega)$ and separating the delay into frequency and non-frequency terms so that

$$S_D(\omega) = 4 \text{Re} \left\{ A(\omega) e^{j[\psi(\omega) + \omega\tau_t + \Delta\omega\tau_t]} \right\} \quad (3-7)$$

where ω_0 is the frequency of the center of the RF band and $\omega_0 \tau_t$ is given by equation 2-3 plus the instrumental term:

$$\omega_0 \tau_t = \omega_0 \tau_G + \omega_0 \tau_\ell = \psi + \omega_0 \tau_\ell = 2\pi \frac{D}{\lambda} \left[\sin \delta_B \sin \delta_S + \cos \delta_B \cos \delta_S \cos(L_S - L_B) \right] + \omega_0 \tau_\ell \quad (3-8)$$

Therefore

$$S_D(\omega) = a(\omega) \cos \omega_0 \tau_t + b(\omega) \sin \omega_0 \tau_t$$

where

$$a(\omega) = 4 A(\omega) \cos (\psi + \Delta\omega \tau_t) \quad (3-9)$$

$$b(\omega) = 4 A(\omega) \sin (\psi + \Delta\omega \tau_t)$$

An estimate of $A(\omega)$ and $\psi(\omega)$ is obtained by using a least mean square error criterion given by

$$(\omega) = \sum_t \left[a(\omega) \cos \omega_0 \tau_t + b(\omega) \sin \omega_0 \tau_t - S_D^i(\omega) \right]^2 \quad (3-10)$$

where S_D^i is the measured value of S_D . Minimizing the error yields two equations for each frequency,

$$\begin{bmatrix} X(\omega) \\ Y(\omega) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} P & U \\ U & Q \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a(\omega) \\ b(\omega) \end{bmatrix} \quad (3-11)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 P &= \sum_t \cos^2 \omega_o \tau t \\
 Q &= \sum_t \sin^2 \omega_o \tau t \\
 U &= \sum_t \sin \omega_o \tau t \cos \omega_o \tau t \\
 X(\omega) &= \sum_t S_D^i(\omega) \cos \omega_o \tau t \\
 Y(\omega) &= \sum_t S_D^i(\omega) \sin \omega_o \tau t
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3-12}$$

From this we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 a(\omega) &= \frac{Q Y(\omega) - U X(\omega)}{\sqrt{PQ - U^2}} \\
 b(\omega) &= \frac{P X(\omega) - U Y(\omega)}{\sqrt{PQ - U^2}}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3-13}$$

The fringe amplitude and phase are

$$\begin{aligned}
 A(\omega) &= \sqrt{a^2(\omega) + b^2(\omega)} \\
 \psi(\omega) &= \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{a(\omega)}{b(\omega)} \right] - \Delta \omega \tau t
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3-14}$$

and

$$S_{xy}(\omega) = A(\omega) e^{j\psi(\omega)} \quad (3-14)$$

In the data processing $S_D(\omega)$ is not computed every 100 millisecond because the Fourier transformation summation can be interchanged with the time averaging summation in computing $X(\omega)$ and $Y(\omega)$. That is

$$X(\omega) = \sum_t \left[\sum_{\tau} R_D(\tau) \cos \omega \tau \right] \cos \omega_0 \tau_t \quad (3-15)$$

$$X(\omega) = \sum_{\tau} \cos \omega_0 \tau_t \left[\sum_t R_D(\tau) \cos \omega_0 \tau_t \right] \quad (3-16)$$

The correlator gives normalized correlation coefficients. Using the clipping correction for small correlation, the computer program computes

$$X'_K = \sum_{I=1}^{100} 2 \cos \left[\frac{2\pi(I-1)(K-1)}{400} \right] WT(I) \sum_t \frac{\pi}{2} (\rho_{I,t}^+ - \rho_{I,t}^-) \cos \omega_0 \tau_t \quad (3-17)$$

$$Y'_K = \sum_{I=1}^{100} 2 \cos \left[\frac{2\pi(I-1)(K-1)}{400} \right] WT(I) \sum_t \frac{\pi}{2} (\rho_{I,t}^+ - \rho_{I,t}^-) \sin \omega_0 \tau_t$$

where $\rho_{I,t}^+$ are the normalized correlation coefficients and

where $WT(I)$ is the weighting function. X_K and Y_K are not yet normalized and so are written with primes. The normalization depends on the relative amounts of each signal which enter the phase combiner. Hence, the program measures a normalized function $S'_{xy}(\omega)$ which it computes from equations (3-13) and (3-14) but using $X'(\omega)$ and $Y'(\omega)$ defined in equation (3-17). The relation between S_{xy} and S'_{xy} will now be discussed.

The added and subtracted video signals from telescope 1 and telescope 2 can be written

$$v^+(t) = \sqrt{G_1} \left[\sqrt{T_{A_1}} s_1(t) + \sqrt{T_{R_1}} n_1(t) \right] + \sqrt{G_2} \left[\sqrt{T_{A_2}} s_2(t) + \sqrt{T_{R_2}} n_2(t) \right] \quad (3-18)$$

$$v^-(t) = \sqrt{G_1} \left[\sqrt{T_{A_1}} s_1(t) + \sqrt{T_{R_1}} n_1(t) \right] - \sqrt{G_2} \left[\sqrt{T_{A_2}} s_2(t) + \sqrt{T_{R_2}} n_2(t) \right]$$

where $\sqrt{T_{A_1}} s_1(t)$ and $\sqrt{T_{A_2}} s_2(t)$ are the signal voltages and $\sqrt{T_{R_1}} n_1(t)$ and $\sqrt{T_{R_2}} n_2(t)$ are the receiver noise voltages and G_1 and G_2 are the power gains in each receiver. The autocorrelation function of each of these signals is

$$R^+ = G_1 T_{A_1} R_{S_1}(\tau) + G_1 T_{R_1} R_{N_1}(\tau) + G_2 T_{A_2} R_{S_2}(\tau) + G_2 T_{R_2} R_{N_2}(\tau) + \sqrt{G_1 G_2 T_{A_1} T_{A_2}} R_{S_1 S_2}(\tau)$$

$$R^- = G_1 T_{A_1} R_{S_1}(\tau) + G_1 T_{R_1} R_{N_1}(\tau) + G_2 T_{A_2} R_{S_2}(\tau) + G_2 T_{R_2} R_{N_2}(\tau) - \sqrt{G_1 G_2 T_{A_1} T_{A_2}} R_{S_1 S_2}(\tau)$$

(3-19)

The zero delay values of these correlation functions are

$$R^+(0) = G_1 T_{S_1} + G_2 T_{S_2} + \sqrt{G_1 G_2 \cdot T_{A_1} T_{A_2}} R_{S_1 S_2}(0)$$

$$R^-(0) = G_1 T_{S_1} + G_2 T_{S_2} - \sqrt{G_1 G_2 \cdot T_{A_1} T_{A_2}} R_{S_1 S_2}(0)$$

(3-20)

where $T_s = T_A + T_R$, the system temperature. The data reduction scheme requires that $R^+(0)$ and $R^-(0)$ be constant in time and equal to each other, since the total power information is lost in the digital correlator. This condition is fulfilled only if

$$\sqrt{T_{A_1} T_{A_2}} R_{S_1 S_2}(0) \sim 0$$

or, equivalently

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} S_{xy}(\omega) e^{j\omega\tau} d\omega \sim 0 \quad (3-21)$$

This is true for:

1. Narrow band spectral line observations where the total bandwidth is small, $B\tau_t \ll 1$ but the average temperature $\sqrt{T_{A_1} T_{A_2}}$ is much less than the system temperature. An interesting effect is observed on visibility spectra of OH sources with very strong narrow features. Since the processing program sets $R^+(0) = R^-(0)$, equation (3-21) is fulfilled exactly. To achieve this the fringe phase in the noise portion of the spectrum will not be random but will be ordered so that the sum of the noise vectors add up to be equal and opposite the signal vector.

Equation (3-21) is also true for:

2. Wide band continuum observations where $B\tau_t \gg 1$. The bandwidth condition can be relaxed if the source is weak so that the normalization is approximately constant.

This interferometer fails to work on strong continuum sources, $T_A > T_R$, where $B\tau_t < 1$ since the total power changes drastically with time. A general rule is that if the fringes observed on an analog detector operating on the sum of the signals are strong relative to the total power, then the computer reduction scheme fails.

The normalized correlation functions, ρ^+ and ρ^- , are related to the actual correlation functions, R^+ and R^- , by

$$\rho^{\pm}(\tau) = \frac{1}{G_1 T_{S_1} + G_2 T_{S_2}} R^{\pm}(\tau) \quad (3-22)$$

whereas the signal term is normalized to

$$\rho^+(\tau) - \rho^-(\tau) = \frac{G_1 G_2}{G_1 T_{S_1} + G_2 T_{S_2}} \sqrt{T_{A_1} T_{A_2}} R_{S_1 S_2}(\tau) \quad (3-23)$$

The effective temperature of the system is defined so that the rms fluctuations in the spectrum are

$$\Delta T = \frac{2 T_{\text{eff}}}{\sqrt{B\tau}} \quad (3-24)$$

where

$$T_{\text{eff}} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{G_1 T_{S_1} + G_2 T_{S_2}}{\sqrt{G_1 G_2}} = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \sqrt{\frac{G_1}{G_2}} T_{S_1} + \sqrt{\frac{G_2}{G_1}} T_{S_2} \right\} \quad (3-25)$$

The minimum system temperature is achieved when

$$\frac{G_1}{G_2} = \frac{T_{S_2}}{T_{S_1}} \quad (3-26)$$

Reference to equation (3-19) shows that the best system temperature is achieved when the power levels from each of the radiometers are set equal before they are combined. The system temperature is, therefore

$$T_{\text{eff}} = \sqrt{T_{S_1} T_{S_2}} \quad (3-27)$$

and the normalization of the visibility function is

$$V(\omega) = \frac{S'_{xy}(\omega) \sqrt{T_{S_1} T_{S_2}}}{S_{EP}(\omega) \sqrt{T_{A_1}(\omega) T_{A_2}(\omega)}} \quad (3-28)$$

S'_{xy} is the normalized interference spectrum calculated from equations (3-13) and (3-17). The bandpass function $S_{BP}(\omega)$ has been included to correct for change in gain across the band.

TESTS:

The link was installed in November, 1966, and phase stability checks of the entire interferometer were carried out. An oscillator locked to 1666 MHz was connected to a horn antenna on the fire tower. A yagi array was mounted on the azimuth deck of the Millstone antenna and connected to the radiometer so that it was not necessary to use the 84 foot reflector. Fringes were simulated by offsetting the 28.5 MHz local oscillator used to convert the Harvard signal up to 30 MHz. Figure 3-4 shows the test setup in

$$x_1(t) = V_1 \sin[\omega t + \phi_1(t)]$$

$$x_2(t) = V_2 \sin[(\omega + \Delta\omega)t + \phi_2(t)]$$

$$P(t) = \frac{[x_1(t) + x_2(t)]^2}{2} = \frac{(V_1^2 + V_2^2)}{2} + V_1 V_2 \cos[\Delta\omega t + \phi(t)]$$

where $\omega = 2\pi \times 30$ MHz; $\phi(t) = \phi_2(t) - \phi_1(t)$; $\Delta\omega =$ frequency offset of 28.5 MHz local oscillator

FIGURE 3-4. TEST CONFIGURATION FOR MEASURING PHASE STABILITY OF INTERFEROMETER.

which the received test signals were merely added and squared, with the output displayed on a chart recorder. Figure 3-5 shows the cosine of the phase between the two signals with the Agassiz signal offset by 0.02 Hz. The system was then zero beat (not 0.002 cps as indicated in the figure). This typical recording shows that one minute integration periods can be used with reasonable phase stability.

3.4 RESULTS

Data was taken for a few days in December, 1966, January and February, 1967. The integration time was limited to one minute for which the strongest feature in W3 gave a signal to rms noise ratio of about 7:1. Several hundred one minute runs were taken on W3. These were coherently averaged together in 10 minute groups by using the phase of the strongest feature, ψ_i , as a reference for the whole spectrum. That is

$$S_{AVG}(\omega) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i^N S(\omega) e^{-j\psi_i} \quad (3-29)$$

where N is the number of runs averaged. Figure 3-6 shows the average of 14 runs when the Millstone antenna was right circularly polarized. Here the signal to peak noise is about 8:1. This averaging procedure is very effective in lowering the noise in order to detect weak features as long as at least one feature is well above the noise on the one minute

PHASE STABILITY CHECK OF AGASSIZ-MILLSTONE
INTERFEROMETER USING TEST TRANSMITTER ON
FIRE TOWER

$f \sim 0.02$ cps $\longleftrightarrow$ $f \sim 0.002$ cps $\longrightarrow$

TIME $\longrightarrow$ 30 SECONDS

$f \sim 0.002$ cps $\longrightarrow$

TIME $\longrightarrow$ 30 SECONDS

FIGURE 3-5. PHASE STABILITY MEASUREMENTS ON INTERFEROMETER. THE 28.5 MHz LOCAL OSCILLATOR WAS FIRST OFFSET BY 0.02 Hz AND THEN SET TO EXACTLY 28.5 MHz.

INTERFERENCE SPECTRUM
 W3 (RIGHT VS LINEAR)

FRINGE AMPLITUDE °K

RESOLUTION

I RMS

$\tau = 840$ SECONDS

-43.5

-44.5

-45.5

VELOCITY KILOMETERS / SECOND

FIGURE 3-6. INTERFERENCE SPECTRUM OBTAINED ON W3 WITH 14 MINUTES OF INTEGRATION. ONE MINUTE RUNS WERE COHERENTLY AVERAGED BY USING THE PHASE AT -45.1 KM/S AS A PHASE REFERENCE.

integration period so it can be used as a phase reference. Incoherent averaging of the fringe amplitudes requires long integration times to lower the noise significantly as shown in equation 2-64. Unfortunately W3 (Right Circular Spectrum) is the only source which could be detected. W3(L) and W49 are only half as strong so that the signal to peak noise is less than 1.5:1.

The feeds on the two antennas were not orthogonally polarized and, therefore, presented problems in interpreting the data. The Agassiz antenna had a linear feed at a position angle of 90° on the celestial sphere (measured to the east from north). During the first set of observations the Millstone Antenna had both horizontal and vertical polarization since the antenna is on an alt-azimuth mount. In the second set the Millstone antenna was circularly polarized. This situation was much better because the polarizations were fixed on the sky. With the Millstone antenna linearly polarized at position angle α , the interferometer response will be

$$S_{xy}(\omega) = S_{HV} \cos \alpha + S_{HH} \sin \alpha = (S_2 + jS_3) \cos \alpha + (S_0 - S_1) \sin \alpha \quad (3-30)$$

where the H and V directions are defined as having position angles 90° and 0° on the celestial sphere and the polarization

parameters are defined in Chapter II. If two non-overlapping features which are 100% polarized in the right and left circular sense have fringe phases ψ_R and ψ_L respectively, because they originate from different spatial positions, then the observed difference in phase will be

$$\theta_L - \theta_R = \psi_L - \psi_R + 2\alpha - \pi \quad (3-31)$$

The interferometers response when Millstone was right circularly polarized was

$$S_{xy}(\omega) = S_{HV} + j S_{HH} = S_2 + j (S_0 - S_1 + S_3) \quad (3-32)$$

The data on the -45.1 km/s feature in W3 obtained with Millstone right handedly polarized is shown in figure 3-7. The feature was unresolved and hence the diameter for the uniform bright disc model was less than 1.0" of arc. The linear polarization data at -45.1 km/s was very complex because of the overlapping left and right circularly polarized features and they were never interpreted in terms of fringe amplitude. The -43.7 and -46.5 km/s features were similarly found to be unresolved and smaller than 2.0" of arc in diameter.

The relative fringe phase between the -45.1 and -43.7 km/s features and between the -45.1 and -46.5 km/s features is shown

FIGURE 3-7.

in figure 3-8. The -45.1 km/s and -43.7 km/s features were assumed to be 100 per cent polarized in the right circular sense and the -46.5 km/s feature was assumed to be 100 per cent polarized in the left circular sense. Equation (3-31) was used to deduce the part of the fringe phase attributable to positional displacement. The . 0 and x in figure 3-8 represent horizontal, vertical and right circular polarization of the Millstone antenna. There is no systematic scatter in the data noticeable above the noise implying the assumption that the features are purely circularly polarized is justified.

The relative phases have been interpreted as being caused by relative positional displacements among the features since the features themselves are unresolved.

The phase difference predicted for spatially separated features for this interferometer is

$$\Delta\phi = (\overset{41.5}{\cancel{4.15}} \Delta\delta_S + \Delta\omega\Delta\tau_\ell) + 45.5 \sin(L_S - L_B) \Delta\alpha_S - 84.4 \cos(L_S - L_B) \Delta\delta_S \quad (3-33)$$

$\Delta x / c \cos \delta_S$

where $\Delta\phi$ is the relative phase in degrees after correction is made for polarization effects and $\Delta\alpha_S$ and $\Delta\delta_S$ are the positional offsets in seconds of arc. The $\Delta\omega\Delta\tau_\ell$ is just a constant term for the error in the instrumental delay.

$\Delta\alpha_S, \Delta\delta_S$ and $\Delta\tau_\ell$ were found by fitting the data to equation

FIGURE 3-8. RELATIVE FRINGE PHASE BETWEEN STRONGEST FEATURES IN THE 1665 MHz SPECTRUM OF OH IN W3.

(3-33). The value for τ_{ℓ} derived from the constant term was 53 microseconds which was expected from the propagation time of the relay link. The position offsets measured relative to the -45.1 km/s feature found were:

V km/s	$\Delta\delta$	$\Delta\alpha \cos \delta_S$	$\Delta\alpha$
-43.7	$-.15'' \pm .3$	$.9'' \pm .3$	$.12^s \pm .04$
-45.1	0		0
-46.4	$-.45'' \pm .3$	$-.1'' \pm .3$	$-.01^s \pm .04$

Figure 3-9 shows a map of the relative positions of these features. These results are discussed in a paper by Moran, Barrett, Rogers, Burke, Zuckermann, Penfield and Meeks (1967).

c31-1463

FIGURE 3-9. MAP OF THE CENTERS OF THE STRONGEST FEATURES IN W3. NONE OF THE FEATURES WERE RESOLVED BY THE INTERFEROMETER.

CHAPTER IV

THE VERY LONG BASELINE INTERFEROMETER SYSTEM *

4.1 INTRODUCTION

In this chapter the basic concepts of the very long baseline interferometer are described. The construction and operation of the system are also discussed. The central idea of the technique is that an interferometer can be formed by cross correlating the data recorded independently at two widely separated and unconnected stations. The success of such an experiment depends on the ability to maintain phase coherence between the local oscillators at each site and to synchronize the data recordings. Both of these problems have solutions in the use of atomic frequency standards which provide reference signals of great stability.

The idea of observing OH sources with such a system was conceived in February, 1967, before the technique had been proved feasible. In May, 1967, the joint group from the National Radio Astronomy Observatory and Arecibo Ionospheric Observatory successfully observed several quasi-stellar radio sources with their independent station interferometer operating over approximately a 100 mile baseline at 50 centimeter wavelength, (Bare, Clark, Kellermann, Cohen, Jauncey, 1967). Much of their equipment was used in the OH experiments described *henceforth referred to as the "VLB" system.

here. A Canadian group also succeeded in operating an independent station interferometer with analog recording equipment at about the same time, (Brotten, Locke, Legg, McLeish, Richards, Chisholm, Gush, Yen and Galt, 1967).

The OH long baseline experiments were made possible through the cooperation of the staffs of the Haystack Microwave facility of the M.I.T. Lincoln Laboratory, the National Radio Astronomy Observatory, the Radio Astronomy Laboratory of the University of California, and the Research Laboratory of Electronics of the Chalmers University of Technology.

Figure 4-1 shows a simplified block diagram of the V.L.B. terminals used in the experiments described here. Many people assisted in the construction of this equipment. The NRAO recording and timing system was built by C. Bare of NRAO. The video converters were designed by A.E.E. Rogers and the Haystack interface was built by J. C. Carter. The program to record the data on the U-490 computer was written by P. P. Crowther and a machine language subroutine was written by N. M. Brenner.

4.2 HARDWARE

A. Atomic Standards

The purpose of the atomic frequency standard is to provide a reference signal of exceptional purity and stability which can be used to synthesize the local oscillator signal

FIGURE 4-1

BLOCK DIAGRAM OF VLB INTERFEROMETER HARDWARE

and to run a clock which starts the tape recorder at the proper instant. The operational criterion that the standard must meet is given as

$$\left| \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T e^{j\phi'(t)} e^{-j\omega_{\text{trial}} t} dt \right| \sim 1 \quad (4-1)$$

where

T = integration time

ω_{trial} = a frequency which maximizes integral

$$\phi'(t) = \Delta\omega_0 t + \phi(t) \quad (4-2)$$

so that

$$\langle \phi(t) \rangle_T = 0$$

$\phi'(t)$ is the relative phase between the local oscillators.

In the data processing the frequency offset, $\Delta\omega_0$, between the standards is compensated for by trying various values of ω_{trial} until the integral is maximized. Equation (4-1) is satisfied if

$$\Delta\phi = \sqrt{\langle \phi^2(t) \rangle} \ll \pi \quad (4-3)$$

The data are usually presented in terms of $\Delta f/f$ which is the fractional deviation in the frequency measured over a specified time interval. Figure 4-2 shows data obtained at Hewlett Packard Time Standards Division (November 30, 1967) on various

FIGURE 4-2. FRACTIONAL FREQUENCY AND PHASE FLUCTUATIONS AS A FUNCTION OF AVERAGING PERIOD FOR SEVERAL TYPES OF FREQUENCY STANDARD. THIS DATA WAS OBTAINED BY THE STAFF OF THE HEWLETT PACKARD FREQUENCY AND TIME DIVISION IN NOVEMBER 1967.

types of atomic standards. This data is also shown in terms of phase fluctuations at 1666 MHz. The break in the curves near 100 seconds integration time is caused by flicker noise which determines the long term performance characteristics of the standards.

The hydrogen maser standard is a quantum mechanical oscillator utilizing the transitions between the hyperfine magnetic states of hydrogen whose frequency difference is $1\ 4\ 2\ 0\ 4\ 0\ 5\ 7\ 5\ 1\ .\ 7\ 8\ 6\ 4\ \pm\ .\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 7\ \text{Hz}$ (Vessot, Peters, Vanier, Beehler, Halford, Harrach, Allan, Glaze, Snider, Barnes, Cutler and Bodily, 1966).

The power level out of the oscillator is very low so that it is necessary to employ a 5 MHz crystal oscillator from which hydrogen frequency can be synthesized and phase locked to the maser. The characteristics of the phase lock loop influence the frequency stability since they determine the relative control exerted by the maser and the crystal oscillator. In all types of standards the crystal oscillator determines the short term stability.

The Rubidium standard operates on a completely different principle from the maser oscillator. Here, optical pumping is used to get most of the Rb atoms into the upper level of the ground state which is split by hyperfine interaction.

An RF signal at the hyperfine transition frequency is synthesized from a crystal oscillator and used to induce stimulated emission, which causes absorption of the light doing the optical pumping. The change in optical absorption is sensed by a photocell which provides feedback to control the crystal oscillator. The Rubidium standard is not considered a primary frequency reference because the transition frequency depends on the pressure of the buffer gas in the Rubidium cell which is present to reduce collisions with the walls.

Extreme spectral purity is required of the 5 MHz signal from the standards because of the high multiplication involved in deriving the local oscillator signal. The energy in the frequency sidebands increases with the square of the multiplication factor so that a 5 MHz signal with sidebands 120 db down would produce, after multiplication by 326, a signal at 1630 MHz with sidebands down by 60 db.

B. Local Oscillator System:

The OH radiometer at Haystack already had a phase locked local oscillator system (shown in figure 4.3) which operated from the Haystack hydrogen maser standard. It was used without modification and duplicated for the NRAO radiometer. The local oscillator was a voltage tunable transistor oscillator with about 10 milliwatts output. The 1 MHz and 5 MHz signals

FIGURE 4-3. FIRST PHASE LOCAL OSCILLATOR SYSTEM.

FIGURE 4-3A. SIDEBAND CONVERSION FROM RF TO VIDEO.

from the atomic standard were used to synthesize 67 MHz which was mixed with a sample of the local oscillator signal in a harmonic mixer to produce a signal near 28 MHz. This was combined with a signal at $(28+\Delta)$ MHz, obtained from a HP-5100 synthesizer, in a phase bridge whose error voltage controlled the local oscillator. To assure that the local oscillator was locked to the desired harmonic of 67 MHz, a narrow band filter followed the local oscillator. After the first two experiments, other local oscillator systems were used. For example, the system in use at the Hat Creek Observatory was checked and found satisfactory for these experiments.

C. Video Converters:

The purpose of the video converters was to convert the signal band at 30 MHz to one video band from DC to 120 KHz and another from DC to 6 KHz. They were designed to have band pass characteristics as flat as possible and to have good image rejection. A 6 KHz channel was chosen to pass a single OH feature and, thereby, give the experiment a maximum chance of success because of the rapid data processing afforded by the narrow bandwidth. The 120 KHz channel was wide enough to pass the entire spectrum of most OH sources. Figure 4-4 shows a diagram of the converter design. In the narrow band

FIGURE 4-4
BLOCK DIAGRAM OF
VIDEO CONVERTER

channel the signal was mixed with 29 MHz to give 1 MHz and then put through a quadrature mixer to convert the upper sideband to video. The signal was then amplified. The wideband channel was a standard double conversion system with local oscillator frequencies of 29 MHz and 1 MHz. Filters before each mixer ensured passage of only the upper sideband. Hence, in both channels a signal of 30,005 ^MKHz was converted to 5 KHz. Two of these units were built in April, 1967, and two more, which had only the 120 KHz channel, in December, 1967.

D. Front Ends and Polarizers

The NRAO radiometer was assembled at Haystack. It consisted of a parametric amplifier, mixer and 30 MHz amplifier. It also had a polarizer and a directional coupler and noise tube for calibration purposes. The system temperature was about 180 °K. The front ends at Haystack and later at the Millstone, Hat Creek and Onsala Observatories were already operational.

Probably the best way to obtain a circularly polarized feed for a parabolic reflector is through the use of a helical feed or a horn with a quarter wave section which will produce either right or left circular polarization. Circular polarization can also be obtained from a horn with two orthogonal linear ports. Figure 4-5 shows a test setup for adjusting

FIGURE 4-5. CIRULAR POLARIZER.

CIRCULAR POLARIZATION IS OBTAINED BY ADJUSTING LINE STRETCHER UNTIL THE REFLECTED POWER IS MINIMUM.

the phase between the two ports before they are combined. The delay line is adjusted so that the reflected power is minimum. This procedure was used for the Millstone and NRAO antennas and the rejection was better than 15 db between right and left modes. The delay was adjusted so that the electrical lengths were equal so that the circularity was broadband. The sense of circularity for the feed can be determined by connecting an oscillator to a helix antenna and noting which of the two feed modes gives the most power. The antenna polarization is usually found from the knowledge that the strongest feature in the 1665 MHz spectrum of W3 is right circularly polarized.

E. Haystack Interface and Data Recording

The conversion of the analog signal into a digital format where it could be sent to the UNIVAC-490 computer over an existing data channel was accomplished by the interface system. The signal was slipped (0,-6 volt logic) and fed into a 30 bit shift register which performed the task of sampling and storing the data. The frequencies of the shift pulses were either 240 KHz or 12 KHz and they were derived from the atomic standard. The contents of this shift register were unloaded into another 30 bit shift register from which it was read into the computer. The end of each 0.2 second record of data was signified by setting a code word into the shift register.

The interface could be set to start at any preset time, dialed in on digit switches, so that when the station clock reached the specified time, the data recording would begin automatically.

The data from the interface were recorded on magnetic tape at 556 BPI by the UNIVAC-490 computer with a program called DATARECORD. This program was interleaved with the antenna pointing program and is one of several data processing programs which can be chosen for observing at Haystack.

Each record, which contained data for a period of 0.2 seconds, had either 2400 bits or 48000 bits of data corresponding to the narrow and wide band sampling rates. Each record was prefaced by five 30-bit words which gave the title, time, local hour angle, declination and refraction correction. Having each record labelled with the time meant that the run was not lost if part of the tape was defective. The total duration of the recording was essentially unbounded because of the computer's ability to change to another tape drive when a given tape was full.

F. NRAO Interface and Recording

The NRAO system was built around an AMPEX TM-10 seven track transport. It recorded only at 800 BPI and 150 inches/second so that the sampling rate was effectively fixed at

720,000 bits/second and the total recording duration at about 200 seconds. Because this sampling rate was too high for the OH work, the redundant samples were later discarded. The data were blocked into records of 0.2 second duration with the last 3600 bits of each record lost while making the inter-record gap. The time for any record could be determined only by its rank from the beginning of the recording.

The signal was formatted by a clipper and shift registers which were controlled by pulses derived from the frequency standard.

G. Timing:

At the Haystack site the clock used to control the start of the data recording was in general use and its relationship to UTC accurately known.

The clocks in the portable NRAO units were synchronized before every experiment by the procedure described below. The atomic standard was set as close as possible to 5 MHz by long term comparison to the 60 KHz transmission of WWV from Fort Collins, Colorado. Some of the standards used in the experiments operated on a frequency defined by the UTC second and others on the A1 second. The A1 second is defined as 9192631770.0 Hz of a certain transition in the cesium atom so as to be equal to the second defined by rotation rate of

the earth in epoch 1900.0. Currently the UTC second is 3×10^{-8} parts longer than the AI second, which reflects the fact that the earth's rotation rate has decreased since 1900. UT2 time is based on the actual rotation rate of the earth and UTC time is legislated to conform with the empirical values obtained for UT2.

Regardless of the time base of the atomic standard the sampling rate was always fixed at the UTC rate whereas the local oscillator settings were computer so that the actual frequencies would be the same by noting that $f_{1666(AI)} - f_{1666(UTC)} = 49.98$ Hz. Most time services transmit time ticks on the UTC time base although some use carrier frequencies based on the AI rate.

The "clock" in the NRAO terminal consists of a system of digital divider and counter circuits which operate from the frequency standard and produce synchronization waveforms with periods of 10, 0.5 and 0.1 Hz. The 720 KHz sampling signal is derived by dividing 5 MHz by $6 \frac{17}{18}$, achieved by dividing the reference by 7 for 17 out of 18 times and by 6 on the remaining time. The lower frequency signals are obtained by additional division. The clock is advanced or retarded by changing the ratio of times that the reference signal is divided by six and by seven.

Figure 4-6 shows a possible five step procedure for setting the clock. The 0.5 Hz waveform is used to trigger the oscilloscope whose vertical input is connected to a WWV receiver. The clock is started manually "when the tone returns" on the WWV transmission. Enough pulses are added or subtracted to advance or retard the synchronization pulse so that the WWV second tick shown in figure 4-6(1) occurs about 15 ms. after the trigger. The 0.1 Hz synchronization is used to trigger the scope as shown in figure 4-6(2). The appearance of the double tick on the minute assures that the correct second tick is being used. Figure 4-6(3) shows the 10 Hz synchronization pattern and the LORAN C waveform. The LORAN C transmissions are maintained by the U.S. Coast Guard primarily as a navigation aid since positions can be obtained by noting the arrival time of pulses from several stations of the East Coast chain. The carrier frequency is 100 KHz and the pattern repeats every 0.1 second. The presence of a ninth pulse in figure 4-6(3) indicates that this transmission is from the master station in Cape Fear, North Carolina. Figures 4-6(4) and 4-6(5) show the oscilloscope triggering on every pulse. The loops are caused by a phase reversal in the modulation of alternate pulses. Since the ground wave propagation time of the LORAN C signals can be

TIME SYNCHRONIZATION

WWV FORT COLLINS, COLORADO

1. SECOND TICK 5 ms/cm

2. DOUBLE TICK 20 ms/cm

LORAN C CAPE FEAR, N.C.

3. TOP: SYNC PULSE 1 ms/cm

4. LORAN PULSE 20 μs/cm

5. 5 μs/cm

FIGURE 4-6.

calculated quite accurately and the delay in the receivers estimated, the synchronization between two stations can be done to an accuracy of a few microseconds without particular effort. This procedure was used at NRAO and Onsala, Sweden. At Hat Creek, California, a Helwitt-Packard portable cesium beam standard was used to synchronize the station.

4.3 SIGNAL PROCESSING:

The signal processing scheme for the interferometer is rather elementary but some aspects of it are new to radio astronomy. One of the features is that a general purpose computer is relied upon to do all the processing after the video signals are digitized.

The purpose of the processing is to estimate the correlation of the electric field components along the wavefront as a function of frequency, ω ,

$$S_{ab}(\vec{A}, \omega) = \langle E_a(\vec{r}_1, \omega) E_b(\vec{r}_2, \omega) \rangle \quad (4-4)$$

where $E_a(\vec{r}_1, \omega)$ is a component of the E field at point $\vec{r}_1$ on the plane perpendicular to the propagation vector, $\vec{k}$, and $E_b(\vec{r}_2, \omega)$ is another component at point $\vec{r}_2$. $\vec{A}$ is the projected baseline vector equal to $\vec{r}_1 - \vec{r}_2$. To determine S_{ab} the voltages $x(t)$ and $y(t)$ induced in the receiving elements by E_a and E_b

are converted to the video frequency range by a triple conversion process and filtered. The signals are recorded and later cross correlated. The correlation function is Fourier transformed and compensated for the delay and doppler shift introduced by the earth's rotation, and for the frequency offsets of the atomic standards. All the essential elements of this procedure are shown in figure 4-7. The three stages of bandpass filtering and mixing are lumped into one stage so that the local oscillator shown in the figure operates at a frequency equal to the sum of the three actual local oscillator frequencies.

The frequency conversion properties of mixers are shown in figure 4-3. We will consider in detail the single sideband system but, also, give some results for the double sideband system. It is very important to notice how the lower sideband has its frequency components reversed. This shows the necessity of having compatible frequency conversion schemes for each receiver in an interferometer.

The signals received at antennas 1 and 2 are $x(t - \tau_t)$ and $y(t)$ when referred to the reference plane perpendicular to $\vec{k}$. Over a finite time these signals have Fourier transforms given by

$$X(\omega) = \int x(t) e^{-j\omega t} dt \tag{4-5}$$

$$Y(\omega) = \int y(t) e^{-j\omega t} dt$$

FIGURE 4-7. BLOCK DIAGRAM OF SIGNAL PROCESSING SCHEME. ALL PROCESSING AFTER THE DATA IS SAMPLED AND RECORDED IS DONE IN A GENERAL PURPOSE COMPUTER.

It should be noted that $|X(\omega)|^2$ is the same estimate of the power spectrum as the Fourier transform of the autocorrelation function if care is taken to ensure that the frequency resolutions are equal. The output of the bandpass filters whose responses are $G_x(\omega)$ and $G_y(\omega)$, are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} X'(\omega) &= X(\omega) e^{-j\omega\tau} G_x(\omega) \\ Y'(\omega) &= Y(\omega) G_y(\omega) \end{aligned} \right\} \omega > 0 \quad (4-6)$$

The local oscillator frequency is ω_0 . A phase term $\phi(t)$ is added to one of the local oscillators which includes the intentional frequency offset, the random frequency offset, and the relative phase noise between the two oscillators. The mixer outputs, assuming that the filters have removed the lower sidebands, is

$$\left. \begin{aligned} X''(\omega) &= X(\omega + \omega_0) e^{-j(\omega + \omega_0)\tau} G_x(\omega + \omega_0) \\ Y''(\omega) &= Y(\omega + \omega_0) G_y(\omega + \omega_0) e^{-j\phi(t)} \end{aligned} \right\} \omega > 0$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} X''(\omega) &= X''^*(-\omega) \\ Y''(\omega) &= Y''^*(-\omega) \end{aligned} \right\} \omega < 0 \quad (4-7)$$

The power obtained after introducing a delay τ_T in tape 1 and cross-correlating the signal is

$$S_{xy}(\omega) = X(\omega + \omega_0) \left[e^{-j(\omega + \omega_0)\tau_T} \right] \left[e^{-j\omega\tau_T + \phi(t)} \right] Y^*(\omega + \omega_0) G_X(\omega + \omega_0) G_Y^*(\omega + \omega_0)$$

$$= S^*(-\omega) \quad \omega < 0$$

(4-8)

The phase term $\phi(t)$ is expanded into its components

$$\phi(t) = (\omega_s + \Delta\omega)t + \phi'(t)$$

where

ω_s = intentional local oscillator offset put in to compensate for the doppler shift of the earth's rotation and, thereby, facilitate the data processing.

$\Delta\omega$ = random frequency offset due to atomic standards.

$\phi'(t)$ = zero mean phase random variable.

$S_{xy}(\omega)$ is filtered at many fringe rates to locate the signal.

That is

$$S'_{xy}(\omega, \omega_R) = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T S_{xy}(\omega) e^{j[\omega_R t + \theta(t) - \omega_s t]} dt$$

(4-9)

where $\theta(t)$ is the estimate of the total fringe phase calculated from equation (2-5), and ω_R the fringe frequency search variable

which is adjusted until S'_{xy} is maximized. This occurs when

$$T = -\tau_t$$

$$\omega_R = -\Delta\omega$$

(4-10)

so that

$$S'_{xy}(\omega, \omega_R = -\Delta\omega) = X_1(\omega + \omega_0) X_2(\omega + \omega_0) G_x(\omega + \omega_0) G_y(\omega + \omega_0) \langle e^{j\phi'(t)} \rangle_T$$

(4-11)

Hence it is clear that proper operation of the system requires

$$\langle e^{j\phi'(t)} \rangle \sim 1$$

(4-12)

Using the results of Chapter II and noting that we compute a normalized $S'_{xy}(m)$ from the clipped signal then the normalized fringe visibility is,

$$A(m) = \frac{S'_{xy}(\omega) \sqrt{T_{S_1} T_{S_2}}}{\sqrt{T_{A_1}(\omega) T_{A_2}(\omega)} G_x(m) G_y^*(\omega)}$$

(4-13)

where T_{S_1} and T_{S_2} are the system temperatures of the two systems and $T_{A_1}(\omega)$ and $T_{A_2}(\omega)$ are the single antenna profiles.

The actual processing is done by computing the cross correlation function of the two signals as shown in figure 4-7. It is interesting to examine the form of this function which is given by

$$R_{xy}(\tau) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} S_{xy}(\omega) e^{j\omega\tau} d\omega \quad (4-14)$$

Substituting equation (4-8) into (4-14) and assuming $X(\omega) X^*(\omega) G_x(\omega) G_y^*(\omega) \approx 1$ in the frequency band from zero to ω_m , which is approximately the case for a continuum source, gives

$$R_{xy}(\tau) = 2\omega_m \left[\cos(\omega_0 \tau_t + \phi(t)) \times \frac{\sin \omega_m \tau'}{\omega_m \tau'} - \sin(\omega_0 \tau_t + \phi(t)) \times \frac{\sin \frac{2\omega_m \tau'}{2}}{\frac{\omega_m \tau'}{2}} \right] \quad (4-15)$$

where $\tau' = \tau_t + \tau_T + \tau$. Notice that $R_{xy}(\tau)$ has an even and odd part so that the its functional form depends on the fringe and instrumental phases. In the same way $R'_{xy}(\tau)$ can be computed from $S'_{xy}(\tau)$. It is clear that the fringe amplitude cannot be estimated merely by taking the peak value of the

correlation function. The easiest way, even though the source may be a continuum source, to find the fringe amplitude is to compute $S'_{xy}(\omega)$ and average over the spectrum. The last section of this chapter gives examples of this behavior.

The double sideband system, on the other hand, always gives a correlation function which is an even function of delay, that is

$$R_{xy}(\tau) = \cos(\omega_0 \tau_t + \phi(t)) \frac{\sin \omega_m \tau'}{\omega_m \tau'} \quad (4-16)$$

where $\tau' = \tau_t + \tau_T + \tau$. In this case the peak value of $R_{xy}(\tau)$ is proportional to the fringe amplitude and there is no need to compute the power spectrum.

4.4 COMPUTER PROGRAMS

A series of computer programs were written by the author for the VLB project. They fall into three categories:

- A. Observational
- B. Raw data processing
- C. Post processing

All the programs were written in FORTRAN and the machine language COMPASS for use on the CDC-3300 computer at Haystack.

A. Observational Programs

The one observation program is called INTERFER. It is a

very flexible program which predicts all the necessary observing parameters for a spectral line interferometer. Either the baseline parameters or the longitude, latitude and elevation of each site are entered along with the source coordinates, the source velocity with respect to the local standard of rest and the start and stop time for the computations.

The program computes the baseline vector in rectangular and polar coordinates in several coordinate frames by using the standard ellipsoid model for the shape of the earth. The results of this computation are listed in Tables 5-1 and 5-2 for all the baselines used here. The position of the source is found by precessing the coordinates to the current epoch and the local hour angles and elevations of the source at both sites are listed at 5 minute intervals for all times when it is above the horizon at both sites. The projected baseline parameters and fringe rates are also listed. The velocity with respect to the local standard of rest is computed and exact local oscillator settings for each station are listed which will place the desired velocity component in the center of the band and make the apparent fringe rate equal to zero. The local oscillator settings are converted from the actual local oscillator frequencies by reference to the specific system being used.

With the aid of this program, observing schedules were made so that measurements could be made at the best projected baselines with local oscillator frequencies predicted so that the desired portion of the spectrum was in the center of the band.

B. Raw Data Processing Programs

The main processing programs were called AUTOCOR and GREENSTAK. AUTOCOR computed the spectra from single tapes while GREENSTAK computed the cross correlation spectra from pairs of tapes. GREENSTAK had three forms: GREENSTAK - for processing a "Haystack" and a "NRAO" tape; GREENHAT - for processing two NRAO tapes; and JODBANK for processing two "Haystack" tapes. The subroutines of these programs, shown in figure 4-8, perform the signal processing function in figure 4-2.

The purpose of GREENSTAK is to compute $S_{xy}(\omega)$, the crossed spectral function, given by equation (4-11). The program reads in one record from each tape at a time, discards redundant bits of data, and breaks it up into ten blocks of about 4800 bits of data each in the wide band case corresponding to 20 milliseconds of recorded signal. These bit strings are called X(I) and Y(I) respectively. Subroutine CORREL, which does the bulk of computations, takes the bit strings, shifts X(I) by the number of bits I_{Delay} which is

Program COMPRESS - Removes redundant samples from data bit strings. (Takes every third or twentieth bit for the 120 KHz and 6 KHz bandwidths respectively.

Subroutine READGB - reads NRAO data tape
EXTRACT - extracts nonredundant bits and makes a new bit string.

Program GREENSTAK - Computes interference spectra.

Subroutine READHAY - reads data tape recorded on Haystack Univac 490 computer.
READGH - reads extracted NRAO tape.
CORREL - cross correlates bit strings.
CPXFOUR - computes complex fourier transform.
PLOT2V - specialized printer plot routine

Program AUTOCOR - Computes power spectra and subtracts baseline spectrum.

Subroutine READHAY
READGH
CORREL
FOURT
PLOTV

Program REPLOT - Replots interference spectra with several weighting function options. Displays fringe amplitude as a contour plot for frequency and fringe frequency.

Subroutine FOURT - Fast fourier transform routine
CONTOUR - finds contours.

Figure 4-8. List of computer programs which are used to process the raw interferometer data.

equivalent to τ_T and computes

$$\rho_t(J) = \sum_{I=1}^{4800} X(I - I_{\text{Delay}}(t) - J) \cdot Y(I) \quad (4-17)$$

where $\rho_t(J)$ is the normalized version of equation 4-15.

CORREL enters one 24 bit register with $X(I - I_{\text{Delay}}(t) - J)$ and another with $Y(I)$ and uses an "exclusive or" instruction to multiply the two words. The answer is another 24 bit word whose bits are summed by looking the answer up for the bit pattern in a table. The arithmetic is

$$1 \times 1 = 0 \times 0 = 1$$

$$0 \times 1 = 1 \times 0 = 0$$

For example, if $X(I - I_{\text{Delay}}) = 52265425_8$ and $Y(I) = 15145113_8$

then $\rho_t(1) = 13_8$. $\rho_t(J)$ is then multiplied by sine and cosine

of the fringe phase plus an instrumental phase due to a frequency

offset between the standards. These correspond to the Fourier

transform of equation (4-9) before the time average is taken

and are given by

$$R_{\cos}(J,L) = \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{1}{T} \sum_t \left[\frac{\rho_t(J)}{N} - 1 \right] \cos\{\theta(t) - [\omega_S + L\Delta\omega_R]t\}$$

$$R_{\sin}(J,L) = \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{1}{T} \sum_t \left[\frac{\rho_t(J)}{N} - 1 \right] \sin\{\theta(t) - [\omega_S + L\Delta\omega_R]t\}$$

$N = 4800$ and the bracketed term converts ρ_t into the normalized correlation function discussed in Chapter II which is computed from $\{+1, -1\}$ logic. $\pi/2$ is the clipping correction and T is the total integration time. $\theta(t)$ is the fringe phase computed for each 0.02 second interval and ω_s is the difference in the local oscillator frequencies which was usually chosen to equal $-d\theta/dt$ at the beginning of the run. $L\Delta\omega_R$, equal to ω_R in equation (4-9), are a series of offset fringe frequencies to compensate for the unknown difference in recorded signal frequencies caused by errors in frequency in the atomic standards and errors in the baseline and source position. The two indices J and L are, therefore, delay and fringe rate offsets from their expected values. The summation on time can run up to 200 seconds but usually stops at 40 seconds so the Fourier transform can be taken:

$$S'_{xy}(k) = \int_{(k)} \{R_{\cos}(J,L) + j R_{\sin}(J,L)\} \quad (4-19)$$

that is

$$\begin{aligned}
 R_e \{S_{xy}(K,L)\} &= \sum_J [R_{\cos}(J,L) \cdot \cos(k\Delta\omega_J\Delta\tau) - R_{\sin}(J,L) \sin(k\Delta\omega_J\Delta\tau)] W(k) \\
 I_m \{S_{xy}(K,L)\} &= \sum_J [R_{\cos}(J,L) \sin(k\Delta\omega_J\Delta\tau) + R_{\sin}(J,L) \cos(k\Delta\omega_J\Delta\tau)] W(k)
 \end{aligned}
 \quad (4-20)$$

where $W(k)$ is a weighting function introduced to reduce spectra confusion. Finally,

$$|S_{xy}(K,L)| = \sqrt{\text{Re}\{S_{xy}(K,L)\}^2 + \text{Im}\{S_{xy}(K,L)\}^2} \quad (4-21)$$

and

$$\psi_{xy}(K,L) = \text{Tan}^{-1} \frac{\text{Im } S_{xy}(K,L)}{\text{Re } S_{xy}(K,L)} \quad (4-22)$$

All important variables are written out on magnetic tape for further processing. The main program recycles and continues to process the same pair of tapes. $R_{\cos}$ and $R_{\sin}$ can be cleared to begin a new integration period or new data can be accumulated with the old.

The standard data reduction format followed for most of the wide band tapes is as follows:

- (1) A "finder" run is done to locate the signal in fringe rate space with

$T = 20$ seconds or 100 records (integration time)

$J = 200$ (Delay Boxes)

$K = 240$ (Frequency Boxes)

$L = 11$ (Fringe Rate Boxes)

$\Delta u_R / 2\pi = 0.3$ Hz

(2) A final processing run consisting of two, three, or four cumulative groups of 200 records each with $\Delta t = 40$ seconds, 200 records.

$$J = 200$$

$$K = 240$$

$$L = 11$$

$$\Delta\omega/2\pi = 0.004 \text{ Hz}$$

Use of the hanning weighting function gives spectra with resolution of 2.4 Hz with one point per 0.5 KHz so that the shape of the spectra is clearly delineated without non-linear interpolation.

The running time for GREENSTAK on the CDC-3300 computer has been measured. CORREL required 1.6 microseconds per one bit multiply. 75% of the normal processing time is spent in CORREL: the rest is in the fringe rotation and bookkeeping. A few additional minutes at the end of each run is needed to compute the Fourier transforms and list and plot the results. Hence, the time required to process 400 records of data; i.e., 80 seconds, with a 200 point correlation function is

$$T \sim [400 \times 43200 \times 200 \times 1.6 \times 10^{-6}] \frac{1}{75} \sim 7400 \text{ seconds}$$

or in general

$$T \sim M \cdot N \cdot 21 \times 10^{-6} \text{ seconds} \quad (4-23)$$

where

M = number of records

N = number of delays

This running time is probably about the same for an IBM 360 MOD 50 and four times the time required for an IBM 360 MOD 65.

AUTOCOR operates on the data on individual tapes for the purpose of computing the single antenna responses used in equation 4-13 to normalize the crossed spectra. The individual tapes contain the power spectrum of the signal plus receiver noise so that it is useful to have a comparison tape, such as one made on a continuum source, to extract the signal spectrum alone. Usually, the system gain is stable enough so that the two tapes can be taken several hours apart. This program computes

$$T_A(K) = T_s \frac{S_{on}(K) - S_{off}(K)}{S_{off}(K)} \quad (4-24)$$

where

$$S_{on}(K) - S_{off}(K) = \sum_{J=2}^N \left\{ \sin \frac{\pi}{2} \left[\frac{2\rho_{on}(J) - \rho_{on}(1)}{\rho_{on}(1)} \right] - \sin \frac{\pi}{2} \left[\frac{2\rho_{off}(J) - \rho_{off}(1)}{\rho_{off}(1)} \right] \right\} \cdot W(J) \cdot \cos \frac{(J-1)(K-1)}{2N} \quad (4-25)$$

N, the number of points in the autocorrelation need only be chosen half as large as in the case of the crosscorrelation function since the autocorrelation function is an even function and, hence, actual 2N points are measured. N is usually chosen equal to 100 to give 2.4 kc/s resolution.

Programs INTERFER and GREENSTAK are listed in Appendix 1.

There are three difficulties introduced by the digital computation described above:

- 1) fringe rate compensation
- 2) delay truncation
- 3) weighting function

which will be briefly discussed.

Frate Compensation:

The way the program is set up, the correlation function must be constant over the 0.02 second interval or the apparent correlation will decrease because of the smearing. This decrease in correlation, shown in 4-9, is just

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{T} \left| \int_0^T e^{j\omega_0 t} dt \right| \quad (4-26)$$

where T is the 0.02" interval and ω_0 is the apparent fringe rate equal to the difference between the natural fringe rate ω_F , and the local oscillator offset, ω_s ,

FIGURE 4-9. DECREASE IN MEASURED FRINGE AMPLITUDE VERSUS APPARENT FRINGE RATE. THE BASIC INTEGRATION TIME, T, USED IN THESE EXPERIMENTS WAS 0.02 SECONDS.

FIGURE 4-10. DECREASE IN MEASURED FRINGE AMPLITUDE VERSUS VIDEO FREQUENCY. THIS EFFECT IS CAUSED BY ROUNDING OFF THE GEOMETRIC DELAY TO THE NEAREST DATA SAMPLE. THE DOTS SHOW THE FRINGE AMPLITUDE ON THE SOURCE 3C273 BUT THE NOISE IS TOO HIGH SEE THIS EFFECT CLEARLY.

$$\omega_0 = [\omega_F - \omega_S]$$

In most of the processing it was not even necessary to correct for this effect since the apparent fringe rate was usually less than a few Hz. In theory, methods could be devised to compensate for fringe rates approaching the recorded bandwidth since all that is required is that the recorded signals have some mutual fourier components.

Delay Truncation:

Equation 4-17 shows how the bit string is shifted an integral number of bits to take out the geometric delay. On the wide bandwidth the delay changes enough so that at the end of the run the compensation is several bits different from what it was at the beginning. The truncation of the delay to an integral bit produces an error which is roughly uniformly spread between $\pm \frac{1}{2}$ bit, i.e. $\pm \tau = \frac{1}{2f_s}$. Hence, the spectrum is phase shifted between $\phi = \pm \pi \frac{f}{f_s}$ and therefore

$$S(\omega) = S_0(\omega) \left[\frac{1}{f_s} \int_{-\frac{1}{2f_s}}^{\frac{1}{2f_s}} e^{j\omega\tau} d\tau \right] = S_0(\omega) \left[\frac{\sin \pi \frac{f}{f_s}}{\pi \frac{f}{f_s}} \right] \quad (4-27)$$

where f_s is the sampling frequency. The reduction in $S(\omega)$ depends on ω , curiously enough. The value of the effect is

0 at $f=0$; 0.9 at band center and .64 at band edge. This effect is visible in the 3C273 spectrum shown in figure 4-10.

Weighting Function:

We can only afford to estimate the correlation function over a small number of delays so that our estimate is actually the product of the true correlation function and some other function, called the weighting function which is zero outside the range when $R(\tau)$ is measured; i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} R_{\text{est}}(\tau) &= R(\tau) \cdot w(\tau) \\ w(\tau) &= w(-\tau) \\ w(\tau) &= 0 \quad |T| > \tau_{\text{max}} \end{aligned} \tag{4-28}$$

and hence

$$S_{\text{est}}(\omega) = S(\omega) \otimes W(\omega)$$

where $\otimes$ denotes convolution and $W(\omega)$, the Fourier transfer of $W(\tau)$, is called the scanning function. The problem is to choose a weighting function which goes smoothly to zero at τ_{max} so that the "ringing" or sidelobes are small, but on the other hand, is as broad as possible so that the resolution is not seriously reduced. This problem is extensively discussed in connection with power spectra estimation and antenna theory, (Blackman and Tukey, 1958).

The choice of a weighting function is normally of little interest in radio astronomy, the hanning function being widely accepted, but is important here because of the great amount of computer time consumed here in the signal processing in order to obtain sufficient resolution. For example, in most cases it is too time consuming to compute enough delays to get enough resolution to resolve the line profile. Hence, in trying to detect a weak signal it is better to use uniform rather than hanning weighting since the signal to noise is higher,

$$\frac{[S/N]_{\text{Uniform}}}{[S/N]_{\text{Hanning}}} = \frac{[T_A/R_U] / \sqrt{R_U}^\tau}{[T_A/R_H] / \sqrt{R_H}^\tau} = \sqrt{\frac{R_H}{R_U}} = 1.3$$

where R_U and R_H are the resolution obtained from uniform and hanning weighting respectively, and τ is the integer time. Naturally, if $S/N_{\text{Peak}} > 5$ then the sidelobes are visible with uniform weighting and weak features cannot be distinguished from them. Table 4-1 list some commonly used scanning functions and their characteristics. Hanning has usually been used in most of the processing done here.

TABLE 4-1. COMMONLY USED WEIGHTING FUNCTIONS

WEIGHTING FUNCTION ^{**} R(τ)	NAME	PEAK SIDELOBE	RESOLUTION ^{***}
1	Uniform	.217	.60 f_s/N
$1 - \tau /\tau_m$	Triangle	.05	.88 f_s/N
$.5 + .5 \cos \pi\tau/\tau_m$	Hanning	.025	1.0 f_s/N
$.54 + .46 \cos \pi\tau/\tau_m$	Hamming	.006	.95 f_s/N
$.42 + .5 \cos \pi\tau/\tau_m + 0.08 \cos 2\pi\tau/\tau_m$	Blackman	.0014	1.13 f_s/N

* all weighting functions are zero for $\tau > \tau_m$.

** f_s is the sampling frequency and N is the number of points in the autocorrelation function or one half the number of points in the crosscorrelation function. (This is because in the autocorrelation function the number of points is 2N since the function has to be even in τ .)

C. Post Processing Programs

There are many programs which are used on the data output from GREENSTAK. One program is REPLOT which read the correlation functions recorded on tape and replots the spectra with a different weighting function and divides them by the bandpass spectrum. It also produces two dimensional contour diagrams of fringe amplitude versus fringe rate and velocity.

There are several model fitting programs such as MODEL which fits the fringe amplitude response of a double source whose frequency spectrum consists of overlapping Gaussian features. Program FRMAP computes the angular separation of non-overlapping features from the relative fringe rate information and program POSITION computes the same quantities from the relative phase data.

4-5 TESTS:

During the week of May 23, 1967, the entire VLB system was assembled in the Haystack random for phase coherence tests. This allowed for a complete test of the equipment and processing program. The only effects unaccounted for were the atmosphere and the fact that both units were essentially in the same environment.

Three of the test performed were:

1. Phase comparison at 30 MHz and 3KHz with a sine wave signal. Both stations on same standard.

2. Phase comparison at 30 MHz and 3 KHz with a sine wave input and separate standards.
3. Cross correlation of sampled data with noise input signal, separate standards, independent starting of tape recorders.

The setups for these tests are depicted in figure 4-11. Tests 1 and 2 were generally run at 30 MHz, after the converters were formed to be working properly, since a Hewlett-Packard phase meter was available which worked at 30 MHz. Test 1 checked the phase stability of the local oscillator systems and the parametric amplifiers. The input sine wave signal was derived from a phase locked oscillator set at 1666 MHz. The phase difference as a function of time for a two hour period is shown in figure 4-12. Most of the slow drift seems attributable to temperature changes in the random since the cable lengths were not equal. This test proved that the local oscillators and parametric amplifiers did not introduce their own noise into the system. Figure 4-13 shows the results of Test 2 where one local oscillator was slightly offset in frequency. The phase noise is attributable to the atomic frequency standards.

Test 3 comprised the most complete check of the apparatus. Figure 4-14 shows the cross spectra obtained for a white noise signal input. These spectra were used as the instrumental bandpass function, $G_x(\omega) G_y^*(\omega)$, correcting the amplitudes and

FIGURE 4-11. TEST CONFIGURATION FOR MEASURING THE PHASE STABILITY AND TIME SYNCHRONIZATION OF THE VLB SYSTEM IN THE LABORATORY. THE RESULTS OF THE MEASUREMENTS ARE SHOWN IN FIGURES 4-12, 13 and 14.

RELATIVE PHASE VERSUS TIME
BOTH TERMINALS ON THE SAME STANDARD

FIGURE 4-12. TEST 1 RESULTS.

FIGURE 4-13. TEST 2 results: 1666 MHz sine wave signal put into VLB terminals, each of which is running off its own frequency standard, and the relative signal phase measured at 30 MHz versus time. 36 minutes of data shown.

FIGURE 4 - 14. TEST 3 RESULTS. IN THIS TEST A NOISE TUBE WAS FIRED INTO BOTH VLB TERMINALS WHICH WERE OPERATING INDEPENDENTLY AND THE VIDEO SIGNALS WERE RECORDED ON MAGNETIC TAPE AND PROCESSED ON THE CDC-3300 COMPUTER. THE CORRELATION SPECTRA WERE USED AS BANDPASS GAIN FUNCTIONS IN THE EXPERIMENTS.

phases of the measured spectra on radio sources. From this test the relative instrumental delay was obtained for the system. This delay, NRAO relative to Haystack was about 4400 microseconds on the 6 KHz channel and 5370 microseconds on the 120 KHz channels. These delays were measured when the start time of the Haystack recording was already delayed by 300,000 microseconds.

4-6 OPERATIONAL RESULTS:

The first observations were made from June 8th to 10th, 1967. The main emphasis of these initial observations was on narrow band observations of the strongest feature in W3. Figure 4-15 shows one of the first detections of W3 with the VLB system. Figure 4-16 shows the apparent fringe rate at which the -45.1 KM/S feature in W3 appeared during the course of the experiment. These are also plotted versus local hour angle with a roughly fitted sine curve drawn through the points. The offset in fringe rate appears to be dominated by position errors rather than by atomic standard frequency errors. The sine wave shown implies

$$\Delta f_{\text{STD}} \sim 0.03 \text{ Hz}$$

$$\Delta \alpha_{\text{S}} + \Delta L_{\text{B}} \sim 3.5''$$

$$50 \Delta D - (\Delta \delta_{\text{S}} + \Delta \delta_{\text{B}}) \sim 3.5''$$

FIGURE 4-15. FIRST EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS WITH THE HAYSTACK-NRA INTERFEROMETER. SHOWN IS A PHOTOGRAPH OF THE COMPUTER PRINTOUT OF AN INTERFERENCE SPECTUM ON W3 COVERING 3 KHZ FOR EACH OF THREE DIFFERENT FRINGE RATES. (JUNE 10, 1967).

FIGURE 4-16. FRINGE RATE OFFSETS MEASURED ON W3 AND INTERPRETED AS BEING CAUSED BY BASELINE AND SOURCE POSITION ERRORS+

where $\Delta\alpha_S$, ΔL_B , $\Delta\delta_S$ and $\Delta\delta_B$ are the source and baseline position errors in arc seconds and ΔD is the baseline length error in kilometers. f_{STD} is the average frequency difference between the local oscillators caused by frequency offsets in the atomic standards. Hence the baseline length is probably accurate to a few hundred meters.

Because the signal-to-noise ratio is so high on W3, the relative behavior of the atomic standards can be monitored. Figure 4-17 shows the fringe phase versus time for a time constant of 2 seconds. Notice that one of the standards shifted phase and frequency during the run. This behavior is characteristic of about 10% of the observations. The fringe amplitude for the same run is shown in figure 4-18. The rms fluctuations are very close to the theoretically expected value indicating that the system was operating properly. This also shows that there are no scintillations with a time scale of the order of 2 seconds.

Tapes taken on 3C273 on the Hat Creek-NRAO interferometer illustrate some of the data processing steps. Figure 4-19 shows $R_{\cos}(\tau)$ and $R_{\sin}(\tau)$ which show the behavior predicted by equation 4-15. The Fourier transform of $R_{\cos} + j R_{\sin}$ yields a spectrum whose shape is just the geometric mean bandpass of the system. The fringe amplitude at

FIGURE 4-17. MEASURED FRINGE PHASE IN TWO SECOND INTERVALS VERSUS TIME FOR A NARROW BAND W3 OBSERVATION. THE DISCONTINUITY AT 160 SECONDS IS ATTRIBUTED TO A PHASE JUMP IN ONE OF THE FREQUENCY STANDARDS.

FIGURE 4 - 18. THE MEASURED FRINGE AMPLITUDE ON THE -45.1 KM/S FEATURE IN W3 VERSUS TIME IN TWO SECOND INTERVALS. THE FLUCTUATIONS ARE DUE ALMOST EXCLUSIVELY TO RECEIVER NOISE.

FIGURE 4-19.

band center versus fringe rate offset is shown in figure 4-20. The OH data provide a good method of calibrating the fringe amplitudes obtained on 3C273 and other continuum sources. The spectrum obtained from an OH recording is normalized to the system temperature. If the flux is known, then the ratio of system temperature to collecting area of the antenna can be obtained. Since the spectrum of a continuum is flat over the recorded bandwidth, there is no indication of the presence of a recorded signal on the tape. The 3C273 run shown was normalized by using the equation

$$A = \frac{1}{R} \frac{S_{OH} P_{12}}{S_C \sqrt{P_1 P_2}} \quad (4-29)$$

where R is the correction effect discussed for the phase noise introduced by the frequency standards and in the data processing. S_{OH} and S_C are the respective fluxes of the OH and continuum sources and P_1 and P_2 are the normalized power obtained on the OH source at sites 1 and 2 respectively and P_{12} is the cross spectral value obtained on 3C273. The result is a fringe amplitude of 0.6 for 3C273 on a baseline of 19×10^6 wavelengths.

The main effect of phase noise in the local oscillators is to spread out the signal in fringe rate space. The fringe amplitude can be estimated in the presence of phase noise by appropriately adding up the signal fragments. The interferometer response before doing the fringe rate filtering is given by

30273

FRINGE FREQUENCY (cps)

FIGURE 4-20. THE FRINGE AMPLITUDE OF 30273 VERSUS FRINGE FREQUENCY. THE SOLID LINE IS THE FILTER SHAPE AND EXPECTED RESPONSE AND THE DOTS ARE THE MEASURED AMPLITUDE. THE STRUCTURE IN THE SIDELOBES IS A MEASURE OF THE SYSTEM PHASE NOISE.

$$g(t) = S e^{j\omega_R t} e^{j\phi(t)} \quad (4-30)$$

where ω_R is the unknown fringe rate and $\phi(t)$ represents the zero mean phase noise. We wish to estimate S . The Fourier transform $S e^{j\omega_R t}$ is $A(\omega_f)$ and of $e^{j\phi(t)}$ is $F(\omega_f)$ so that the Fourier transform of $g(t)$ is

$$G(\omega_f) = A(\omega_f) \otimes F(\omega_f) \quad (4-31)$$

where ω_f is the fringe frequency.

Examples of $G(\omega_f)$ and $A(\omega_f)$ are shown in figure 4-20 (dotted and solid line respectively). For an integration time of T , $A(\omega_f)$ is

$$A(\omega_f) = S e^{\left\{ \frac{j(\omega_R - \omega_f)T}{2} \right\}} \frac{\sin\left[(\omega_R - \omega_f) \frac{T}{2} \right]}{(\omega_R - \omega_f) \frac{T}{2}} \quad (4-32)$$

and

$$F(\omega_f) = \int_0^T e^{j\phi(t)} e^{-j\omega_f t} dt \quad (4-33)$$

Using Parseval's theorem

$$\int |G(\omega_f)|^2 df = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T |g(t)|^2 dt = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T S^2 dt = S^2 \quad (4-33)$$

and hence

$$S = \left[\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |G(\omega_f)|^2 d\omega_f \right]^{1/2} \quad (4-35)$$

which is easily measured. The estimate is biased since S is always a positive number even in the absence of signal. If a small noise term, $n(t)$, is added to $g(t)$ such that

$$\langle n^2(t) \rangle = T_{S_1} T_{S_2} \frac{1}{B\tau} \quad (4-36)$$

where T_{S_1} and T_{S_2} are the system temperatures, B is the resolution bandwidth and τ is the integration time. The unbiased estimate is

$$S^* = \left[\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |G(\omega_f)|^2 d\omega_f - \frac{T_{S_1} T_{S_2}}{B\tau} \right]^{1/2} \quad (4-37)$$

This problem is discussed by Clark, Bare, Cohen, Jauncey and Kellermann (1968).

The first OH measurement with the long baseline interferometer using independent standards is reported by Moran, Burke, Barrett, Rogers, Ball, Carter, and Bare (1967).

CHAPTER V

RESULTS OF VERY LONG BASELINE OBSERVATION

5.1 SUMMARY OF EXPERIMENTS

Five VLB interferometers were completed between June, 1967, and January, 1968. The first one was carried out between Westford, Massachusetts, and Greenbank, West Virginia, a distance of 845 kilometers. In January, four stations located at Westford, Massachusetts; Greenbank, West Virginia; Hat Creek, California; and Onsala, Sweden, were successfully coupled as a four element interferometer. Table 5-1 lists the parameters for all the baselines in rectilinear coordinates and, also, the site coordinates of each station. The site coordinates and elevations were taken from the American Ephemeris and Nautical Almanac and used with the standard ellipsoid model of the earth in computing the baselines. Table 5-2 lists the baselines in polar coordinates and, also, gives the fringe spacings. Figure 5-1 shows the four antennas used in the experiments and Figure 5-2 shows the baselines drawn on a globe as they would appear to an observer in space. Table 5-3 lists information about the five observing periods. Each session was typically 48 to 96 hours long with the time being shared with the NRAO-AIO group which was engaged in observations

TABLE 5-1
INTERFEROMETER STATION COORDINATES

STATION	LONGITUDE DEGREES	LONGITUDE HOURS	GEODEIC LATITUDE DEGREES	GEOCENTRIC LATITUDE DEGREES	ELEVATION METERS
ONSALA	-11.9167	-0.7944	57.3917	57.216	14
HAYSTACK	71.4887	4.7659	42.6231	42.4305	145
NRAO	79.8367	5.3224	38.4376	38.2496	823
HAT CREEK	121.4733	8.0982	40.8179	40.6269	1050

TABLE 5-2. INTERFEROMETER BASELINE PARAMETERS

BASELINE STATIONS	LENGTH KILOMETERS	D/λ^* $\times 10^{-6}$	λ/D ARC"	θ^{**} DEGREES	LHA [†] HOURS	DECLINATION DEGREES	AZIMUTH ^{††} DEGREES	ELEVATION ^{††} DEGREES
HAYSTACK-NRAO	845.19	4.695	0.0439	7.608	9.5021	-24.668	239.451	- 3.654
HAT CREEK-NRAO	3505.98	19.476	0.0106	31.944	0.8821	- 3.331	80.459	-15.962
HAYSTACK-HAT CREEK	4033.34	22.403	0.0092	36.916	13.3168	- 2.118	284.593	-18.437
HAYSTACK-ONSALA	5599.68	31.108	0.0066	52.184	19.3317	10.836	42.913	-26.143
NRAO-ONSALA	6319.35	35.105	0.0059	59.505	19.5881	12.851	38.911	-29.813
HAT CREEK-ONSALA	7718.74	42.880	0.0048	74.627	22.3763	8.957	24.085	-37.355

* λ = 18,001 cm

** ANGLE BETWEEN VECTORS FROM CENTER OF EARTH TO EACH STATION

† REFERED TO GREENWICH MERIDIAN

†† FROM STATION 1 TO STATION 2 IN COORDINATES OF STATION 1

FIGURE 5-1. ANTENNAS IN THE FOUR ELEMENT INTERFEROMETER.

NRAO 140 foot

Millstone Hill 84 foot

Onsala, Sweden, 85 foot

Hat Creek 85 foot

FIGURE 5-2
BASELINES
JOINING
WESTFORD, MASS;
GREEN BANK,
WEST VIRGINIA
HAT CREEK,
CALIFORNIA, a;
ONSALA, SWEDEN

TABLE 5-3

SUMMARY OF RECORDED DATA BY SOURCE

DATE	STATIONS	3C273	W3	W10	W24	W49	W51	W75	NGC6334	REDUCED
June 8 - 11, 1967	HAYSTACK NRAO	2 WL	17 NR 3 NL 4 NC 3 WR 1 WL 4 WC	0	4 NL	3 NR 4 NL 1 WR 1 WL	0	0	3 NR	All
June 29 - July 1, 1967	HAYSTACK NRAO	0	13 NR 6 NL 2 NC 7 WR 4 WL	0	4 NL 1 WL	2 NR 4 NL 2 WR 2 WL	0	0	2 NR 2 NL	Narrow band only
July 22- 26, 1967	HAT CREEK NRAO JOD BANK	4 NR 2 WR	17 NR 3 NL 8 WR 6 WL 3 WC 8 NR 2 NL	0	3 NR 2 NL 2 WR 2 WL 0	3 NR 6 NL 9 WR 8 WL 2 NR 6 NL	1 NR 1 NL 1 WR 1 WL 2 NL	2 NL 2 NW 2 NL	2 NR 5 WR 5 WL 0	All W3 3 pair W3
Aug 17-19, 1967	NRAO JOD BANK	3 NR	16 NR 5 NL	0	0	0	0	0	0	3 pair + 8 ms.

N = Narrow bandwidth, W = Wide bandwidth
 R = Right handed polarization on both antennas, L = Left handed polarization
 C = Crossed circular polarization

TABLE 5-3 (continued)

DATE	STATIONS		SOURCES								REDUCED
	3C273	W3	W10	W24	W49	W51	W75	NGC6334			
January 27-30, 1968	NRAO	6 WR	9 NR 2 NL 15 WR 11 WL	4 WR 2 WL	2 WR 3 WL	3 WR 3 WL	1 WR 1 WL	3 WL	2 WR 2 WL	19 pairs out of 158 possible pairs.	
	ONSALA	3 WR	14 NR 1 NL 11 WR 5 WL	0	0	0	0	0	0		
	HAYSTACK	3 WR	15 WR 17 WL	4 WR 2 WL	2 WR 3 WL	5 WR 4 WL	2 WR 2 WL	5 WL	2 WR 2 WL		
	HAT CREEK	2 WR	4 WR 3 WL	1 WR 1 WL	0	1 WR 1 WL	0	1 WL	1 WR 1 WL		

N = Narrow bandwidth, W = Wide bandwidth
 R = Right handed polarization on both antennas, L = Left handed polarization
 C = Crossed circular polarization

of continuum source with much of the same equipment. Tape recordings could be taken comfortably at intervals as short as 15 minutes. The average interval was much longer than this so that the fraction of the total scheduled time actually spent recording data was probably about 10%.

The equipment worked reasonably well for all experiments. Some of the problems experienced with the tape drives and atomic standards was traceable to their being transported between observatories. The least successful experiment was the June 28th one because the local oscillator in the receiver at NRAO failed and the HP-5100 synthesizer which supplied the 28 MHz local oscillator reference signal was inadvertently left running on its interval crystal oscillator and thereby increased the system phase noise somewhat.

The program INTERFER was run before each experiment to provide a listing in five minute intervals of the source coordinates, projected baseline, and local oscillator settings for each station and for all the OH sources to be examined. The general objectives of the observing program was set out before each observing period in the case of the June and July experiments, but the actual schedule was agreed upon during the period via telephone conversation. The August and January experiments were carefully planned in advance with every run listed. The equipment was reliable and the observers experienced

so that this procedure worked well with little rescheduling. The January program required almost a month of planning because of the complexity of coordinating four stations with attention paid to such things as source visibility, projected baseline coverage, maser refills and many other factors. This was well worth the effort and the data obtained was excellent. The phone bill was drastically reduced also.

5.2 OBSERVATION OF W3

The most extensive observations were made on the OH source near the HII region W3 (IC1795). The projected baseline loci are shown in figure 5-3 for the Haystack-NRAO baseline and the Hat Creek-NRAO interferometers. Both loci are nearly circular and, therefore, most of the discussion will be in terms of the angular characteristics of the source.

The -45.1 km/s feature was examined at many local angles on the Haystack-NRAO baseline with the 6 kc/s filter. Figure 5-4 shows the visibility spectrum at four different local hour angles. Each spectrum was computed from a 60 point correlation function with hanning weighting so that the resolution is 400 Hz in frequency or 0.072 km/s in velocity. The integration time is 160 seconds giving a signal to noise ratio of 50:1. This feature clearly has two components which are spatially separated and whose axis lies roughly parallel to the interferometers

FIGURE 5-3. The accessible portions of the projected baseline loci in the direction of W3 for the Hat Creek - NRAO and Haystack - NRAO interferometers. The projected baselines for the data shown in figures 5-10, 11, 12 and 13 are marked with the local hour angles at NRAO indicated. x and o denote left and right circular polarization observations (shown on conjugate loci for convenience).

FIGURE 5-4. W3 INTERFERENCE SPECTRA WITH 400 Hz RESOLUTION

fringes at 21.5 hours and perpendicular to it at 3.4 hours. Figure 5-5 shows a plot of the phase difference between the components centered at -45.3 km/s and -45.0 km/s. The fringe amplitude of the -45.0 component is also shown in this figure. The separation deduced from the phase data was

$$\Delta\alpha = 0.016''$$

$$\Delta\delta = 0.018''$$

A model fitting program, MODEL, which varies $\Delta\alpha$ and $\Delta\delta$ and also the line width, amplitude and velocity of each component, was run to determine the parameters of the double source. Both components were found to be about 2.0 km/s wide with the stronger one having 70% of the flux and centered at -45.0 km/s and the weaker one having 30% of the flux and centered at -45.3 km/s. To compare these results to the single antenna spectrum, the power spectrum of a wide band recording was computed with 400 Hz resolution. The -45.1 km/s feature showed a bulge in the low velocity side and a double Gaussian fit to the profile gave about the same parameters for the components as derived from the interferometer data.

The -45.1 km/s feature was also observed with the antennas cross-polarized. In this mode the interferometer responds only to the linearly polarized signal. A pair of spectra taken fifteen minutes apart are shown in figure 5-6. The

Figure 5-5. Fringe amplitude and phase shift on the -45.1 km/s feature in W3 versus local hour angle. Fringe spacing is about 0.05 seconds of arc.

FIGURE 5-6

LEFT-RIGHT spectrum is quite different from the RIGHT-LEFT one. The amplitude profiles are different and in one case the phase is fairly constant with frequency and in the other it varies linearly with frequency.

A simple model which "explains" this difference consists of two point sources separated in space and, also, separated but overlapping in frequency. Each component is linearly polarized but with a different position angle. The details of the model are shown in figure 5-7. A flat phase response in the case of the LEFT-RIGHT spectrum is obtained by assuming that the phase effects due to the positional displacement and difference in polarization position angle cancel. In the RIGHT-LEFT spectrum, then, the phase varies smoothly and monotonically as the ratio of the temperature from each component changes with frequency. This model also fits the stokes parameters measured on a single antenna where it has been observed that the position angle of the linearly polarized radiation decreases with frequency across the -45.1 km/s feature.

Figures 5-8 and 5-9 show spectra of W3, obtained in right and left circular polarization respectively, with the 120 kc/s filter. The fringe visibility was computed as a function of frequency for various fringes frequencies near the expected fringe rate. The plots shown in figures 5-8 and 5-9 are the ones which have the fringes rates which give the highest

$$A_{RL}(\omega) = \sum_i T_{RL_i} e^{j\phi_i} = T_1(\omega) e^{j(\phi_1 + 2p_1)} + T_2(\omega) e^{j(\phi_2 + 2p_2)}$$

$$A_{LR}(\omega) = \sum_i T_{LR_i} e^{j\phi_i} = T_1(\omega) e^{j(\phi_1 - 2p_2)} + T_2(\omega) e^{j(\phi_2 - 2p_2)}$$

$$A_{RL}(\omega) = |A_{RL}(\omega)| e^{j\psi_{RL}(\omega)}, \quad A_{LR}(\omega) = |A_{LR}(\omega)| e^{j\psi_{LR}(\omega)}$$

$$\psi_{RL}(\omega) = \tan^{-1} \left\{ \frac{T_1(\omega) \sin(\phi_1 + 2p_1) + T_2(\omega) \sin(\phi_2 + 2p_2)}{T_1(\omega) \cos(\phi_1 + 2p_1) + T_2(\omega) \cos(\phi_2 + 2p_2)} \right\}$$

$$\psi_{LR}(\omega) = \tan^{-1} \left\{ \frac{T_1(\omega) \sin(\phi_1 - 2p_2) + T_2(\omega) \sin(\phi_2 - 2p_2)}{T_1(\omega) \cos(\phi_1 - 2p_2) + T_2(\omega) \cos(\phi_2 - 2p_2)} \right\}$$

If \$\phi_1 + 2p_1 = \phi_2 + 2p_2\$ then \$\psi_{RL} = \text{constant}\$

FIGURE 5-7. The crossed circular polarization response of an interferometer to a double source where the components are linearly polarized with position angles \$p_1\$ and \$p_2\$. \$\phi_1\$ and \$\phi_2\$ are the positional offsets of the components expressed in terms of fringe phase.

W3
 RIGHT CIRCULAR POLARIZATION
 PROJECTED FRINGE SPACING = 0.044"
 ANTENNA TEMPERATURES CAN BE CONVERTED TO
 FLUX, IN FLUX UNITS, BY MULTIPLYING SCALE
 BY FMR.

FIGURE 5-8. INTERFERENCE SPECTRUM ON W3 IN RIGHT CIRCULAR POLARIZATION.
 DOTTED LINE = INTERFEROMETER RESPONSE, SOLID LINE = SINGLE ANTENNA RESPONSE.

W3
 LEFT CIRCULAR POLARIZATION
 PROJECTED FRINGE SPACING = 0.071"

FIGURE 5-9. INTERFERENCE SPECTRUM ON W3 IN LEFT CIRCULAR POLARIZATION.

visibility for most of the features. These spectra were computed by program GREENSTAK. A trial run of 100 records was made to locate the signal in fringe rate space. Then 400 records were processed in the standard format of a 200 point correlation function and 11 fringe rate channels spaced 0.004 Hz apart. The hanning weighting function was used and a 240 point Fourier transform taken. This gives five points per resolution interval of 2.4 KHz or 0.43 km/s. This redundancy gives the profile dots a somewhat deceptively smooth appearance, but is very useful because the spectrum is clearly delineated. Another program, REPLOT, divides each point in the spectrum by the system gain and multiplies by the system temperature.

The visibility spectra are shown by dotted lines in figures 5-8 and 5-9 whereas the single antenna spectra, measured from the tapes individually and scaled so that they represent the expected profiles for an unresolved source, are shown by solid lines. Hence, at any velocity the fringe amplitude is the ratio of the temperatures given by the dotted and solid lines. The phase dots have a solid line drawn through them in the portions of the spectrum where they are considered meaningful.

In the right circular spectrum of W3 the only clearly unresolved feature is the one at -43.7 km/s. The -45.1 km/s

feature has two components as has been discussed. Comparison of the fringe amplitude here and in figure 5-5 where it was measured with 400 Hz resolution shows the drastic reduction in the fringe amplitude which can occur because of frequency smoothing. This is because the smoothing is a vector averaging process as opposed to scalar averaging of single antenna spectra. Hence the -45.1 km/s feature "appears resolved" because of the poor frequency resolution. The -41.7 km/s feature is spatially separated from its "wing" at -41.0 km/s as is evidenced by the phase shift between the two velocities. Notice that the low level diffuse features at -42.4, -43.1 and -44.4 km/s are present and, therefore, also have small angular sizes.

The left circular spectrum is even more complex with at least six features present: -44.6, -45.5, -46.2, -46.5, -47.4, and -49.1 km/s. The -44.6 km/s feature has unity fringe amplitude as has the low velocity half of the -46-4 km/s feature. Figures 5-10 and 5-11 show five visibility spectra in right and left circular polarization respectively taken at various local hour angles with the Haystack-NRAO interferometer. Figure 5-12 and 5-13 show six spectra in right and left circular polarization taken with the Hat Creek-NRAO interferometer. The total processing time for these 22 spectra was almost 100 hours on the CDC-3300. Notice that the temperature scale

W3 RIGHT CIRCULAR POLARIZATION

HAYSTACK - NRAC BASELINE

VELOCITY KILOMETERS / SECOND

FIGURE 5-10. FRINGE AMPLITUDE ON W3 VELOCITY VELOCITY FOR FIVE LOCAL HOUR ANGLES. θ = RESOLUTION AND P = BASELINE POSITION ANGLE. RIGHT CIRCULAR POLARIZATION.

W3 LEFT CIRCULAR POLARIZATION

HAYSTACK - NRAO BASELINE

VELOCITY KILOMETERS / SECOND

FIGURE 5-11. FRINGE AMPLITUDE ON W3 VERSUS VELOCITY FOR FIVE LOCAL HOUR ANGLES. θ = RESOLUTION AND P = BASELINE POSITION ANGLE. LEFT CIRCULAR POLARIZATION.

W3 RIGHT CIRCULAR POLARIZATION

HAT CREEK - NRAO BASELINE

FIGURE 5-12. FRINGE AMPLITUDE ON W3 VERSUS VELOCITY FOR SIX LOCAL HOUR ANGLES. RIGHT CIRCULAR POLARIZATION.

W3 LEFT CIRCULAR POLARIZATION

HAT CREEK - NRAO BASELINE

VELOCITY KILOMETERS / SECOND

FIGURE 5-13. FRINGE AMPLITUDE OF W3 VERSUS VELOCITY FOR SIX LOCAL HOUR ANGLES. LEFT CIRCULAR POLARIZATION.

on the Hat Creek-NRAO spectra has been expanded by a factor of two. For convenience, the fringe amplitudes for the strongest features are listed in table 5-4.

The precise interpretation of the shapes of the features is hindered by the lack of complete baseline coverage. Some characteristics can be recognized. Figure 5-3 has the projected baseline for each of the spectra in figures 5-10,11,12,13 marked. The right circular measurements are shown on one loci and the left circular ones on the conjugate loci.

In the right circular spectrum only the -43.7 km/s feature remains unresolved with constant fringe amplitude of $0.9 \pm .1$. The -45.1 km/s feature is rather weak. Figure 5-14 shows some high resolution spectra of this feature where at least three components are recognizable. These three overlapping velocity components probably have sizes of about $0.01''$ of arc and may have complex structure within themselves. The -43.1 km/s feature is probably double. On the Haystack-NRAO baseline its fringe amplitude is usually very low implying that most of these points in the s_x, s_y plane are near the first null in the visibility function. On the Hat Creek-NRAO baseline the baseline loci sweeps through many maxima and minima of the visibility function. The best fit to a double source gives a separation of about $0.02''$ of arc. The fit is not very good

TABLE 5-4. SUMMARY OF THE FRINGE AMPLITUDES OF THE FEATURES OF W3

LHA*	θ	P	FRINGE AMPLITUDE FOR EACH VELOCITY FEATURE				LHA	θ	P	FRINGE AMPLITUDE FOR EACH VELOCITY FEATURE		
			-44.6	-45.5	-46.4	-49.1				-41.7	-43.7	-45.1
HOURS	"	DEG	HOURS	"	DEG	HOURS	"	DEG	HOURS	"	DEG	
17.6	0.068	147	1.0	0.2	0.7	0.9	0.064	132	0.4	1.0	1.0	
19.7	0.057	112	0.2	0.6	0.7	0.9	0.052	103	0.2	1.0	0.8	
23.1	0.045	65	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.9	0.045	59	0.2	1.0	0.6	
4.2	0.044	0	0.3	0.5	0.7	0.9	0.044	21	0.4	1.0	0.5	
6.6	0.044	-32	0.6	0.5	0.8	0.7	0.044	-28	0.4	1.0	0.6	
22.4	0.011	135	0.4	0.1	0.6	0.2	0.011	143	0.04	0.9	0.3	
22.5	0.011	133	0.3	0.1	0.5	<0.1	0.011	128	0.2	0.9	0.2	
1.0	0.011	99	0.2	<0.1	0.4	<0.1	0.011	106	0.5	0.9	0.3	
2.8	0.011	75	<0.1	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.011	78	0.1	0.9	0.1	
4.0	0.011	53	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.011	60	0.2	0.9	0.03	
6.4	0.012	20	0.8	0.4	0.4	0.6	0.012	32	0.4	0.9	0.1	

* Local Hour Angle measured at NRAO.

P = Projected baseline position angle

θ = Resolution

Note: These fringe amplitudes are taken from the spectra shown in figures 5-10,11, 12, and 13 where the spectral resolution is 2.4 KHz or 0.43 KM/S.

W3 RIGHT CIRCULAR POLARIZATION

HAT CREEK-NRAO BASELINE

VELOCITY KILOMETERS/SECOND

FIGURE 5-14. W3 INTERFERENCE SPECTRA WITH 400 Hz (0.073 km/s) RESOLUTION FOR SEVERAL LOCAL HOUR ANGLES.

indicating that the feature is actually more complex. The wing to this feature at -41.0 km/s is clearly a separate source.

In the left circular spectra measured on the Hat Creek-NRAO baseline, the least resolved feature is the one at -46.5 km/s. Its fringe amplitude dips slightly as a function of local hour angle although the line width is constant. This probably means that the feature is elongated. A curious fact is that on this baseline most of the other features are missing on all the spectra between 22 hours and 3 hours. On either side of this range they all appear together. This indicates a similarity in the structure of the sources. Indeed this could be construed to mean they are all elongated in the same direction which is approximately perpendicular to the galactic plane.

In the January experiment the Haystack-Onsala baseline results showed that the feature of smallest angular size in W3, the one at -43.7 km/s, was resolved. Figure 5-15 shows the fringe amplitude vs. local hour angle. Its general lack of local hour angle dependence indicates that it is roughly circular in shape. In this experiment several runs were made with all four stations simultaneously recording. The results of measuring the cross correlation among all six pairs from one such event is shown in figure 5-16. The visibility of the -43.7 km/s feature systematically decreases with increasing

FIGURE 5-15. FRINGE AMPLITUDE ON -43.7 AND -45.1 KM/S FEATURES IN W3 WITH $D/\lambda \sim 30 \times 10^6$.

W3

- 43.7 KM/S FEATURE
23^H UT JAN. 29, 1968

WESTFORD, MASSACHUSETTS
GREENBANK, WEST VIRGINIA
HAT CREEK, CALIFORNIA
ONSAALA, SWEDEN

PROJECTED BASELINE LENGTH IN MILLIONS OF WAVELENGTHS

FIGURE 5-16. THE FRINGE AMPLITUDES OF THE -43.7 km/s FEATURE IN W3 MEASURED SIMULTANEOUSLY ON SIX BASELINES.

projected baseline. The data is fit fairly well with either a uniform disc model of diameter $0.0045''$ of arc or by a Gaussian disc model of diameter $0.0025''$ of arc. The data seems to define a sharper shoulder in the visibility function than is provided by either a uniform disc or Gaussian disc model. This may be caused by the fact that the source is actually elliptical in shape since the various points in figure 5-16 are measured at widely different baseline position angles. The linear dimension corresponding to $.004''$ is about 10 astronomical units, if the distance is 2600 pc.

Fringe Rate Map:

The data from the Hat Creek-NRAO interferometer were used to determine the spatial separations among the features. The features were known to be separated by $1''$ of arc from the results of the Agassiz-Millstone interferometer. The long baseline data was not complete enough to resolve the 2π ambiguities which arise in relative phase measurements. Instead, the relative positions were determined by measuring the differences in fringe rate among the features. The fringe rate offset, which is the difference between the measured fringe rate and the fringe rate expected, based on the geometry of the interferometer and source, is given in equation 2-89 and is dependent on the source position error, baseline position

error and instrumental effects such as frequency offset in the frequency standards or changes in the atmospheric delay. However, by measuring only the difference in fringe rate among features on the spectrum we have a quantity which depends only on their right ascension and declination separation. The difference in fringe rate between two features separated by $\Delta\alpha$, and $\Delta\delta$, is

$$\Delta f = \frac{D}{\lambda} \omega_R \cos \delta_B \left[\sin \delta_S \sin(L_S - L_B) \Delta\delta_S + \cos(L_S - L_B) \cos \delta_S \Delta\alpha_S \right] \quad (5-1)$$

where D/λ is the baseline length in wavelengths, ω_R is the sidereal rotation rate of the earth and $\delta_S, \delta_B, L_S,$ and L_B are the polar coordinates of the source and baseline. This equation evaluated for the Haystack-NRAO and Hat Creek-NRAO interferometers is

$$\Delta f_{\text{Haystack}}^{\text{NRAO}} = 0.00078 \cos(L_S - L_B) \Delta\alpha_S + 0.00145 \sin(L_S - L_B) \Delta\delta_S \text{ Hz} \quad (5-2)$$

$$\Delta f_{\text{Hat Creek}}^{\text{NRAO}} = 0.00325 \cos(L_S - L_B) \Delta\alpha_S + 0.00604 \sin(L_S - L_B) \Delta\delta_S \text{ Hz} \quad (5-3)$$

This difference in fringe rate among features is a very obvious effect in the data, so much so that it is sometimes necessary to display the fringe amplitude as a function of both velocity and fringe rate rather than as a cut at just one fringe rate.

The program REPLOT sets up a fringes amplitude matrix and calls the display routines available on the CDC 3300 computer at Haystack to make contour plots of the fringe amplitude on a cathode ray oscilloscope. These can be photographed on polaroid film. Examples of this display are shown in figure 5-17 for both a right circular and left circular spectrum. The velocity axis is vertical and the fringe rate axis is horizontal.

The computation of $\Delta\alpha_S$ and $\Delta\delta_S$ is done by a program called FRMAP. The fringe visibility of a point source feature as a function of fringe rate is

$$A_V(f_R) = A_0 \frac{\sin \pi(f_R - f_0) T}{\pi(f_R - f_0) T} \quad (5-4)$$

where T is the integration time and f_0 is the feature's fringe rate. f_R is empirically adjusted to minimize the

W3 NRAO - HAT CREEK BASELINE
FRINGE AMPLITUDE VS VELOCITY
AND FRINGE RATE

RIGHT CIRCULAR POLARIZATION LHA = 23.9 HOURS

LEFT CIRCULAR POLARIZATION LHA = 4.3 HOURS

FIGURE 5-17.

error between the data and the equation (5-3) whereas A_0 can be found by the usual minimization procedure. This technique works well because all the components of a given feature in most cases lie close to one another compared with the separation between distinct features. The fringe rates of all the right circular features is measured relative to the -43.7 km/s feature and all left circular features relative to the -46.4 km/s feature. These measured relative fringe rates are then used to find $\Delta\alpha_S$ and $\Delta\delta_S$ in equation (5-3) by a least mean square fit procedure.

There is an obvious graphical way to determine the relative positions from two or more measured fringe rate differences. Notice that each measurement defines a straight line locus in $\Delta\alpha_S, \Delta\delta_S$ space for the relative position. The intersection of the lines, which have different slopes for different local hour angles, defines the relative position. Figure 5-18 shows an example of this method.

Since only circular polarization measurements were made it was necessary to use the Agassiz-Millstone results for the separation between the -43.7(R) and -46.4(L) features. The accuracy of this measurement was about the same as with the long baseline data. The additional uncertainty introduced by this measurement has been added to the error in the left circular features. It was necessary to include some of the

FIGURE 5-18. The determination of the positional separation between the -45.1 and -43.7 km/s features in W3. TOP: Graphical determination of position from equation (5-3). BOTTOM: Fringe rate difference vs local hour angle and the least mean square fitted curve.

data from the Haystack-NRAO baseline to determine the position of the -49.1 km/s feature since it was so weak on the longer baseline. Consequently, the position of this feature has large uncertainty.

The results of all the W3 work are summed up in Table 5-5 and displayed in a map in figure 5-19. The linear scale of 1000 AU is based on a distance to W3 of 1700 pc which may be too low. The -49.1, -44.6, and -45.5 km/s are shown as irregular blobs but actually seem to be aligned in the same direction as the -46.6 km/s feature. The apparent brightness temperature of the features is on the order of 10^{12} °K. Only the apparent sizes and positions have been measured here. In other words, a single plane wave impinging on an interferometer is identified as originating from a point source at infinity although, in fact, the plane wave could have been launched by very extended radiator which maintains constant phase across its dimensions.

The relative position between -43.7 km/s and -45.1 km/s features obtained with the fringe rate data in July, 1967, agrees well with the position measured in December, 1966, with the Agassiz-Millstone interferometer. The fact not only sheds light on the competence of the observer but, also, points out that these features are not moving relative to one another than about 40 km/s in the direction perpendicular to the line of sight, which is not surprising.

TABLE 5-5. Sizes and Relative Positions of the Features in the 1665 MHz OH spectrum of W3.

FEATURE	POL	$\Delta \alpha \cos \delta$ Seconds of arc	$\Delta \delta$	FRINGE AMPLITUDE **	T_A °K	T_B °K x 10 ¹²	STRUCTURE and DIAMETER
-41.7 KM/S	R	.24±.4	-.11±.4	0.1 - 0.5	48	0.5	Probable double Separation = 0.02" Orientation uncertain.
-43.7	R	0	0	0.9±.1	82	4.8	0.004"
-44.7	L	-.33±.5	-2.03±.5	0.0 - 0.8	36	0.1	Complex, 0.02"
-45.1	R	-.89±.3	-0.01±.3	0.0 - 0.3	155	1.8	Double, separation = 0.02", weaker additional components.
-45.5	L	-.40±.5	-1.93±.5	0.0-0.4	90	.3	Complex, 0.02"
-46.4*	L	-.93±.3	-0.30±.3	0.2 - 0.6	80	1.5	One component is elongated 0.006 x 0.010" of arc.
-49.1	L	-.14±.7	0.28±.7	0.0 - 0.6	26	0.1	complex, 0.02"

* Position determined from relative phase measurements on Agassiz-Millstone interferometer.
 ** Measured on NRAO-Hat Creek baseline.

MAP OF OH EMISSION SOURCE IN W3

FIGURE 5-19. Map of the relative positions and the shapes of the principal features in the 1665 MHz spectrum of OH in W3. The velocity and sense of circular polarization are indicated for each feature. The linear scale is based on a distance of 1700 pc. Best absolute position of map is given in Table 1-1.

5.3 OBSERVATIONS OF W49, W24 AND NGC6334

Data from the sources W49, W24 and NGC6334 have been reduced. Data on some weaker sources such as W51, W75 and W10 and, also W3 (1667 mc/s) has been taken but not analyzed. The project baseline loci for W75, W49 and W24 are shown in figure 5-20.

A right and left circularly polarized spectra of W49 appear in figures 5-21 and 5-22. There are at least eight distinct features in the left spectrum and six in the right. Curiously, they all have about the same fringe amplitude, ~ 0.5 . Spectra taken near the point of maximum project baseline show the strongest features to have a fringe amplitude of 0.2. This information is suggestive that the features are circular with equivalent uniform disc sized of about $0.05''$ of arc or Gaussian half power widths of $0.03''$ of arc. To date, none of the features identified as originating from "position 2" in the Haystack-Millstone data has been observed. As expected, none of the tapes on W49 on the Hat Creek-NRAO baseline showed any detectable correlation.

Observations of NGC6334(I), shown in figure 5-23 and 5-24, show that the strongest feature in the left spectrum is unresolved; i.e., less than $0.015''$ of arc, while the strongest feature in the right spectrum has two components both of which appear to be slightly resolved.

The visibility spectra of the $O\text{H}$ emission source near the galactic center proved difficult to obtain. It was not detected,

FIGURE 5-20 The accessible portions of the Haystack - NRAO Baseline on W24, W49 and NGC6334. The dots indicate the projected baselines for the spectra shown in figures 5-21, 22 and 25. The projected baseline for NGC6334 is similar to the one for W24.

FIGURE 5-21. W49 INTERFERENCE SPECTRUM IN RIGHT CIRCULAR POLARIZATION.
DOTTED LINE = INTERFEROMETER RESPONSE AND SOLID LINE = SINGLE ANTENNA RESPONSE.

FIGURE 5-22. W49 INTERFERENCE SPECTRUM IN LEFT CIRCULAR SPECTRUM.

NGC 6334 (I)
 RIGHT CIRCULAR POLARIZATION
 PROJECTED FRINGE SPACING = 0052"

FIGURE 5-23. NGC6334 (NORTHERN SOURCE) INTERFERENCE SPECTRUM IN RIGHT CIRCULAR POLARIZATION. DOTTED LINE = INTERFEROMETER RESPONSE, SOLID = ZERO BASELINE RESPONSE.

FIGURE 5-24. NGC6334 INTERFERENCE SPECTRUM IN LEFT CIRCULAR POLARIZATION.

to a level of 10% full correlation, in the data taken in June or July, 1967. In January, 1967, a spectrum of W24 in left circular polarization was obtained by observing the source at the time of maximum foreshortening of the baseline, which was considerable since the baseline and source declination were nearly equal. Figure 5-25 shows the spectrum taken at a fringe spacing of 0.12" of arc. The uniform disc size corresponding to the fringe amplitude of 0.4 measured here is 0.09" of arc. This is 900 AU at the distance of W24 compared to 10 AU for the size of the smallest feature in W3.

5.4 THE JODRELL BANK EXPERIMENTS:

The series of experiments with Jodrell Bank have not been successful. The first experiment, suggested by R. D. Davies at Jodrell Bank was a post detection correlation experiment. The detected analog signal was recorded during the June 28th observing period on a Ferrograph tape recorder at NRAO and Jodrell Bank. A video converter, supplied by Jodrell Bank was used to mix the 30 mc/s signal down to 5 kc/s audio signal where it was detected and filtered. Another channel of the tape recorder had a start signal and reference signal for the purpose of synchronizing and removing flutter in the playback of the signal into the correlator. This data was analyzed at Jodrell Bank and no positive results have been reported.

In July and August, the data was recorded without detection on analog tape recorder at Jodrell Bank and sent

FIGURE 5-25. W24 INTERFERENCE SPECTRUM IN LEFT CIRCULAR POLARIZATION. DOTTED LINE = INTERFEROMETER RESPONSE, SOLID LINE = ZERO BASELINE RESPONSE.

to Haystack where it was played back and digitized on the Haystack VLB recording system. The data at NRAO was recorded on the normal digital tape recorder. The sampling signal was derived from the 2 kc/s sine wave recorded on one of the tape recorder tracks. The start of the recording was denoted by a sharp pulse on the tape. To partially test the system, recording at Jodrell Bank were made simultaneously on two tape recorders. These were digitized independently and found to be virtually perfectly correlated. This provided a fairly good indication that the difficulty did not come from either of the tape recorders or the digitalization procedure. The major unknown factor was the phase stability of the local oscillator at Jodrell Bank and the relative instrumental delay between the signal recordings.

An example of processing one pair of tapes is shown in figure 5-26. The coherent integration time is only one second, while the total integration time was 80 seconds. The total delay searched here was ± 5 milliseconds and total fringe rate ± 2 cps. The top scan shows the result of processing a pair of Haystack-NRAO tapes in this fashion. The gain of the Mark II antenna was larger than Haystack so that the correlation should have been about the same.

W3, -43.7 KM/S FEATURE

JODRELL BANK - NRAO BASELINE

PROGRAM TEST WITH DATA FROM
HAYSTACK - NRAO INTERFEROMETER

SQUARED CORRELATION VS DELAY

FRINGE RATE OFFSET = 2 Hz

1 Hz

0 Hz

-1 Hz

-2 Hz

SQUARE OF CROSSCORRELATION FUNCTION

DELAY IN MILLISECONDS

FIGURE 5-26. SAMPLE OF THE PROCESSED DATA IN THE SEARCH FOR CORRELATION IN THE TAPES FROM THE JODRELL BANK - NRAO INTERFEROMETER. CURRENT INTEGRATION TIME = 1 SECOND, TOTAL = 80 s

The experiment was conceived as an appendage to the main program and time was never available to bench-check the system in the way the Haystack-NRAO system was checked. There was also no interchange of personnel which might have been useful in detecting blunders or incompatibilities. In conclusion, it seems that the most likely cause of failure was caused by an error in the relative delay.

CHAPTER VI

SUMMARY OF RESULTS

6.1 CONCLUSIONS

At the outset of this thesis research, the sizes of the OH emission sources were not known. It was only known that the features were less than 20" of arc in size and coincident to within 3" of arc. From the high resolution data obtained here with the long baseline interferometers, a map of the emission sources in the 1665 MHz transition of W3 was constructed. The map shows the positions of the seven strongest features whose fluxes are greater than 0.1 of the flux of the strongest feature. The smallest feature was found to have a size of 0.004" of arc. The ratio of the solid angle subtended by this feature to the total solid angle, $\Omega_S/4\pi$, is 2.4×10^{-17} . The various components of a given feature in the frequency spectrum were usually found to originate from different points in space but clustered in an area of about 0.0004 sq. arc seconds. On the other hand, the separation between features is about 1 second of arc so that the area containing the OH emission is very sparsely populated with actual emission points.

The linearly polarized component of the -45.1 km/s feature appears to have two components separated slightly in velocity and space. Each component has a different position

angle of linear polarization. The position of these linearly polarized components is near the right circular components at -45.1 km/s. It is possible that the -45.1 feature has two elliptically polarized features, with different position angles, or that there are two separate linear and circular components. It is not possible to determine with the existing data whether the linear components are exactly coincident with the circular ones. The left circular feature at -45.5 km/s is removed from this complex by about $2''$ of arc, however.

It seems quite probable that the OH sources are condensations in a much larger cloud in which the maser action is taking place. The geometry of the sources places constraints on the various pump models but does not appear to eliminate any as being inconsistent with the data.

It is very tempting to visualize patterns in the distribution of the feature positions. Since there are only seven points they should all fit any model proposed to explain their distribution without exception if the model is to have statistical significance. An example of a "one exception" model is the one in which the sources are on a large rotating cloud. The -49.1 km/s feature does not fit this model.

In the 1665 MHz transition the right handed features tend to be grouped on the high velocity side of the spectrum

so that the "center of mass" of the right handed features is separated by about 3 KHz from the center of mass of the left handed features. The map shows that centers of mass of the two groups of oppositely polarized features are separated by about 1" of arc. A curious fact, which is probably coincidental, is that all the right handed features are separated in right ascension by about 0.5" of arc per kilometer and the left handed features are separated in declination by 0.5" of arc per kilometer.

It has been suggested that the wavefront of the radiation is distorted in some random fashion as it emerges from the OH cloud so that the sources seen by an observer are just the parts of the wavefront which are normal to the line of sight. If this were the case, these "images" might be expected to jump around erratically. Comparison of the data on the separation of the -43.7 km/s feature and the -45.1 km/s feature taken in December, 1966, July, 1967, and January, 1968, suggest that these features have not moved with respect to one another by more than ± 0.3 " of arc. It has also been shown here that the -45.1 km/s feature does not scintillate in amplitude on a time scale of seconds. The largest baseline interferometer does not show any short time; i.e., 10 seconds, phase scintillations corresponding to apparent motion of the source by .002" of arc.

The sources in W24, W49, and NGC6334 were also examined at 1665 MHz but not at enough projected baselines to construct a map of the relative feature positions. W49, for example, has many more identifiable features than W3 and they are obviously spatially separated from one another. Curiously, the separations of the W49 features appears to about 1" of arc, the same as in W3, although it is five times farther away. Another interesting fact is that the 15 strongest features in the W49 spectra shown in figures 5-21 and 5-22 all have fringe amplitudes of about 0.5. In W3, the features have a size variation of about a factor of 5, while in W49 the factor is less than 2. The sizes of the features in W24 were larger than expected, considering the great distance of the source. Thus, there is a hundred to one range in the linear dimensions of the OH features among the sources studied with the larger features being farther away. Figure 6-1 shows the locations of the sources in the galaxy and table 6-1 lists the positions, linear and angular dimensions, solid angle, flux, intensity and power of the smallest feature in each of the regions studied. It is possible that the linear size increases with the total emitted power so that the sources farthest away, W24 and W49, should have the largest size since they are the most powerful. It seems more plausible that if the fact the most distant sources are the largest is not just a chance occurrence, then we are seeing the effect of interstellar

FIGURE 6-1. GALACTIC MAP SHOWING THE POSITIONS OF THE FOUR OH SOURCES STUDIED.

FIGURE 6-2. ANGULAR SIZES OF THE SMALLEST FEATURES IN EACH OF THE OH SOURCES VERSUS THEIR DISTANCE FROM THE SUN.

TABLE 6-1. SIZES AND INTENSITIES OF THE OH SOURCES OBSERVED HERE

SOURCE	D Parsecs	l ^{II} Degrees	b ^{II} Degrees	θ _m Seconds of arc	d A.U.	Steradians $\times 10^{-15}$	S $w\text{-m}^{-2}\text{-Hz}^{-1}$ $\times 10^{-26}$	I $w\text{-m}^{-2}\text{-Hz}^{-1}$ -steradian $\times 10^{-12}$	P Watts/KHz $\times 10^{19}$
W3	2600	134.0	1.1	0.004	10	0.3	120	4000	9
NGC6334	700	351.4	0.6	<0.015	<10	<4.2	130	>310	0.7
W24	10000	0.7	0.0	0.09	900	150	140	94	160
W49	13800	43.2	0.0	0.05	700	46	170	37	360

D = Distance to the source.

l ^{II}, b ^{II} = Galactic longitude and latitude.

θ _m = Diameter of smallest feature in the source. (Uniformly bright disc model)

S = Solid angle subtended by smallest feature

I = Peak flux of smallest feature

P = Intensity

P = Power per KHz if the source radiates isotropically.

scattering. In W3, for example, most of the features have irregular cross sections on the order of 0.02" in diameter. This is probably the true size of the feature. The smallest feature in W3 is nearly circular in shape and has a diameter of 0.004" of arc. Possibly this means that this feature is much smaller and the blurring effect for the medium between the sun and W3 is such that it smears the image to 0.004". In the more distant sources, the shapes would be completely masked by scattering. It might be expected that the angular spectrum of the source would increase with the square root of the number of scattering blobs as is the case in some situations in ionospheric and interplanetary scattering. Figure 6-2 shows the sizes of the smallest features in the OH sources versus distance from the sun. Clearly a detailed model has to be developed which will show a decrease in ionization, for example, with galactic radius, so that the fact that W49 is farther away than W24, yet smaller, can be explained. Some of the theory of scattering by thin screens discussed by Ratcliffe (1956) and Salpeter (1966) can be used in this problem. The size of the irregularities and the fluctuations in the refractive index, and the plasma frequency, are important parameters in calculations of this nature.

The scattering hypothesis is probably unwarranted on the basis of observations of four OH sources, but it could

be substantiated by observations of other types of radio sources, such as quasi stellar objects, at various galactic latitudes.

6.2 FURTHER WORK

Much work can be done with the existing long baseline interferometer system. The sizes of the weaker emission sources, such as W10, W51, and W75 should be measured. This will help substantiate or disprove the interstellar scattering hypothesis. The positions of the sources of 1667 MHz emission should be measured to see what relation they bear, if any, to the 1665 MHz sources. It might be found, for example, that the 1667 MHz sources in W3 lie inside the circle defined by the 1665 MHz sources. An important task is to see if there is any geometric connection between the linear and circular components of the "elliptically polarized" features. This has not been done so far because phase stability could not be maintained between data recordings of different polarizations. The system can be modified so that both antennas change polarization rapidly during a run in such a way that all four polarization combinations are obtained. By taking enough data in this way complete polarization maps can be made with positional accuracies of better than $0.005''$ of arc if the relative fringe phase information is utilized. Proper motions of $.001''$ of arc/year might be expected in W3, based on a velocity of 10 km/s.

APPENDIX

Some of the programs used in the very long baseline interferometer experiments are listed here. They were written in FORTRAN for use in the CDC-3300 computer.

Program GREENSTAC takes two recorded tapes, reads them, cross correlates the data bit strings, compensates for the motion of the baseline, Fourier transforms the correlation function, and plots the fringe visibility spectrum. The subroutines that it calls which are not listed here are:

ACARDIN - reads data from card reader.
FORNUMS - reads data from typewriter in free field format.
FREQCONV - computes the local oscillator frequency from the dial settings for a variety of settings.
READHAY - reads the data tape made on Haystack's U490 computer.
READGH - reads the data tape made on the NRAO recording system. It call a COMPASS machine language subroutine, EXTRACT, which discards the redundant bit of data.
CORREL - a COMPASS subroutine which cross correlates the data bit strings.
CPXFOUR - computes Fourier transform.
PLOTSCH, PLOT2V - plots results on printer.

Program INTERFER is also listed. It is used for planning the experiments and it computes all the necessary parameters for spectral line observations with any two stations in five minute intervals. Listed with it are two subroutine which it calls: BASELINE, which computes the baseline coordinates, and FRINGE, which computes the fringe rate, fringe phase, excess delay, s_x and s_y . The other subroutines which are called but

not listed are:

MOVE - computes the source coordinates in the current epoch.
DOPCAL - computes the velocity of the source with respect to the local standard of rest and also the sidereal time.
ALTPOL - transforms from one polar coordinate system to another.
PLOTUV - plots projected baseline locus for source.

ACARDIN, FORNUMS, DOPCAL, MOVE, and ALTPOL were furnished by J.A. Ball. The routines CORREL and EXTRACT were written with the assistance of N. Brenner and J. A. Ball.

PROGRAM GRENSTAC

THIS PROGRAM TAKES DATA TAPES RECORDED ON TWO TELESCOPES AND
AND CROSS CORRELATES THE DATA BIT STRINGS, COMPENSATING FOR THE
DIFFERENTIAL DELAY AND DOPPLER SHIFT CAUSED BY THE EARTH'S ROTATION.
A FOURIER TRANSFORM IS TAKEN ON THE CORRELATION FUNCTIONS GIVING THE
FRINGE VISIBILITY WHICH IS DISPLAYED AS A FUNCTION OF FREQUENCY AND
AND FRINGE RATE.

NOTES ON RUNNING TIME. ONE BIT CORRELATION TAKES 1.6 MICROSECOND
ONE RECORD HAS 46800 BITS. A 200 POINT CORRELATION TAKES ABOUT 20 SEC/RC
OF WHICH 15 SEC IS TAKEN UP WITH RAW CORRELATION AND THE REST WITH FRINGE
ROTATION AND BOOK KEEPING. THIS IS FOR 120 KC/S BANDWIDTH.
FUNCTION IS COMPUTED ONLY EVERY 0.020 SECONDS
FRINGE RATE SHOULD BE COMPENSATED FOR TO WITHIN 20 CPS SINCE CORRELATION
PROGRAM WRITTEN MAY 1967 REVISED DECEMBER 1967

*****JAMES M. MORAN JR *****

```

DIMENSION COSPH(9,11),SINPH(9,11),ANS(10),PA(80),
1 IHAY(2100),INR40(2100),ICORR(200),
2 RSIN(200,11),RCOS(200,11),TREAL(240),TIMAG(240),FAMP(240),
4 ENS(10),CNS(10),DNS(10),ENS(10),GNS(10),DOPFO(15),IBAND(2),
5 FASE(240),WT(200),AMOD(30),FNS(10), TAMP( 1.5 ),RAMP( 1.5)
6 ,BX(20),BH(20),BD(20)

```

JUMP 1 IGNORE PARITY ERRORS,

JUMP 2 ABORT

JUMP 3 SELECT FRINGE AMPLITUDE PLOTTING SCALE

JUMP 4 IGNORE START TIMES AND CONTINUOUS PROCESSING

JUMP 5 ACCUMULATIVE PROCESSING

JUMP 6 DEBUGGING PRINTOUT AND PARAMETER INPUT FROM CARD READER

COMMON RCOS,RSIN,IPTR,TIME,IREF,ISHIFT,I

EXTERNAL FORANUM

CHARACTER PA

CORE CHANGE FOR PLOTTING OVER CRACK

DIMENSION IAA(1)\$IAD=77777B+1655B-LOC(IAA(1))\$IAA(IAD)=14600010B

PIE=3.141592653

R=PIE/180.

TMAX=.5

IBAND(1)=1

IBAND(2)=20

C BASELINE FROM HAYSTACK (ST 1) TO ST 2 IN HAYSTACK COORDINATES

C READ IN COORD IN STAT 1 FRAME TO STAT 2

C THESE COORDINATES WILL BE REVERSED LATER

C BASELINES...1 HAYSTACK-NRAO,2 HAT CREEK-NRAO,3 HAYSTACK-HAT CREEK

C 4 HAYSTACK-ONSALA, 5 NRAO-ONSALA, 6 HAT CREEK-ONSALA

BX(1)=845.167 \$ BH(1)=4.7364 \$ BD=-24.6678

BX(2)=3505.9524 \$ BH(2)=-7.2160 \$ BD(2)=-3.3310

BX(3)=4033.3438 \$ BH(3)=-16.4491 \$ BD(3)=-2.1179

BX(4)=5599.6812 \$ BH(4)=-9.4342 \$ BD(4)=10.8356

BX(5)=6319.3529 \$ BH(5)=-9.7343 \$ BD(5)=12.8505

BX(6)=7718.7397 \$ BH(6)=-10.7219 \$ BD(6)=8.9570

1 REWIND 40

IHPT=0

ASUM=0.

ASUMSQ=0.

ASUMP=0.

ASUMI=0.

MSUM=0

IDUMP=1

IREF=0

IWRITE=0

DSHIFT=0.

DO 610 I=1,200

DO 610 K=1,11
RCOS(I,K)=0.

610 RSIN(I,K)=0,
CONSTANTS TO BE ENTERED BY TYPEWRITER
HTAPE, HAYSTACK TAPE NUMBER
NTAPE, NRAO TAPE NUMBER
IFILEH,IFILEN FILE ON INPUT TAPES 1 AND 2 RESPECTIVELY
IMODE,1,NORMAL,2,MATCHED FILTER,3,NO FRINGE ROTATION
4,READ IN OUTPUT TAPE
INTEG,INTEGRATION PERIOD IN RECORDS
IPTR, NUMBER OF POINTS IN CORRELATION FUNCTION MAX 200
IPTS, NUMBER OF POINTS IN VISIBILITY SPECTRUM MAX 240
IWT, WEIGHTING FUNCTION , 1 FOR UNIFORM, 2 FOR COSINE
IDELAY, INSTRUMENTAL DELAY HAYSTACK REL TO NRAO
IBW,1=5 KC, 2=100 KC
DOPD, FRINGE FREQUENCY SEARCH INTERVAL IN CPS SHOULD BE SET PROPORTIONAL
TO RECIPROCAL OF INTEGRATION TIME DOPD LESS THAN 4 X INTEG
DOP,EXPECTED FRINGE FREQUENCY OFFSET IN CPS
NDOP, NUMBER OF FRINGE FREQUENCIES SEARCHED MAX 11
TIMEST,START TIME OF INTEGRATION PERIOD IN SECONDS (MIN PLUS .3 SEC)
TAPTIME,TIME OF BEGINNING OF GB TAPE IN SECONDS
FREQHAY, HAYSTACK SYN FREQ IN MEGACYCLES
FREQGB,NRAO LO SYN FREQ IN MEGACYCLES
SLHAI, SOURCE LHA (HOURS) AT 0 HOURS UT AT STATION 1 ON SAME DAY
IL1,IL2, LOCAL OSCILLATOR FORMULAS FOR ST 1 AND ST 2 1-8 EVEN FOR A1
BASECOD, CODE FOR BASELINE DESIRED, 99 FOR ENTRY FROM CARD READER
WRITE (59,619)
619 FORMAT(1X, 40HJUMP 6 ON FOR CARD READER INPUT PRESS GO)
PAUSE
GO TO (707,708) SSWTCHF(6)
C INPUT FROM CARD READER
707 CALL A CARD IN(ANS,NA) ACARDI
CALL A CARD IN(BNS,NB) ACARDI
CALL A CARD IN(CNS,NC) ACARDI
CALL A CARD IN(DNS,ND) ACARDI
CALL A CARD IN(ENS,NE) ACARDI
IF(NA+NB+NC+ND+NE-29) 1,709,1
C INPUT FROM TYPEWRITER
708 WRITE(59,700)
700 FORMAT(1X, 25HENTER HTAPE NTAPE,IFILEGB) FORNUM
CALL FOR NUMS(ANS,0,3)
WRITE(59,701)
701 FORMAT(1X,41HENTER IMODE,IBW,INTEG,IPTR,IPTS,IWT,INCOH) FORNUM
CALL FOR NUMS(BNS,0,7)
WRITE (59,702)
702 FORMAT(1X, 38HENTER DOP,DOPD,NDOP,IDELAY,NCENT,NWIDE) FORNUM
CALL FOR NUMS(CNS,0,6)
WRITE(59,703)
703 FORMAT(1X, 20HENTER TIMEST,TAPTIME) FORNUM
CALL FOR NUMS(DNS,0,6)
WRITE(59,704)
704 FORMAT(1X,49 HENTER FREQHAY,FREQGB,SLHAI,DEC,ILO1,ILO2,IBASECOD) FORNUM
CALL FOR NUMS(ENS,0,7)
709 IHTAPE=ANS(1)
NTAPE=ANS(2)
IFILEGB=ANS(3)
IMODE=BNS(1)
IBW=BNS(2)
ISWITCH=3-IBW
IN=3+IBAND(ISWITCH)+.5

```

IPTR=BNS(4)
IPTS=BNS(5)
IWT=BNS(6)
INCOH=BNS(7)
GO TO (15,14) IWT
HANNING WEIGHTING FUNCTION
14 DO 16 I=1,IPTR
A=3.141592653*(2.*(I-1)/IPTR-1.)
16 WT(I)=.5+.5*COSF(A)
GO TO 18
C UNIFORM WEIGHTING
15 DO 17 I=1,IPTR
17 WT(I)=1.
18 DOP=CNS(1)
DOPD=CNS(2)
NDOP=CNS(3)
IDELAY=CNS(4)
NCENT=CNS(5)
NWIDE=CNS(6)
TAPTIME=DNS(4)*3600.+DNS(5)*60.+DNS(6)
TIMEST=DNS(1)*3600.+DNS(2)*60.+DNS(3)
IL1=ENS(5)
IL2=ENS(6)
CALL FREQCONV(ENS(1),ENS(2),IL1,IL2 ,FROTATE,FREQHAY,FREQGB) FREQCO
FREQHAY=FREQHAY+1638.
FREQGB=FREQGB+1638.
SLHAI=ENS(3)
DEC=ENS(4)/360.
IBASECOD=ENS(7)
IF(IBASECOD-99) 712,713,712
713 CALL A CARD IN (FNS,NF) ACARDI
BASE=FNS(1)*1000.
BASELHA=FNS(2)+12.
BASEDEC=-FNS(3)
GO TO 714
712 BASE=BX(IBASECOD)+1000.
BASELHA=RH(IBASECOD)+12.
BASEDEC=-BD(IBASECOD)
714 CONTINUE
COSB=COSF(BASEDEC*R)
SINB=SINF(BASEDEC*R)
GO TO (804,805,804,720) IMODE
720 WRITE(59,719)
719 FORMAT(12HENTER JWRITE) FORNUM
CALL FOR NUMS(GNS,1,1)
JWRITE=GNS(1)
721 READ (10) TEST
GO TO (722,723) EOFCKF(10)
722 REWIND 10
GO TO 721
723 READ (10) LHTAPE,MTAPE,NDOP,IPTR,IPTS,IMODE,JNTEG,IWT,INCOH,
1 IRW,IDELAY,ISHIFT,IACUM,IWRITE,CUSB,SINB,BASELHA,DOP,DOPD,
2 TIM ,FREQHAY,FREQGB,SLHAI,DEC,FROTATE,APFRATE,SLHOUR,ASHIFT,
3 DSHIFT
READ (10,488) ((RCOS(I,J),RSIN(I,J),I=1,IPTR),J=1,NDOP)
READ (10,488) (TREAL(K),TIMAG(K),FAMP(K),FASE(K),K=1,IPTS)
GO TO (722,724) EOFCKF(10)
724 IF(LHTAPE.EQ.IHTAPE) 725,721
725 IF(MTAPE.EQ.NTAPE) 726,721
726 IF(JWRITE.EQ.IWRITE) 727,721
727 IACUM=0

```

ENS(4)=DEC*360.

```
GO TO 804
805 AZ=1.32/NWIDE
      BZ=-2.772/(NWIDE*NWIDE)
      DO 800 K=1,IPTS
800 AMOD(K)=AZ*EXPF(BZ*(K-NCENT)**2)
      PRINT 808,(AMOD(K),K=1,IPTS)
808 FORMAT(10X,10F10.4)
      IF(IPTS-30) 807,807,1
807 IF(IPTR-IPTS) 1,809,1
809 IF(INCOH) 1,1,804
804 PRINT 5,IMODE,INTEG,IPTR,IDELAY,IBW,DOP,DOPD,NDOP,TIMEST,
      1 TAPTIME,FREQHAY,FREQGB,SLHAI,ENS(4),IHTAPE,NTAPE
      5 FORMAT(1H1,24HDATA REDUCTION CONSTANTS,///,2X,5HIMODE,17,/,
      1 2X,5HINTEG,17,/,3X,4HIPTR,17,/,1X,6HIDELAY,17,
      2/,4X,3HIBW,110,/,4X,3HDOP,F10.2,/,3X,4HDOPD,
      2 F10.3,/,3X,4HNDOP,110,/,1X,6HTIMEST,F10.2,/,1X,7HTAPTIME,
      3 F10.2,/,1X,7HFREQHAY,F15.8,/,1X,7H FREQGB,F15.8,/,3X,5HSLHAI,
      4 F10.4,/,5X,3HDEC,F10.4,/,3X,5HHTAPE,17,/,3X,5HNTAPE,17,////)
      PRINT 12
      IFGB=IFILEGB-1
      DO 13 I=1,IFGB
13 CALL SEFF(40)
12 FORMAT(1H1,1X,131H IACUM IREC TIME PHASE
1FRINGE RATE DELAY LHA HAY(1) NRAO(1) HAYR GBR
2 SHIFT APF,///)
C INPUT PARAMETERS ENTERED AND SETUP COMPLETED
C SELECT CORRECT FILE AND RECORD ON EACH TAPE
19 CALL READHAY(NC,XXXX,DEC,REF,TIME,IHAY)
GO TO (20,23) SSWTCHF(4)
23 IF(ABSF(TIMEST-TIME)-.18) 20,20,21
21 IF(TIMEST-TIME) 22,20,19
22 REWIND 30
PRINT 24,TIME
24 FORMAT(1X,8H TIME IS,F10.2,8H SECONDS)
GO TO 19
20 CONTINUE
29 CALL READGH(1,IN,INRAO,NWDSIN,NWDSOUT,NPARITY,IDUMP,40)
IREC=IREC+1
GO TO (30,33) SSWTCHF(4)
33 IF(ABSF(TIMEST-(IREC-1)*.2-TAPTIME)-.18) 30,30,31
31 IF(TIMEST-(IREC-1)*.2-TAPTIME) 32,30,29
32 REWIND 40
IREC=0
GO TO 29
30 CONTINUE
IACUM=1
35 CONTINUE
C USE SIDEREAL SECOND IN COMPUTING LOCAL HOUR ANGLE
SLHA=SLHAI/24.+TIME/86164.09
GO TO (910,912) SSWTCHF(6)
910 PRINT 911,TIME
911 FORMAT(1H1, 15HHAYSTACK RECORD, F10.3,10H SECONDS,///)
PRINT 914,(IHAY(!),I=1,NC)
914 FORMAT(2X,8012)
912 CONTINUE
GO TO (920,922) SSWTCHF(6)
920 PRINT 921,IREC
921 FORMAT(1H1, 19HNRAO RECORD, NUMBER,18,///)
PRINT 914.(INRAO(1),I=1,NWDSOUT)
```

READH/
JUMP

READGH


```

C COMPUTE ABSOLUTE DELAY AND DO CROSSCORRELATION
C CORREL IS THE SUBROUTINE WHICH TAKES THE BIT STRINGS FROM EACH TAPE
C AND CROSSCORRELATED THEM. IT MUST BE GIVEN A POSITIVE BIT SHIFT HENC
C IT IS SOMETIMES NECESSARY TO TO SHIFT ONE WORD STRING.
C THE CORRELATION FUNCTION IS STORED IN ICORR, ISTART IS THE BIT NUMBER I
C IHAY WHICH IS MULTIPLIED WITH THE FIRST BIT OF INRAO. ISTOP-ISTART IS
C THE NUMBER OF DELAYS. LAST ARGUMENT IS THE NUMBER OF BITS CORRELATED,
C CORRELATION ARITHMETIC IS 1 X 1 = 0 X 0 = 1, 1 X -1 = -1 X 1 = 0.
MSHIFT=0
ISTART=ISHIFT-IPTR/2+1
ISTOP=ISHIFT+IPTR/2+1
IF(ISTART) 74,74,76
74 MSHIFT=-ISTART/24+1
ISTART=ISTART+MSHIFT*24
ISTOP=ISTOP+MSHIFT*24
76 CONTINUE
DO 40 I=1,9
DSHIFT=DSHIFT+(ASHIFT-ISHIFT)
L=(I-1)*10*IBAND(IBW)+1
LL=L+MSHIFT
IF(LL+10+ISTOP/24+1-97*IBAND(IBW)) 43,43,40
43 IF(MSHIFT) 45,45,46
46 CALL CORREL(ICORR,ISTART,ISTOP,INRAO(LL),IHAY(L),10*IBAND(IBW)) CORRE
GO TO 44
45 CALL CORREL(ICORR,ISTART,ISTOP,INRAO(L),IHAY(L),10*IBAND(IBW)) CORRE
44 CONTINUE
C MULTIPLY BY SINE AND COSINE PHASE
XT=120.*IBAND(IBW)
DO 42 J=1,IPTR
C CONVERT ARITHMETIC , MULTIPLY BY SINE AND COSINE OF PHASE AND ACCUMULA
DO 42 JJ=1,NDOP
RSIN(J,JJ)=RSIN(J,JJ)+(ICORR(J)/XT-1.)*SINPH(I,JJ)
42 RCOS(J,JJ)=RCOS(J,JJ)+(ICORR(J)/XT-1.)*COSPH(I,JJ)
IWRITE=IWRITE+1
GO TO (930,932) SSWTCHF(6)
930 PRINT 931,L,MSHIFT,ISTART,ISTOP,IPTR,ISHIFT
931 FORMAT (1H1,28HCROSSCORRELATION FUNCTION,L=,I6, /1X,13I10, /)
PRINT 933,(ICORR(KJ),KJ=1,IPTR)
933 FORMAT(2X,10I12)
PRINT 935
935 FORMAT(///)
PRINT 934,((RSIN(J,JJ),J=1,IPTR),JJ=1,NDOP)
PRINT 934,((RCOS(J,JJ),J=1,IPTR),JJ=1,NDOP)
934 FORMAT(5X,10F10.5)
932 CONTINUE
40 CONTINUE
IF(INTEG-IACUM) 54,54,48
48 CALL READHAY(NC,XXXX,DEC,REF,TIME,IHAY) READH
CALL READGH(1,IN,INRAO,NWDSIN,NWDSOUT,NPARITY, IDUMP,40) READG
IREC=IREC+1
GO TO (49,47) SSWTCHF(1)
47 IF(NC) 48,54,50
50 IF(NPARITY) 48,54,49
49 IACUM=IACUM+1
GO TO (1,35) SSWTCHF(2)
C
C ENTER TRANSFORM PART OF PROGRAM
54 CONTINUE
IP=IPTR/2+1
SHIFT=DSHIFT/IWRITE
GO TO (666,777,666,666) IMODF

```

```

777 IHBT=IHBT+1
XINCOH=INCOH
XINCOH=SQRTF(XINCOH)
XNORM=PIE*10./(2.*IWRITE*XINCOH)
DO 840 I=1,NDOP
DO 841 K=1,IPTS
RCOS(K,I)=RCOS(K,I)*XNORM
841 PAMP(K,I)=RAMP(K,I)+RCOS(K,I)**2+RSIN(K,I)**2
CALL CPXFOUR(RCOS(1,I),RSIN(1,I),IPTR,TREAL,TIMAG,IPTS,-1,IP,1,WT)CPXFOU
DO 810 K=1,IPTS
TREAL(K)=TREAL(K)+AMOD(K)
810 TIMAG(K)=TIMAG(K)+AMOD(K)
CALL CPXFOUR(TREAL,TIMAG,IPTS,FAMP,FASE,IPTS,1,1,IP,WT) CPXFOU
DO 820 K=1,IPTS
820 TAMP(K,I)=TAMP(K,I)+(FAMP(K)**2+FASE(K)**2)
840 CONTINUE
IF(IHBT-INCOH) 799,780,780
780 DO 785 I=1,NDOP
798 CALL PLOTSCH(RAMP(1,I),RMX,TAMP(1,I),TMX,IPTS) PLOTSC
GO TO (784,785) SSWTCHF(3)
784 WRITE(59,794)
794 FORMAT(15HENTER RMAX,TMAX)
CALL FOR NUMS(GNS,2,2) FORNUM
RMX=GNS(1)
TMX=GNS(2)
GO TO 798
785 CONTINUE
IHBT=0
DO 787 I=1,9
DO 787 K=1,120
RAMP(K,I)=0.
787 TAMP(K,I)=0.
GO TO 783
C COMPLEX FOURIER TRANSFORM FOR SPECTRAL DATA
C COHERENT AVERAGING
C SPECTRA ARE NORMALIZED INSTEAD OF CORRELATION FUNCTIONS SO THAT THE
C LATTER CAN BE ACCUMULATED AFTER TRANSFORM.
666 ANORM=PIE/(2.*IWRITE)
DO 70 I=1,NDOP
PRINT 67,DOPFQ(I),I,IWRITE,SHIFT
67 FORMAT(1H1,F10.3,21B,F10.4)
PRINT 63
63 FORMAT(///,20X,25HSINE CORRELATION FUNCTION,///)
PRINT 68,(RSIN(K,I),K=1,IPTR)
68 FORMAT(5X,10F10.5)
PRINT 64
64 FORMAT(///,20X,27HCOSINE CORRELATION FUNCTION,///)
PRINT 68,(RCOS(K,I),K=1,IPTR)
PRINT 61
61 FORMAT(///,20X,18HWWEIGHTING FUNCTION)
PRINT 68,(WT(K),K=1,IPTR)
C DO COMPLEX FOURIER TRANSFORM ON COMPLEX CORRELATION FUNCTIONS
CALL CPXFOUR(RCOS(1,I),RSIN(1,I),IPTR,TREAL,TIMAG,IPTS,-1,IP,1,WT)CPXFOU
DO 66 K=1,IPTS
TREAL(K)=TREAL(K)+ANORM
TIMAG(K)=TIMAG(K)-ANORM
FAMP(K)=SQRTF(TREAL(K)**2+TIMAG(K)**2)
C KEEP FRINGE PHASE BETWEEN 180 AND -180 DEGREES AND COMPENSATE FOR
C FRACTIONAL BIT SHIFT.
ANG=ATAN(TIMAG(K)/TREAL(K))+
1 (0.5-SIGN(0.5,TREAL(K)))*SIGN(PIE,TIMAG(K))

```

IF(FASE(K)-180.) 190,190,191

191 FASE(K)=FASE(K)-360.
GO TO 66

190 IF(FASE(K)+180.) 192,66,66

192 FASE(K)=FASE(K)+360.

66 CONTINUE

PRINT 90

90 FORMAT(///,20X, 22HREAL FRINGE VISIBILITY,///)

PRINT 68,(TREAL(K),K=1,IPTS)

PRINT 91

91 FORMAT(///,20X, 27HIMAGINARY FRINGE VISIBILITY,///)

PRINT 68,(TIMAG(K),K=1,IPTS)

IQ=IPTS/2+1

ASUM=ASUM+FAMP(IQ)

ASUMSQ=ASUMSQ+FAMP(IQ)*FAMP(IQ)

ASUMR=ASUMR+TREAL(IQ)

ASUMI=ASUMI+TIMAG(IQ)

MSUM=MSUM+1

VAR=ASUMSQ/MSUM-((ASUMR**2+ASUMI**2)/(MSUM*MSUM))

STD=SQRTF(VAR/MSUM)

PRINT 85, ASUM,ASUMSQ,ASUMR,ASUMI,VAR,STD,MSUM

85 FORMAT(///,6F14.5,110)

GO TO (71,75) SSWTCHF(3)

71 WRITE (58,73)

73 FORMAT(1X, 22HENTER FRINGE AMP LIMIT)

CALL FOR NUMS (GNS,1,1)

TMAX=GNS(1)

75 CALL PLOT2V(FAMP,FASE,IPTS,TMAX)

GO TO (71,70) SSWTCHF(3)

70 CONTINUE

C TEST TO SEE IF OUTPUT TAPE ALREADY HAS DATA ON IT.

READ(10) TEST

GO TO (487,485) EOFCKF(10)

485 IF(TEST-PIE) 487,482,487

482 CALL SEFF(10)

487 BACKSPACE 10

C WRITE OUTPUT TAPE

WRITE(10) PIE

WRITE(10) IH1APE,NTAPE,NDOP,IPTR,IPTS,IMODE,INTEG,IWT,INCOH,

1 IBW,IDELAY,ISHIFT,IACUM,IWRITE,COSB,SINB,BASELHA,DOP,DOPD,

2 TIMEST,FREQHAY,FREQGB,SLHAI,DEC,FROTATE,APFRATE,SLHOUR,ASHIFT,

3 DSHIFT

WRITE(10,488) ((RCOS(I,J),RSIN(I,J),I=1,IPTR),J=1,NDOP)

WRITE (10,488) (TREAL(K),TIMAG(K),FAMP(K),FASE(K),K=1,IPTS)

488 FORMAT(6F20.9)

END FILE 10

BACKSPACE 10

IACUM=0

GO TO (793,783) SSWTCHF(5)

793 PRINT 792

792 FORMAT(141,10HACCUMULATE,///)

GO TO 48

783 GO TO (80,81) SSWTCHF(4)

81 WRITE(59,82)

82 FORMAT(16HRUN IS COMPLETED)

GO TO 1

80 PRINT 12

799 DO 611 I=1,200

DO 611 K=1,11

DCOS(I,K)=0.

JUMP 3

FORNUM

PLOT2V

```
611 RSIN(I,K)=0.  
DSHIFT=0.  
IWRITE=0  
GO TO 48  
END
```

3200 FORTRAN DIAGNOSTIC RESULTS - FOR GRENSTAC

ERRCRS

,56

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GRENSTAC I/O 56  
GRENSTAC CK 03 17403
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PROGRAM INTERFER
DIMENSION DX(12), ISOUR(20), BLAT(2), BLONG(2), FLFV(2)
1,IFORM(2), FREQSET(2), ISITE(2), UE(100), VE(100), SH(100)
DIMENSION IAA(1) $IAD=77777B+1655B-LCC(IAA(1)) $IAA(IAD)=14600010B
C THIS PROGRAM COMPUTES OBSERVING PARAMETERS FOR VERY LONG BASELINE
C INTERFEROMETERS
C COMPOSED BY J. MORAN... IMPROVED JAN. 1968
C JUMP 1 ON FOR UV PLANE PLOT
R=3.141592653/180.
C IBASELIN=1, COMPUTE BASE PARAMETERS FROM LAT AND LONG, =2, READ IN
READ 887, IBASELIN
887 FORMAT(I1)
GO TO (888,889) IBASELIN
C COMPUTE BASELINE
888 CALL BASELINE(BLAT, BLONG, ELEV, BASE, BAZ, BEL, BLHA, BDEC, ISITE)      BAESLIN
GO TO 890
889 READ 891, BASE, BAZ, BEL, BLHA, BDEC
891 FORMAT(5F10.4)
C ENTER CODE NUMBERS FOR LO SYNTHESIZER FORMULA
890 READ 4,IFORM(1),IFORM(2)
4 FORMAT(2I2)
C ENTER DATES FOR COMPUTATION
101 READ 1,NMB,NDB,NMF,NDF,NYRTWO      READ
1 FORMAT(5I4)
NYR=NYRTWO+1900
C READ TITLE
READ 7, ISOUR      READ
7 FORMAT(20A4)
ENTER SOURCE COORDINATES AND EPOCH
READ 2, RAHRS, RAMIN, RASEC, DDEG, DMIN, DSEC, IEPO      READ
2 FORMAT(6F7.1, I5)
EPOCH=IEPO
RAH=RAHRS+SIGN(RAMIN,RAHRS)/60.+SIGN(RASEC,RAHRS)/3600.
DECD=DDEG+SIGN(DMIN,DDEG)/60.+SIGN(DSEC,DECD)/3600.
C ENTER FREQUENCY(MC/S) AND VELOCITY (KM/S), BANDCENTER OFFSET(KC/S)
C BANDCENTER OFFSET = BW/2 SO THAT SIGNAL IS CENTERED AT 30 MC + BCO KCS
READ 3, FREK, VEL, BCO      READ
3 FORMAT(3F12.6)
TIMECONV=FREK*3./100.
C TIMECONV IS USED TO CONVERT FROM FREQUENCIES DERIVED FOR UT2 STANDARDS
C TO SETTINGS ON OSCILLATORS USING A1 STANDARDS. I.E. COMPUTER
C FREQUENCIES ARE TOO HIGH IF USED WITH A1 STD SO NUMBERS MUST BE REDUCED
C BY 3 X 10 (EXP 8)
C WX IS FRINGES PER SECOND OF ARC
WX=BASE*FREK*R/(.29979*3600)
DX(1)=31
DX(2)=28
DX(3)=31
DX(4)=30
DX(5)=31
DX(6)=30
DX(7)=31
DX(8)=31
DX(9)=30
DX(10)=31
DX(11)=30
DX(12)=31
NDAYB=0
NDAYF=0
NMP=NMB-1

```

```

DO 5 I=1,NMB
5 NDAYB=NDAYB+DX(I)
  NDAYB=NDAYB+NDB
  NMF=NMF-1
DO 6 I=1,NMF
6 NDAYF=NDAYF+DX(I)
  NDAYF=NDAYF+NDF
  NSUT=0.
DO 1000 NDAY=NDAYB,NDAYF
  INDEX=0
  UT=-1./12.
  EPC=NYR+NDAY/365.
  YEARS=EPC-EPOCH
C  PROCESS COORDINATES
  CALL MOVE(NYR,NMB,NDB,RAH*15.*R,DECC*R,DELA,DELD,DC)      MOVE
  DECP=DECD+DELD/R
  RAHP=RAH+DELA/(15.*R)
102 CONTINUE
  IPAGE=1
  PRINT 98,NDAY,NYR,FREK,VEL,ISCUR,RAH,DECD,EPOCH,RAHP,DECP,EPO,  WRITE
  1 BASE,BAZ,BEL,BLHA,BDEC,TIMECCNV
98  FORMAT(1H1, 9X,4H DAY,15,5H YEAR,15,/,10X,10H FREQUENCY,F12.3,
  1 5H MC/S,/,10X,9H VELOCITY,F10.3,5H KM/S,/,10X,20A4,/,10X,
  2 5H R.A.,F10.3,6H HOURS,10X,4H DEC,F10.3,8H DEGRES,
  3 5X,5HEPOCH,F8.1,/,10X,5H R.A.,F10.3,6H HOURS,10X,4H DEC,
  4 F10.3,8H DEGRES,5X,5HEPOCH,F8.1,
  5 /,10X,9H BASELINE,F10.3,11H KILMETERS,/,10X,8H AZIMUTH,F10.3
  3,4H DEG,10H ELEVATION,F10.3,4H DEG,/,10X,9H BASE LHA,F10.3,
  7 6H HOURS,5H DEC,F10.3,4H DEG,/,10X, 31H FREQ OFFSET FOR TIME CON
8  VERSION,F10.2, 4H CPS)
  PRINT 555, ISITE(1),ISITE(2)
555 FORMAT(/,10X,A4,6H TC ,A4,/)
  DO 519 I=1,2
  GO TO (511,512,513,514,515,516,517) IFORM(I)
511 PRINT 521
521 FORMAT(10X, 48HLO FORMULA, FREQ SYNTHESIZER=FCBS(UT)-1638. MC/S)
  GO TO 519
512 PRINT 522
522 FORMAT(10X, 54HLO FORMULA, FREQ SYNTHESIZER=FOBS(UT)-1638.-.00004
1995)
  GO TO 519
513 PRINT 523
523 FORMAT(10X, 47HLO FORMULA, FREQ SYNTHESIZER=(FCBS(UT)-1610.)/2.)
  GO TO 519
514 PRINT 524
524 FORMAT(10X, 57HLO FORMULA, FREQ SYNTHESIZER=(FCBS(UT)-.00004995-161
10.)/2.)
  GO TO 519
515 PRINT 525
525 FORMAT(10X, 49HLO FORMULA, FREQ SYNTHESIZER=(FRFOBS(UT)-30.)/35.)
  GO TO 519
516 PRINT 526
526 FORMAT(10X, 50HLO FORMULA, FREQ SYNTHESIZER=(FCBS-30.00004995)/35.)
  GO TO 519
517 PRINT 527
527 FORMAT(10X, 29HLINE CENTER FREQUENCY LISTED)
519 CONTINUE
  PRINT 510,RCO
510 FORMAT(/,10X, 37HFREQCBS IS THE LINE CENTER FREQ MINUS,F6.2,5H KC/
1S,/,10X 38HDELAY IS EXCESS DELAY IN STATION 2 DEG,/,10X,
  2 67HFRINGE RATE IS THE APPARENT DECREASE IN OBSERVING FREQ AT STAT
31ON 2)

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```

PRINT 97
97 FORMAT (////, 4X,131H GMT LST(1) LHA(1) LHA(2) VELOCITY WRITE
1 FREQ(1) FREQ(2) ELEV(1) ELEV(2) SX SY DE
2LAY FR RATE POL ANG)
PRINT 500
500 FORMAT(/,4X,130HH M HCURS HOURS HOURS KM/S MC
1/S MC/S DEG DEG CYCLES PER SEC ARC MICROSE
2C CPS DEG,/)
103 CONTINUE
UT=UT+1./12.
IF(UT-24.) 42,42,99
42 NHUT=UT
43 NMUT=(UT-NHUT)*60.+5
IF(NMUT-60) 40,41,41
41 NHUT=NHUT+1
GO TO 43
C COMPUTES VELOCITY WRT LSR, V1, USE COORDINATES OF CURRENT EPOCH
40 CALL DOPCAL(RAHP,0.,0.,DECP,0.,0., NYRTWC,NDAY,NHUT,NMUTDOPCAL
1,NSUT,V1,VE,V,XLST,BLAT(1),ELCNG(1))
C FREQUENCY SHIFT IN KILOCYCLES
C DELFQ IS THE OFFSET FROM REST FREQ DUE TO SOURCE AND SLN
C MC/S
DELFQ=-FREQ*(V1+VEL)/299792.9
FRFQ=FREQ+DELFQ
INTX=XLST
ST=XLST-INTX
STHR=ST*24.
LSTHR=ST*24
LSTMN=(ST-LSTHR/24.)*60.*24.
LSTSC=(ST-LSTHR/24.-LSTMN/1440.)*60.*60.*24.
SLHA=ST*24.-RAHP
SLHB=SLHA-(BLONG(2)-BLONG(1))/15.
IF(SLHA) 23,22,22
23 SLHA=SLHA+24.
22 CONTINUE
CL=COSF(BLAT(1)*R)
SL=SINF(BLAT(1)*R)
SSD=SINF(DECP*R)
CSD=COSF(DECP*R)
XNUM=SINF(SLHA*15*R)*CL
XDEN=CSD*SL-SSD*CL+COSF(SLHA*15.*R)
CALL ARCT(XNUM,XDEN,PANG) ARCT
PANG=PANG/R
CALL ALTPOL(BLAT(1)*R,DECP*R,SLHA*R*15.,SEL,SAZ,ID) ALTPOL
SEL1=SEL/R
IF(SEL) 100,24,24
24 CALL ALTPOL(BLAT(2)*R,DECP*R,SLHB*R*15.,SEL,SAZ,ID)
SEL2=SEL/R
IF(SEL) 100,27,27
27 CALL FRINGE(SLHA,DECP,BASE,SLHA,BDEC,FREQ,FRATE,DELAY,SX,SY) FRINGE
IF(NMUT) 894,892,894
894 IF(NMUT-30) 893,892,893
892 INDEX=INDEX+1
UB(INDEX)=SX
VB(INDEX)=SY
SH(INDEX)=SLHA
893 CONTINUE
C L.O. TRANSLATION FREQUENCIES IN MC/S
FREQORS=FREQ-BCO/1000.
-241-

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C      IFORM ODC   FOR UT TIME STANDARDS,EVEN FOR ATOMIC TIME STANDARDS
C      IFORM=1    HAYSTACK 67 MC/S SYSTEM
C      IFORM=3    NRAO RHODE AND SCHWARTZ SYSTEM
C      IFORM=5    BERKELEY MULTIPLICATION SYSTEM
C      IFORM=6    STRAIGHT
      DO 529 L=1,2
      GO TO (551,552) L
552  FREQOBS=FREQOBS-FRATE/1000000.
551  GO TO (531,532,533,534,535,536,537) IFORM(L)
531  FREQSET(L)=FREQOBS-1638.
      GO TO 529
532  FREQSET(L)=FREQOBS-1638.-TIMECONV/1000000.
      GO TO 529
533  FREQSET(L)=(FREQOBS-1610.)/2.
      GO TO 529
534  FREQSET(L)=(FREQOBS-1610.000-TIMECONV/1000000.)/2.
      GO TO 529
535  FREQSET(L)=(FREQOBS-30.)/35.
      GO TO 529
536  FREQSET(L)=(FREQOBS-30.-TIMECCNV/1000000.)/35.
      GO TO 529
537  FREQSET(L)=FREQOBS+.003
529  CONTINUE
      PRINT 25,NHUT,NMUT,STHR,SLHA,SLFB,V1,FREQSET(1),FREQSET(2),SEL1,
1SEL2,SX,SY,DELAY,FRATE,PANG
      25  FORMAT(1X,2I4,3X,F9.4,3F8.3,2F14.8,2F8.2,2F10.2,F10.1,F9.2,F7.1)
      IPAGE=IPAGE+1
100  CONTINUE
      IF(IPAGE-30) 103,103,102
      99  CONTINUE
      GO TO (897,1000) SSWTCHF(1)
897  CALL PLOTUV(UB,VB,SH,WX,INDEX)
1000 CONTINUE
      GO TO 101
      END

```

PLETL

3200 FORTRAN DIAGNOSTIC RESULTS - FOR INTERFER

ERRCRS

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SUBROUTINE BASELINE(BLAT,BLONG,ELEV,D,AZ,EL,BLHA,DEC,ISITE)
C APRIL 20,1967 THIS PROGRAM COMPUTES THE BASELINE VECTOR BETWEEN
C ANY TWO POINTS ON THE EARTH, THE COORDINATES ARE GIVEN IN BOTH
C LOCAL HOUR ANGLE AND DECLINATION AND IN AZIMUTH AND ELEVATION
C AS SEEN FROM SITE ONE. SHAPE OF EARTH FROM EPHEMERIS
C BASELINE VECTOR IS FROM SITE ONE TO SIT TWO
C ENTER GEODETIC LATITUDES
C BASELINE COORDINATES ARE REFERENCED TO POSITION 1
C DIMENSION BLONG(2),BLAT(2),ELEV(2),P(2),Q(2),CLA(2),SLA(2),
1 CLO(2),SLO(2),ELATGC(2),ISITE(2)
R=3.141592653/180.
A=6378388.
C 1 COORDINATES OF HAYSTACK
C 2 COORDINATES OF NRAO 140
DO 4 I=1,2
READ 3,BLATD,BLATM,BLATS,BLONGD,BLONGM,BLONGS,ELEVAT,ISIT
3 FORMAT(7F10.4,A4)
BLAT(I)=BLATD+SIGN(BLATM,BLATD)/60.+SIGN(BLATS,BLATD)/3600.
BLONG(I)=BLONGD+SIGN(BLONGM,BLONGD)/60.+SIGN(BLONGS,BLONGD)/3600.
ISITE(I)=ISIT
4 ELEV(I)=ELEVAT.
C CONVERT LATITUDES TO GEOCENTRIC LATITUDES
BLATGC(1)=BLAT(1)-(11./60.+35.6635 /3600.)*SINF(2.*BLAT(1)*R)+
1 (1.1731/3600.)*SINF(4.*BLAT(1)*R)-(.0026/3600.)*SINF(6.*BLAT(1)*R)
BLATGC(2)=BLAT(2)-(11./60.+35.6635 /3600.)*SINF(2.*BLAT(2)*R)+
1 (1.1731/3600.)*SINF(4.*BLAT(2)*R)-(.0026/3600.)*SINF(6.*BLAT(2)*R)
C Q IS SITE RADIUS VECTOR LENGTH BASED ON STANDARD ELLIPSOID
DO 1 I=1,2
CLO(I)=COSF(BLONG(I)*R)
SLO(I)=SINF(BLONG(I)*R)
CLA(I)=COSF(BLATGC(I)*R)
SLA(I)=SINF(BLATGC(I)*R)
P(I)=.998320047+.001683494*COSF(2.*BLAT(I)*R)-
1 .000003549*COSF(4.*BLAT(I)*R)+.000000008*COSF(6.*BLAT(I)*R)
1 Q(I)=A*P(I)+ELEV(I)
CDEL=COSF((BLONG(2)-BLONG(1))*R)
SDEL=SINF((BLONG(2)-BLONG(1))*R)
CA=SLA(1)*SLA(2)+CLA(1)*CLA(2)+CDEL
C ALPHA IS ANGLE BETWEEN SITE VECTORS
ALPHA=ACOSF(CA)/R
D=SQRTF(Q(1)**2+Q(2)**2-2.*Q(1)*Q(2)*CA)
D=D/1000.
C CARTESIAN COMPONENTS OF BASELINE VECTOR
C SITE VECTOR 1 IS IN BZ,BY PLANE
BX=Q(2)*CLA(2)*SLO(2)-Q(1)*CLA(1)*SLO(1)
BY=Q(2)*CLA(2)*CLO(2)-Q(1)*CLA(1)*CLO(1)
BZ=Q(2)*SLA(2)-Q(1)*SLA(1)
DEC=ATANF(BZ/SQRTF(BX**2+BY**2))
CALL ARCT(BX,BY,BLHA)
BLHA=BLHA-BLONG(1)*R
C COMPUTE AZ AND EL
SEL=SLA(1)*SINF(DEC)+CLA(1)*COSF(DEC)*COSF(BLHA)
CEL=SQRTF(1.-SEL**2)
SINA=-COSF(DEC)*SINF(BLHA)
COSA=SINF(DEC)*CLA(1)-COSF(DEC)*COSF(BLHA)*SLA(1)
CALL ARCT(SINA,COSA,ANG)
AZ=ANG/R
DEC=DEC/R
BLHA=BLHA/(15.*R)
FL=ASINF(SEL)/R

```

```
PRINT 2,ISITE(1),ISITE(2),BLAT(1),BLAT(2),BLATGC(1),BLATGC(2),  
1 BLONG(1),BLONG(2),ELEV(1),ELEV(2),
```

```
1 P(1),P(2),Q(1),Q(2),ALPHA,BX,BY,BZ,BLHA,DEC,AZ,EL,D  
2 FORMAT(1H1,10X,16 HBASELINE FROM ,A4,7H TO ,A4,///,10X,  
1 21H GEODETIC LATITUDES,2F20.6,///,  
1 10X,21H GEOCENTRIC LATITUDES,2F20.6,///,  
1 21X,11H LONGITUDES,2F20.6,///,20X,8H HEIGHTS,2F20.1,///,10X,  
2 18H FRACTIONAL RADII,2F20.9,///,20X,7H RADII ,2F20.1,  
3 7H METERS,///,20X,6H ALPHA,F20.4,///,20X,9H BX,BY,BZ,3F20.1,///,  
4 20X,7H LHA,DEC,2F20.6,///,20X,7H AZ,EL,2F20.6,///,20X,5H BASE,  
5 F20.4,12H KILOMETERS)  
RETURN  
END
```

3200 FORTRAN DIAGNOSTIC RESULTS - FOR BASELINE

ERRORS

AD,56

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BASELINE I/O 56  
BASELINE I/O 56  
BASELINE I/O 56
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SURROUTINE FRINGE(SLHA,SDEC,BASE,ELHA,BDEC,FREQ,FRATE,DELAY,SX,SY)
C   BASELINE IS FROM SITE 1 TO SITE 2
C   DELAY IS EXCESS DELAY TO SITE 2
C   FRINGE RATE IS APPARENT DECREASE IN FREQ AT SITE 2
R=3.141592653/180,
CSD=COSF(SDEC*R)
SSD=SINF(SDEC*R)
CBD=COSF(BDEC*R)
SBD=SINF(BDEC*R)
ANG=(SLHA-BLHA)*R*15.
W=FREQ*BASE/.2997929
C   COSINE OF ANGLE BETWEEN BASELINE AND LINE TO SOURCE
CETA=SSD*SBD+CSD*CBD*COSF(ANG)
C   DELAY IN MICROSECONDS
DELAY=-BASE*CETA/.2997929
C   .25 DEGREES PER MINUTE OF TIME
FRATE=+W*CBD*CSD*SINF(ANG)
C   SIDEREAL TIME
FRATE=FRATE*2.*3.141592653/(86164.09)
WP=W*R/3600,
C   CYCLES PER SECOND OF ARC
SX=WP*CBD*SINF(ANG)
SY=WP*(CSD*SBD-CBD*SSD*COSF(ANG))
RETURN
END

```

3200 FORTRAN DIAGNOSTIC RESULTS - FCR FRINGE

ERRCRS

AD.56

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